

Arboviral and zoonotic diseases in Libya: A joint WHO-ISS intervention to mitigate threats using the One Health approach

Workshop

« One Health integrated surveillance for priority zoonotic and vector-borne diseases in Libya »

Tunis, 7-11 July 2025

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Acronyms

ESA: Environmental Sanitation Affairs

FAO: Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations

FDCC: Food and Drug Control Center

GIS: Geographic Information System

IHR NFP: International Health Regulations National Focal Point

ISS: Istituto Superiore di Sanità (Italian National Institute of Health)

MoA: Ministry of Agriculture

MOE: Ministry of Environment

MOH: Ministry of Health

MoLG: Ministry of Local Governance

NCAH: National Center of Animal Health

NCDC: National Center for Disease Control

NBW: National Bridging Workshop

OH: One Health

PEP: Post-Exposure Prophylaxis

PVBDs: Priority Vector-Borne Diseases

PZDs: Priority Zoonotic Diseases

RRTs: Rapid Response Teams

RVFV: Rift Valley Fever Virus

SOPs: Standard Operating Procedures

UNEP: United Nations Environment Programme

VBDs: Vector-Borne Diseases

WHO: World Health Organization

WOAH: World Organization for Animal Health

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Background

Multisectoral approaches, such as One Health (OH), have been recognized as the best approaches for the prevention and preparedness of threats emerging at the human-animal-environment interface to support global health security.¹ Therefore, the OH approach needs to be adopted in surveillance systems for zoonotic and vector-borne disease (VBDs), so as to promptly assess the multiple potential risk factors that are involved before they become a threat and to guide relevant actions.² Conventional disease surveillance is usually siloed by sectors, with separate systems addressing the health of humans, domestic animals, cultivated plants, wildlife and the environment.

Libya, as other countries, faces ongoing threats from the emergence and re-emergence of zoonotic and VBDs. These threats are exacerbated by the limited integration of surveillance systems across human, animal, and environmental health sectors.

In line with the One Health Joint Plan of Action (2022–2026)³ and the One Health High level Expert Panel⁴ a key priority is the establishment of integrated OH surveillance systems,

¹ OHHLEP (One Health High-Level Expert Panel). (2023a). One Health action for health security and equity. *Lancet (London, England)*, 401(10376), 530–533. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(23\)00086-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(23)00086-7)

² Dente, M. G., Riccardo, F., Nacca, G., Ranghiasi, A., Escadafal, C., Gaayeb, L., Jiménez-Clavero, M. A., Manuguerra, J. C., Picard, M., Fernández-Pinero, J., Pérez-Ramírez, E., Robert, V., Victoir, K., & Declich, S. (2018). Strengthening Preparedness for Arbovirus Infections in Mediterranean and Black Sea Countries: A Conceptual Framework to Assess Integrated Surveillance in the Context of the One Health Strategy. *International journal of environmental research and public health*, 15(3), 489. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph15030489>

³ FAO, UNEP, WOA, & WHO. (2022). *One Health Joint Plan of Action, 2022–2026*. World Health Organization; Geneva, Switzerland. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.4060/cc2289en>

⁴ One Health High-Level Expert Panel (OHHLEP), Hayman, D. T. S., Adisasmito, W. B., Almuhairi, S., Behravesh, C. B., Bilivogui, P., Bukachi, S. A., Casas, N., Becerra, N. C., Charron, D. F., Chaudhary, A., Ciacci Zanella, J. R., Cunningham, A. A., Dar, O., Debnath, N., Dungu, B., Farag, E., Gao, G. F., Khaita, M., Machalaba, C., ... Koopmans, M. (2023). Developing One Health surveillance systems. *One health (Amsterdam, Netherlands)*, 17, 100617. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.onehlt.2023.100617>

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including the development of joint surveillance protocols. These mechanisms will enable early detection, timely information sharing, and coordinated response efforts across the human, animal, and environmental health sectors. Strengthening collaboration among key stakeholders from different sectors at all levels, will enhance the country's capacity to monitor, prevent, and control zoonotic and VBDs. This OH approach will also contribute to building resilient health systems, improving outbreak preparedness, and reducing the overall burden of disease in Libya, as in other countries.

From the 23rd to 25th of February 2025, the National Bridging Workshop (NBW) for OH in Libya was held in Tripoli. The workshop was hosted at the kind invitation of the Government of Libya, with organizational support from the World Health Organization (WHO), the World Organization for Animal Health (WOAH), the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) and United Nations Environment Program (UNEP) and in collaboration with Istituto Superiore di Sanità (ISS – the Italian National Institute of Health). One of the objectives of the roadmap produced during the workshop was to develop national joint surveillance systems for OH related threats.

Within the project “Arboviral and zoonotic diseases in Libya: A joint WHO–ISS intervention to mitigate threats using the OH approach” funded by the Italian Cooperation and co-implemented by WHO Libya and ISS a situation analysis study explored how the OH approach could be adopted in the surveillance of zoonotic and VBDs in Libya and what are the challenges (Annex 1 – Situation analysis). Rift Valley fever Virus (RVF//V) and Rabies were used as case studies. Currently the surveillance systems for these diseases are mainly sectoral. For RVF/V the gaps to develop a OH surveillance system were identified in the need for joint protocols/standard operation procedures (SOPs) for surveillance, training of the OH workforce engaged in the surveillance and diagnosis of the pathogen, and the establishment of OH Rapid Response Teams (RRT). For Rabies the priorities identified were the

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development of joint protocols/SOPs for surveillance and control, building national laboratory capacities, the establishment of vaccination teams, and the training of the OH workforce.

Based on these results a five-day workshop “Strengthening One Health Integrated Surveillance for Priority Zoonotic Diseases in Libya” was organized in Tunis from 7 to 11 July 2025 within the framework of the WHO-ISS project, and whose main aim was to design OH surveillance systems for priority zoonotic diseases (PZDs) and priority VBDs (PVBDs) in Libya and develop joint protocols for their surveillance.

Aim and objectives

The main aim of the workshop was to provide an opportunity for the Libyan stakeholders to brainstorm in multisectoral groups and co-design using OH approach the joint surveillance of PZDs and PVBDs in Libya, and identify multisectoral surveillance actions for the development of OH surveillance protocols. Over the course of five days, the Libyan stakeholders from national institutions from different sectors worked in multisectoral groups to:

- Identify OH surveillance scope, actors and characteristics for PZDs and PVBDs in Libya;
- Agree on joint surveillance activities to be performed to establish a OH surveillance system for PZDs and PVBDs in Libya;
- Design the OH surveillance system for PZDs and PVBDs in Libya and describe the necessary requirements in terms of resources, capacities and governance framework to implement the activities;

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- Outline the next steps in the short and long term to develop the OH surveillance system for the PZDs and PVBDs in Libya;
- Identify the strategic technical pillars of Libya's OH strategy.

Stakeholders

The workshop engaged 23 participants from Libyan Institutions (Annex 2 - participants) covering zoonotic and vector-borne diseases surveillance activities:

- Public health services representatives (Ministry of Health, National Center for Disease Control)
- Animal health representatives (Ministry of Agriculture, National Center for Animal Health)
- Environmental health representatives (Ministry of Environment, Environmental Sanitation Affairs)
- Food and Drug Control services representatives (Food and Drug Control Center)
- National International Health Regulations Focal Point
- Academia (Medicine and Veterinary faculty)

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Methods

Developing OH surveillance systems is challenging, therefore, a step-wise approach was adopted during the five-day multisectoral workshop organized from the 7th to the 11th July 2025. The gaps to the current surveillance system were identified and progressive adaptations towards a OH approach to surveillance were proposed, in the short term, if considered minor adaptations, or in the long term, if considered major adaptations. The first day of the workshop focused on an introduction about OH surveillance of zoonoses and VBDs. The three following days of the workshop were dedicated to co-design OH surveillance approaches for PZDs and PVBDs in Libya, and identify multisectoral actions for the development of OH surveillance protocols (a document describing the design and the joint actions needed to develop a OH surveillance system). The last day was devoted to define the pillars of the OH strategy in Libya (Annex 3 – Agenda of the workshop).

The stakeholders were divided in three groups according to the pathogen way of transmission (Rabies, Brucellosis, VBDs– including RVFV, Leishmaniasis and Dengue). Group discussion leaders were selected from the participants for each group and engaged before the workshop.

The methodology adopted during the workshop was based on the findings of previous studies about the development of OH surveillance systems implemented by ISS in other

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countries^{5,6,7} and the Italian National Plan for Prevention of Arboviruses, one of the first national plan for the prevention, control and surveillance of Arboviruses, developed with a OH approach. Multisectoral actions according to the different pillars of OH surveillance (routine data collection and reporting, joint risk assessment and reduction, coordinated early warning and preparedness, data collection and reporting during the epizootic/epidemic period, cross-cutting activities) were listed in a template (Annex 4 - Template). For each action the three multisectoral groups needed to describe the joint activities, responsible, timeframe, means and assumptions (barriers to be addressed to implement the activity). The groups were also asked to co-design the OH surveillance systems and identify milestones in the short and long term to develop the OH surveillance system.

The analysis of the templates describing the multisectoral actions and the flow of information drafted during the workshop supported the development of this report that, together with the templates, should be considered the protocol to guide the development of a OH surveillance system for the selected PZDs and PVBDs in Libya.

Results

⁵ Milano, A.; Robbiati, C.; Declich, S.; Calistri, P.; Pediconi, O.; Amato, L.; Paronyan, L.; Avetisyan, L.; Manucharyan, A.; Avetisyan, G.; et al. Assessing the Adoption of One Health Approaches in National Plans to Combat Health Threats: The Pilot of a One Health Conceptual Framework in Armenia. *Trop. Med. Infect. Dis.* 2024, 9, 22. <https://doi.org/10.3390/tropicalmed9010022>

⁶ Dente MG, Riccardo F, Bolicci F, et al. *Implementation of the One Health approach to fight arbovirus infections in the Mediterranean and Black Sea Region: Assessing integrated surveillance in Serbia, Tunisia and Georgia.* *Zoonoses Public Health.* 2019;66(3):276-287. doi:10.1111/zph.12562

⁷ Robbiati, C., Milano, A., Habib, M., Declich, S., Dente, M. G., & On behalf of the study working group. (2024). *MediLabSecure One Health Situation Analysis (OHMeSA) in Montenegro.* MediLabSecure Project. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10631734>

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The priority zoonotic and vector-borne diseases

Following a discussion with the participants, and on the basis of the PZDS and PVBDs identified as a priority during the OH prioritization exercise organized by WHO Libya on September 3-5, 2024 in Tripoli, it was deemed worthwhile devoting the workshop to the development of OH surveillance protocols for Rabies, Brucellosis, RVF/V, Leishmaniasis, and Dengue.

Epidemiological situation and case definitions

Rabies

Rabies is not endemic in Libya, with sporadic cases in humans and animals (domestic and stray). Definition for human case of rabies and animal bite are reported in the National Guidelines for Surveillance. No definition for animal rabies case is available.

Brucellosis

Brucellosis is endemic in Libya, reflecting ongoing transmission linked to animal reservoirs, especially goats, sheep, and cattle, which are the main sources of *Brucella melitensis* and *B. abortus* infections in humans. The disease prevalence ranging from 6–30% across endemic regions, indicating notable exposure risk in Libya’s rural and pastoral areas. The disease likely remains under-diagnosed and under-reported, consistent with patterns seen across similar regional contexts.

Vector Borne Diseases

- **RVF/V:** Libya is at significant risk of RVF emergence due to multiple environmental, ecological, and systemic vulnerabilities:
 1. **Geographical and Ecological Risk:** Libya shares long, porous borders with Sudan, Chad, and Niger, where RVF is endemic, and Egypt, which has

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recorded major outbreaks. These borders facilitate cross-border livestock movement, a key driver of RVFV introduction

2. Presence of Competent Vectors: The *Aedes* and *Culex* mosquito species capable of transmitting RVFV are widely present in Libya. The climatic conditions, particularly heavy rains and temporary flooding—create ideal breeding sites, increasing the risk of vector proliferation and virus amplification

3. Susceptible Animal Population: Libya maintains a large population of susceptible domestic ruminants (sheep, goats, cattle, and camels). Low herd immunity in animals increases the likelihood of widespread transmission once the virus is introduced

4. Weak Surveillance and Response Systems: Weak veterinary and public health infrastructures, limited diagnostic capacity, and low preparedness for RVF detection or containment. These factors increase the risk that an introduction could go undetected until major human and animal outbreaks occur.

- **Dengue:** Dengue fever has not yet been reported as endemic in Libya, but the country remains ecologically vulnerable due to the presence of *Aedes* mosquito species, climatic suitability, and increasing urbanization. Although no confirmed local transmission has been documented, imported cases in travelers transiting through Libya suggest potential exposure pathways⁸. Weak surveillance, limited diagnostic capacity, and underreporting of febrile illnesses make it difficult to determine the true extent of risk. Given its geographic proximity to endemic regions and cross-border human mobility, Libya faces a threat of dengue introduction and establishment, underscoring the need to strengthen arboviral surveillance, vector control, and One Health preparedness systems to prevent future outbreaks.
- **Leishmaniasis:** Leishmaniasis is one of Libya’s most persistent endemic zoonotic diseases, transmitted by Phlebotomus sandflies and caused mainly by *Leishmania major* (Zoonotic Cutaneous Leishmaniasis – ZCL) and *L. tropica* (Anthroponotic Cutaneous Leishmaniasis – ACL).

⁸ Fiore V, Caruana G, Are R, Peruzzo F, Bagella P, Naitana A, Salis T, Babudieri S, Madeddu G. “Emerging arbovirolosis in Italy: report on 8 cases of imported Dengue virus infection in Sardinia.” *Infectious Diseases & Tropical Medicine*, 2017; 3(1): e366.

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Rodents (*Psammomys obesus*, *Meriones libycus*) act as the principal reservoirs, while domestic dogs are reservoirs for visceral forms (*L. infantum*). The disease remains a major public health problem, aggravated by underreporting, population displacement, and weak surveillance due to ongoing conflict.

One Health surveillance system: minor adaptations

From the analysis of the template filled by the participants during the workshop (Annex 5,6,7 – Templates filled by the participants) the following information was summarized.

Rabies

Aim and objectives of the OH surveillance system

The main aim of OH surveillance for Rabies would be to enable early detection and timely response to outbreaks and to understand the burden of the disease.

The specific objectives are:

- Timely reporting of animal bites and suspected human rabies cases.
- Timely reporting suspected animal rabies cases.
- Monitoring the administration and effectiveness of the post-exposure prophylaxis (PEP), especially in high-risk communities.

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Actors engaged

Municipal/Local level: Public and private veterinary clinics, healthcare facilities, Rapid Response Teams (RRTs).

National Level: NCAH (Surveillance Directorate, Zoonotic Directorate), NCDC (Surveillance Directorate, Zoonotic Directorate), ESA.

International organizations: WHO, WOA, FAO.

Type, seasonality and geographical area

Passive continuous surveillance of animal bite cases and suspected rabies cases (human and animal) at country level.

In the areas at risk (western mountains region, the cities near the western border of Libya with Tunisia) increased risk assessment activities need to be performed.

Data collection and reporting during epizootic/epidemic period

For Rabies each case is considered an epizootic/epidemic. Epidemiological information from RRT and vet clinics (public and private) is exchanged among sectoral focal points at the level of municipality through mobile phone and official letter immediately when a trigger is present (Figure 1). After field investigation a report is shared between human and animal health sectors at municipality level. Vertical notification between municipal and national level is in charge of each sector and should happen by phone calls followed by official letters immediately when a trigger is present.

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Figure 1: Design of the first adaptations towards a OH surveillance system for Rabies showing information sharing between actors (green arrows), while red arrows indicate notification ways (Annex 8 – Digitalized version).

Joint risk assessment and reduction

Annual risk assessment is performed by the focal points at the local level in the areas at risk through a joint risk assessment tool/checklist. GIS maps may be used where feasible; however, their application in the short term may be challenging, and simpler risk-mapping approaches will be applied initially. The information is analyzed by OH epidemiologists at central level. A report is shared by each focal point with the national sectoral entity who

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sends feedback about strategies to be adopted. Community awareness campaigns are performed based on risk.

Coordinated early warning and preparedness

After implementing annual risk assessments, the municipality focal points produce a report including preparedness recommendations and share it with the national sectors. When events consistent with a potential outbreak are reported from the focal points they are jointly investigated and the reports shared with the national sectoral referents.

Brucellosis

Aim and objectives of the OH surveillance system

The main aim of OH surveillance for Brucellosis is to detect and confirm index or suspected cases in humans and animals through diagnostic techniques.

The specific objectives are:

- Establish effective communication channels for coordinated reporting between the animal and human health sectors.
- Sharing surveillance data across all relevant sectors and levels.

Actors engaged

Alert Level: Farmers, slaughterhouses, point of entry, traders, factories.

Local/Municipal level: Public veterinary clinics, private veterinary clinics, health facilities.

National Level: NCAH (Surveillance Directorate, Zoonotic Directorate), NCDC (Surveillance

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Directorate, Zoonotic Directorate), RRTs, ESA.

International Level: WHO, WOA, INFOSAN.

Type, seasonality and geographical area

Passive surveillance of human cases, and active surveillance of animal cases. Surveillance activities are carried out all-year round and across the entire country. The specific modalities for active animal surveillance are still to be defined by national stakeholders; possible approaches may include risk-based serology, sentinel sites, and abattoir-based surveillance.

Routine data collection and reporting (*epizootic/epidemic period*)

Epidemiological information is reported by NCAH local focal points to NCDC and ESA local focal points and NCAH, NCDC, ESA at national level monthly (*right away after a signal*) through a report (*urgent notifications may be transmitted through phone calls or WhatsApp, followed by official communication*) (Figure 2.). At the national level, data are exchanged monthly between NCAH and NCDC (*right away after an alert*). Data exchanges are carried out through the communication channels routinely used by the institutions, based on available resources and existing coordination practices.

Community awareness campaigns are jointly organized in high-risk areas, especially after human cases and during periods of increased risk.

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Figure 2: Design of the first adaptations towards a OH surveillance system for Brucellosis showing information sharing (dotted arrows) between actors, while solid arrows indicate notification ways. Different colors refer to different levels (red alert, green municipality, blue and red central, black international) (Annex 9 – Digitalized version).

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Joint risk assessment and reduction

A nationally coordinated joint task force directs annual assessments to identify areas at risk of Brucellosis transmission. High-risk areas include those with dense livestock populations (sheep, goats, cattle, camels), traditional animal husbandry practices, limited vaccination coverage, previously reported cases, and bordering regions with frequent animal movement. Tools such as checklists, incidence forms and risk assessment matrices, are routinely applied to categorize risks and determine control measures. GIS mapping may be introduced in the longer term as capacities and resources expand. Findings are compiled into joint reports shared with national authorities and used to guide community awareness campaigns in at-risk areas.

Coordinated early warning and preparedness

Once an alert is received, suspicious events or cases in humans or animals are reported immediately through established sectoral reporting lines. During high-risk periods, communication occurs daily or weekly, while in normal periods it is maintained monthly or quarterly. Early warning activities include the rapid exchange of signals between sectors, preliminary joint assessments to qualify the alert, and the activation of local response teams when needed. Preparedness measures rely on the procedures routinely followed by the institutions and the communication channels agreed among the sectors to ensure timely coordination. Where relevant, the information is consolidated at national level to support decision-making and guide early risk reduction actions.

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Vector-borne diseases

Aim of the OH surveillance system

Develop early warning systems linking meteorological data, vector density, and livestock health/human health.

Specific objectives for RVF/V

- Monitor animal abortions, fever in herds, and wildlife mortality as trigger points.
- Incorporate entomological and virological data for forecasting
- Integrate data from veterinary labs, environmental sensors, and human clinics.
- Link outbreak alerts to rapid joint interventions in high-risk zones.

Specific objectives for Dengue

- Early detection and prevention of dengue virus introduction and transmission through integrated human, entomological, and environmental surveillance in high-risk areas.
- Monitor the presence, abundance of Aedes mosquito vectors to identify potential hotspots and guide vector-control interventions.
- Strengthen diagnostic and laboratory capacity for timely confirmation of dengue infection in humans and vectors.
- Assess climate, environmental, and urban factors contributing to dengue risk and integrate them into national arboviral preparedness and adaptation plans.

Specific objectives for Leishmaniasis

- Detect and monitor transmission trends of cutaneous and visceral leishmaniasis in humans and animals
- Strengthen entomological surveillance of Phlebotomus sandflies (density, seasonality, infection rate) to anticipate seasonal peaks and guide control operations.
- Enhance diagnostic, reporting, and response capacities

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Actors engaged

Local level: local officers of NCAH, surveillance teams of NCDC, local officers of ESA, monitoring officers of MOE, other relevant stakeholders (e.g. waste management, livestock/slaughterhouse, inspectors, entomologists, food safety officers);

National level: NCAH, NCDC, ESA, MOE and One Health Steering Committee

International organizations: WHO, WOA, FAO, UNEP

Type, seasonality and geographical area for RVF/V

Human cases: Passive case detection at health facilities and active case finding through mobile clinics all year round in the southern region and western livestock markets.

Animal cases: Passive surveillance (syndromic monitoring of sentinel livestock and event-based reporting of abortions) all year round in the southern region and western livestock markets. Seasonal serosurveys and field investigations in high-risk areas during transmission season.

Environmental health: Entomological larval survey and GIS risk mapping monthly (December-March) and bi-weekly (April-November).

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Type, seasonality and geographical area for Dengue

Human cases: No confirmed local outbreaks, but Libya remains at risk due to regional circulation of dengue in MENA (Humphrey et al., 2016).

Vector activity: *Aedes aegypti* and *Aedes albopictus* surveillance is focused on urban and peri-urban areas during the warm season April–November, when climatic conditions support vector breeding.

Geographical areas: Coastal and urban zones with suitable humidity and water-storage conditions.

Type, seasonality and geographical area for Leishmaniasis

Human cases: Reported throughout the year, with most cutaneous leishmaniasis cases occurring between November and March, consistent with Libya’s national CL seasonality.

Animal cases: Sporadic detection year-round in dogs and livestock in endemic areas.

Vector activity: *Phlebotomus* sand flies are active April to November, with peaks in June and September, as shown in Libyan entomological studies.

Geographical areas: Mainly western and northwestern regions, including Al-Rabta, Al-Jabal Al-Gharbi, and peri-urban areas.

Routine data collection and reporting (*epizootic/epidemic period*)

Joint field data collection every two months by the local focal points at municipal level through standardized forms (*weekly*) (Figure 3). Exchange of epidemiological information between the municipal focal points weekly and monthly through meetings, excel sheets and reporting templates and WhatsApp for initial or urgent communications (*daily*). Following joint data analysis and interpretation, reports are produced and sent by each sector to its respective national entity.

At national level, NCAH, NCDC, ESA, and MOE consolidate these inputs through joint reporting to the OH Steering Committee, which coordinates the national response.

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Formal notification (red arrows in Figure X) is made from local to national level and from national authorities to international organizations (WHO, WOAH, FAO, UNEP). Investigations (black arrows) are conducted jointly by sectoral teams, and primary response actions (green arrows) are implemented locally with national support.

Figure 3: Design of the first adaptations towards a OH surveillance system for VBDs (RVFV was used as a proxy) showing information sharing and collaboration between actors for reporting and

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notification (red arrows), investigation (black arrows) and response (green arrows) (Annex – 10 Digitalized version).

Joint risk assessment and reduction

Annual risk assessment is performed a national OH task force team twice a year in the areas at risk through a joint risk assessment tools/checklists and GIS maps and the information is analyzed by the team. A report is shared by each focal points with the national sectoral entity who send feedback about strategies to be adopted. Community awareness campaigns are performed based on risk.

Coordinated early warning and preparedness

When events consistent with a potential outbreak are identified an alert is launched by the national OH task force through SMS/WhatsApp to the municipal level to engage in response actions based on readiness protocols reviewed monthly.

Cross-cutting activities

Cross-cutting activities to the different surveillance activities and diseases should be considered:

- Joint governance mechanism at national level (OH taskforce) to coordinate and review surveillance activities.
- Definition, agreement and update of joint indicators for the minimum information to be shared for each disease.
- Planning and implementation of joint trainings and monitoring and evaluation activities (i.e. simulation exercises).
- Sharing of diagnostic capacities (equipment, material, expertise) among sectors when feasible.

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- Develop joint agreements with partners (e.g. universities, private sector, non-governmental organizations) to support surveillance activities e.g. data collection in the field, community awareness.

OH surveillance system: major adaptations

The OH surveillance systems drafted during the workshop for the different PZDs and PVBDs included minor adaptations mainly in terms of information sharing between sectors. To strengthen the level of OH integration within the system, information-exchange pathways among sectors should be streamlined by enhancing coordination at both local and national levels. Therefore, some major adaptations at structural level should be promoted in the long term, by favoring the integration of surveillance systems across sectors, levels and diseases (in line with the concept of integrated surveillance) to maximize resources and efforts. This “advanced” OH surveillance system suggested here (Figure 4) is based on opportunities that emerged during the workshop, such as: reinforce capacity at municipality level (human resources, equipment, material, training) including lab capacities; consolidate the OH task force to advocate for the adaption of the legal framework for the necessary communication, collaboration and sharing across sectors (also for laboratories) and ensuring sustainable funding via public-private partnerships and UN grants; develop joint SOPs and forms (standardized across municipalities); adopt data tools such as dashboards and GIS to assess risk; establish event-based surveillance systems at community level made of governmental and non-governmental actors; engage actively communities.

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Figure 4: The flow of information in the OH surveillance system (long term)

The actors

Community surveillance team: workers from healthcare facilities, vet clinics (public and private), farmers, community members that should support event-based surveillance activities.

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Municipality One Health team: NCDC surveillance officers and rapid response teams, NCAH surveillance officers, environmental officers, which constitutes the One Health Rapid Response teams slaughterhouses officers, food inspection officers, waste management officers (different roles according to the disease).

National OH task force: MoH, MoA, MoLG, MOE, NCDC, NCAH, ESA, FDCC

OH steering committee: Serves as the highest national decision-making under the Libya One Health MoU. It ensures strategic leadership, inter-ministerial collaboration, and resource mobilization for the operationalization of the One Health approach.

Composition

- Chair: Minister of Health (on a rotational basis among the four-line ministries).
- Permanent members: Ministers/representatives from MoH, MoA, MoE, MoLG and directors/representatives of NCDC, NCAH, FDCC. International organizations: WHO, WOA, FAO, UNEP

The flow of information

We describe here a passive flow of information, that should be complemented by active surveillance activities specific for each disease.

The community surveillance team after an ad-hoc training is in charge to notify potential events to the municipality OH team through SMS/phone call/WhatsApp for urgent alert, and official form.

National OH task force to develop SOPs for the local surveillance team including triggers for alert (e.g. a dog found dead, a case of animal bite, abortions in livestock, an animal or human sample subjected to diagnostic testing for a disease, a human arriving at a

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healthcare facility for post-exposure prophylaxis, a suspect human or animal case, febrile illnesses in humans, increase in mosquitoes density, heavy rainfall etc.).

The municipality OH team receives the alert, it includes the information available in an excel sheet and share an official letter with the governorate and national OH taskforce. The OH team organizes a joint field investigation and include all the relevant information in a joint excel sheet and send a standardized summary report to the governorate and OH task force at national level and implement the necessary measures.

National OH task force to develop joint field investigation SOPs (including algorithms for lab diagnosis)

Rabies

- Example of epidemiological data to be collected for Rabies (excel file or dashboard):

Incident details: Date of Report, Location of Incident,

Animal details: Animal Type/species, Animal Status after Incident, Animal Behavior, vaccination status

Human exposure details: Number of People Exposed, Type and location of Exposure (bite, scratch), Name of Exposed Individual (for follow up, Health Facility, Status of Post-Exposure Prophylaxis.

Description of measures taken

Brucellosis

- Example of epidemiological data to be collected for Brucellosis:

Human data

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- Patient demographics (age, sex, residence)
- Symptom onset date, clinical signs (fever, sweats, arthralgia, hepatosplenomegaly)
- Relevant exposures in last 30 days (animal contact, raw milk/cheese consumption, slaughtering, assisting births, handling aborted materials)
- Occupation (farmer, shepherd, veterinarian, butcher, lab worker)
- Travel history to endemic areas
- Household contacts exposed
- Laboratory tests: RBT, ELISA, blood culture, PCR (if available)
- Treatment started, follow-up status

Animal data

- Species affected (sheep, goats, cattle, camels)
- Number of abortions, stillbirths, weak newborns
- Herd vaccination status (S19/Rev1)
- Introduction of new animals (dates, origin)
- Contact with neighboring herds
- Laboratory results (RBT, CFT, ELISA, culture if available)

Environmental / contextual data

- Location of case(s) (GPS if available)
- Animal movement routes, communal grazing points
- Slaughterhouse exposure
- Milk-collection centers, markets visited
- Waste disposal practices for aborted materials

Vector Borne Diseases

- **Example of epidemiological data to be collected for VBDs:**

Human data

- Patient demographics & location
- Exposure: mosquito bites, handling of sick animals, presence at birthing/abortion events
- Hemorrhagic symptoms, fever, neurologic signs
- Lab tests: IgM/IgG ELISA, PCR

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Animal data

- Abortion storms (number, species, date)
- Mortality in young animals
- Movement of herds before symptoms
- Vaccination status (if applicable)
- Lab tests (RT-PCR, ELISA, virus isolation)

Vector / environmental data

- Mosquito density (Aedes/Culex)
- Flooding, rainfall, standing water
- GIS coordinates of clusters
- Temperature, humidity trends

Example of epidemiological data to be collected for Dengue

Human data

- Patient demographics & symptoms (fever, rash, hemorrhage, warning signs)
- Travel history or contact with known dengue cases
- Lab confirmation: NS1, IgM/IgG, PCR
- Location of residence/work/school

Vector data

- Aedes mosquito indices:
 - House Index (HI)
 - Container Index (CI)
 - Breteau Index (BI)
- Larval habitat mapping
- Adult mosquito surveillance where available

Environmental data

- Water storage practices
- Waste management conditions
- Temperature/rainfall influencing breeding

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□ **Example of epidemiological data to be collected for Leishmaniasis**

Human data

- Type of leishmaniasis (CL or VL)
- Demographics, clinical symptoms, lesion characteristics
- Travel or migration history
- Exposure to outdoor night-time activities
- Lab confirmation: microscopy, PCR, rk39 (VL)

Animal data

- Presence of potential reservoir dogs or other mammals
- Testing of suspected reservoir animals (where relevant)

Vector data

- Sandfly density, species identification (*Phlebotomus* spp.)
- Infection rate in vectors (if lab capacity exists)
- Seasonality and location of collection points

Environmental data

- Housing conditions (cracks, organic waste, humidity)
- Vegetation/shelter areas near homes

The national OH taskforce sends a feedback to the municipality OH team, produce a joint bulletin and informs the OH steering committee about the results of the joint investigation.

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Joint risk assessment and preparedness

The OH municipality team together with the community surveillance team performs joint risk assessments every three months in the municipality area and community awareness activities based on risk, and share the results with the OH task force who develop risk maps.

National OH task force to develop joint risk assessment SOPs integrating different diseases.

The OH task force shares joint preparedness recommendations based on risk and plan for after-action reviews and simulation exercises.

National OH task force to develop joint SOPs for preparedness

Discussion and way forward

The workshop was a great opportunity for the Libyan stakeholders from different sectors to meet and discuss about OH surveillance applications for PZDs and PVBDs in Libya and highlighted gradual pathways to strengthen surveillance activities in the short term towards a OH approach and structural adaptation to be adopted in the long term to integrate teams, levels and diseases. Surveillance systems are dynamic and continuously evolving entities; therefore their design should be gradual and take into account a certain grade of flexibility.

To guide the development of an advanced OH surveillance system for PZDs and PVBDs in Libya some recommendations based on the findings of the workshop are here provided (Table 1). First of all, a OH task force at national level composed of technical experts of different sectors working within the surveillance of zoonotic diseases should be

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consolidated. They should meet regularly to coordinate the development of the OH surveillance system starting from the implementation of an inventory of OH resources and capacities at country level (from national to municipal) including laboratories to identify strengths and gaps (training, equipment, material, human resources, etc.). Where gaps exist a plan to close those gaps should be developed, including the development of joint agreements with private sector, organizations, universities and research institutes to provide essential services (e.g. data collection, training and community awareness) and between veterinary, entomological and medical laboratories to share diagnostic capacity and expertise, including quality management. The OH task force should advocate to decision-makers to adapt the legal framework, to allow the sharing of data/information among sectors at municipality and national level, and secure funding to ensure the sustainability of the OH surveillance system. Strategic SOPs, including case definitions for all the sectors, for joint data collection and sharing (including a set of minimum indicators/data to be shared), joint diagnostic procedures, joint risk assessment, joint early warning and preparedness, should be developed together with the relevant forms standardized across the country. Tools like data dashboard and GIS, might be adopted to streamline data sharing and risk assessment. At the local level focal points from each municipality from governmental and non-governmental actors should be identified and trained to be included in the community surveillance team to establish event-based surveillance systems. Community awareness campaigns should be implemented regularly and based on risk.

Pathways to develop an advanced OH surveillance system in Libya
Consolidation of the national OH task force
Advocacy to adapt the legal framework and ensure funds
Inventory of OH resources and capacities at national and municipality level

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Close the gaps identified with the inventory, also by developing agreements with non-governmental actors to perform activities and share capacities (i.e. between laboratories)
Strengthen capacities at municipal level including labs, with training and resources
Develop SOPs (including case definitions) for the different phases of the OH surveillance system
Establish event-based surveillance systems at community/local level
Perform community awareness campaigns based on risk

Table 1: Pathways to develop an advanced OH surveillance system in Libya

Limitations

This report tried to summarize the large amount information collected during the workshop and go a step forward by describing pathways to develop an advanced OH surveillance system that could be developed in Libya in few years. The workshop was a productive opportunity for discuss and agree about OH surveillance actions in Libya and the stakeholders participated actively, thanks also to the work of the group discussion leads. As always some constraints in the performance of the workshop were recorded. Discuss about how to develop OH surveillance systems is challenging and requires understanding and agreement at conceptual and operational level among all the actors. Unfortunately the use of Artificial Intelligence tools hampered, in our opinion, the identification of concrete, feasible and context relevant OH surveillance actions for Libya. Moreover, the language barrier (it was not possible to have discussions always in English) was a limit for the ISS researchers. Some discrepancies in the OH flow of information drafted and described were noted. Least but not last a foodborne outbreak impacted the normal performance of the activities during the workshop.

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Annexes

Annex 1: Situation analysis workshop

Annex 2: List of participants

Annex 3: Agenda

Annex 4: Template

Annex 5: Rabies template filled by the participants

Annex 6: Brucellosis template filled by the participants

Annex 7: VBDs template filled by the participants

Annex 8: Rabies digitalized flowchart

Annex 9: Brucellosis digitalized flowchart

Annex 10: VBDs digitalized flowchart

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Situation analysis to identify opportunities to reinforce One Health surveillance for vector-borne and zoonotic disease in Libya

Tripoli 26 February & 7 May 2025

Final Report

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1. Introduction

Multisectoral approaches, such as One Health (OH), have been recognized as the best approaches for the prevention and preparedness of threats emerging at the human-animal-environment interface, to support global health security.^{1,2} Therefore, the OH approach needs to be adopted in surveillance systems, so as to promptly assess the multiple potential risk factors that are involved before they become a threat and to guide relevant actions. Conventional disease surveillance has been siloed by sectors, with separate systems addressing the health of humans, domestic animals, cultivated plants, wildlife and the environment.

The Integrated Disease Surveillance and Response (IDSR) is a strategy for strengthening national public health surveillance and response systems at all levels and provides a framework for meeting the core capacity requirements of the International Health Regulations (IHR, 2005) in the African region.³ However, the OH component of the IDSR, which aims at supporting the integration of human-animal-environmental surveillance, is not yet developed due to lack of resources, competences and specific guidance.

Libya aims to fully adhere to the IDSR strategy and incorporate a OH lens, to target vector-borne and zoonotic diseases, which represent a serious threat for the country. Therefore, the

¹ OHHLEP (One Health High-Level Expert Panel). (2023a). One Health action for health security and equity. *Lancet (London, England)*, 401(10376), 530–533. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(23\)00086-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(23)00086-7)

² FAO, UNEP, WOA, & WHO. (2022). *One Health Joint Plan of Action, 2022–2026*. World Health Organization; Geneva, Switzerland. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.4060/cc2289en>

³ Technical Guidelines for Integrated Disease Surveillance and Response in the WHO African Region 3rd Edition. Brazzaville: WHO Regional Office for Africa; 2019. Licence: CC BYNC-SA 3.0 IGO.

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implementation of the IDSR strategy needs to consider the adoption of the OH approach in the Libyan context.

This study is a situation analysis aimed at exploring:

- a) how the OH approach could be adopted in the surveillance of zoonotic and vector-borne diseases in Libya; and
- b) what are the challenges to the development of a OH surveillance system for zoonotic and vector-borne diseases in the Libyan context.

1.1 Objectives

- a) Assess how the IDSR strategy can incorporate OH surveillance, using a vector-borne and a zoonotic disease relevant to Libya as case studies; and
- b) Identify the challenges and opportunities of adopting the OH approach within the IDSR strategy in the Libyan context.

2. Methods

This study was conducted in the context of the National International Health Regulations–Performance of Veterinary Services (IHR-PVS) Bridging Workshop (NBW), held from 23 to 26 February 2025. The methodology included interviews with representatives from relevant sectors and a multisectoral workshop aimed at aligning and consolidating the information collected.

Two relevant pathogens (one zoonotic and one vector-borne) were selected as case studies to explore the actual surveillance system and potential avenues for OH integration: Rift

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Valley Fever Virus (RVFV), as emerging priority⁴, and Rabies, considering the recent outbreak in Libya.

The study focused on discussions regarding collaboration and coordination among the human, animal, and environmental sectors in Libya to address the selected pathogens, following an approach previously implemented by Istituto Superiore di Sanità (ISS) in other countries.^{5,6,7}

2. 1 Stakeholders

The stakeholders involved in surveillance activities for zoonoses and arboviral diseases at different levels (national, intermediate, district) were engaged in the analysis. A full list is provided in Table 1 and Annex I.

⁴ Miller, L. N., Elmselati, H., Fogarty, A. S., Farhat, M. E., Standley, C. J., Abuabaid, H. M., Zorgani, A., Elahmer, O., & Sorrell, E. M. (2023). Using One Health assessments to leverage endemic disease frameworks for emerging zoonotic disease threats in Libya. *PLOS global public health*, 3(7), e0002005. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pgph.0002005>

⁵ Milano, A.; Robbiati, C.; Declich, S.; Calistri, P.; Pediconi, O.; Amato, L.; Paronyan, L.; Avetisyan, L.; Manucharyan, A.; Avetisyan, G.; et al. Assessing the Adoption of One Health Approaches in National Plans to Combat Health Threats: The Pilot of a One Health Conceptual Framework in Armenia. *Trop. Med. Infect. Dis.* 2024, 9, 22. <https://doi.org/10.3390/tropicalmed9010022>

⁶ Dente MG, Riccardo F, Bolici F, et al. *Implementation of the One Health approach to fight arbovirus infections in the Mediterranean and Black Sea Region: Assessing integrated surveillance in Serbia, Tunisia and Georgia.* *Zoonoses Public Health.* 2019;66(3):276-287. doi:10.1111/zph.12562

⁷ Robbiati, C., Milano, A., Habib, M., Declich, S., Dente, M. G., & On behalf of the study working group. (2024). MediLabSecure One Health Situation Analysis (OHMeSA) in Montenegro. MediLabSecure Project. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10631734>

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Ministry of Health (MoH)
Ministry of Agriculture (MoA)
Ministry of Environment (MoE)
National Centre for Disease Control (NCDC)
National Centre for Animal Health (NCAH)
Food and Drug Control Center (FDCC)
Environmental Sanitation Affairs (ESA)
World Health organization (WHO)
Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO)
World Organization for Animal Health (WOAH)
University

Table 1: Stakeholders engaged in the situation analysis study

2.2 Key informant interviews

Semi-structured interviews were conducted with the human health sector, animal health sector and environmental health sector. A check-list was used to explore the existing surveillance system for the two selected pathogens within each sector (Annex II).

2.3 Multisectoral workshop

Multisectoral working groups (human, animal, and environmental health) were organized to identify the opportunities and gaps in OH surveillance for the two selected pathogens, as well as the challenges related to implementation of OH surveillance in Libya.

2.4 Schedule of the activities during the NBW

The schedule of the activities conducted as part of the study within the NBW workshop is presented in Figure 1.

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DAY 4 (26 February 2025)	
One Health Situation Analysis in Libya - Istituto Superiore di Sanità	
9:00-9:30	Introduction to One Health surveillance (30')
9:30-12:30	Sectoral consultations with stakeholders engaged in surveillance activities of zoonoses and vector-borne diseases according to the different sectors. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Human health stakeholders' consultation (60') • Animal health stakeholders' consultation (60') • Environmental health stakeholders' consultation (60')
12:30-13:30	Lunch
13:30-16:45	Multisectoral workshop with all the engaged stakeholders from the different sectors. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Introduction (15') • Working groups to describe the current surveillance system for the two selected pathogens and identify opportunities for the integration of the One Health approach (120') • Restitution (60')
16:45-17:00	Discussion and way forward (15')
17:00-17:15	Closure (15')

Figure 1: Schedule of OH SA Activities on Day 4 of the NBW

3.Results

As reported, the study was intended to be implemented with two sessions, one with interviews with the referents of the different sectors involved, the other with multisectoral working groups.

Unfortunately, due to security reasons, the working groups were suspended and re-scheduled to the first available option: 7 May 2025 at the NCDC in Tripoli. The ISS team participated online, while all other stakeholders attended the session in person.

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3.1 Participants

A total of 27 participants took part in the study, representing the following Institutions: the National Centre for Disease Control (NCDC), Faculty of veterinary medicine, Faculty of medicine, Ministry of Environment (MOE), Food and Drug Control Center (FDCC), National Centre for Animal Health (NCAH), Environmental Sanitation Affairs (ESA), Ministry of Health (MOH), Bengasi Hospital (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Institutional Affiliation of Participants Engaged in the Situation Analysis

3.2 Interviews

Table 2 summarizes the main findings from the interviews, organized under three categories: barriers, opportunities, and possible actions to enhance OH surveillance in Libya.

Barriers	Opportunities	Possible actions
No dedicated budget for integrated/OH activities	National OH MoU signed;	An operative multisectoral steering committee should be established

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	<p>IHR highlights the need to strengthen OH capacities and resources;</p> <p>One Health Task Force already established</p>	
Lack of formal means and tools for intra and inter sectoral communication	<p>Informal communication is present between sectors especially during outbreaks</p> <p>NCDC informs the MoH during outbreaks.</p>	Establish standardized and routine mechanisms for information exchange (e.g., Excel-based data sharing, regular epidemiological bulletins, etc.)
Lack of a centralized and jointly managed website for public awareness campaigns	<p>Sensitisation means available (e.g. NCDC’s website, website, radio station, green telephone lines, Facebook pages managed by sector);</p> <p>An agreement with NCAH exists but not fully operational;</p> <p>MoE website could serve as an additional channel for awareness communications;</p> <p>Local-level awareness activities/campaigns are supported by the Environmental Sanitation Affairs</p>	Develop a Standard Operating Procedure (SOP) for coordinated communication campaigns within and across sectors
No joint risk assessments conducted and no training opportunities available for staff involved	Consolidation of intersectoral collaboration protocols could support joint risk assessment efforts	<p>Develop and implement a SOP for intersectoral risk assessments;</p> <p>Identify and allocate resources for capacity-building and training on integrated risk assessment methodologies</p>

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RVF/V		
<p>No RVF/V human surveillance currently in place</p> <p>Animal surveillance plan activated in 2021, but hindered by unavailability of diagnostic kits; Active surveillance in animal at cross-border is limited due to the unavailability of kits;</p> <p>Entomological surveillance is currently not implemented;</p> <p>Weather data are collected by the MoE but not shared with the other sectors for early warning purposes</p>	<p>Previous human seroprevalence study conducted in 2009 (Annex III); new studies planned in southern regions but pending implementation;</p> <p>Development of a surveillance plan with support of FAO has been started;</p> <p>Vector control activities are conducted by the ESA, however, these are not yet guided by risk-based area identification</p>	<p>Identify, designate, and equip a national reference laboratory for RVF diagnostics;</p> <p>Allocate resources for capacity building and training of laboratory personnel</p> <p>Establish protocols for intersectoral data sharing, including weather data, to support early warning systems;</p> <p>Identify and prioritize high-risk areas for targeted vector control activities based on entomological and environmental indicators</p>
Rabies		
<p>Rabies surveillance plan is currently not in place</p>	<p>A previous plan was available but it was suspended in 2011. Joint field missions were carried out during the most recent/last outbreak</p>	<p>Review and update the suspended national rabies surveillance plan to align with current epidemiological needs and OH priorities;</p> <p>Institutionalize outbreak response activities based on lessons learned from past field missions</p>

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Lack of national reference laboratories for rabies in both human and animal sectors; Limited national diagnostic capacity for sample collection, confirmation, and timely reporting	Existing agreement with Pasteur Institute in Tunis for test confirmation (but sometimes one month to have results)	Identify, designate, and strengthen national reference laboratories for rabies diagnosis in both human and animal sectors; Establish sustainable collaboration mechanisms with international laboratories (e.g., Pasteur Institute) while enhancing in-country diagnostic capacity
Early warning signals are mainly triggered by media rather than formal surveillance or early detection systems	At risk areas are monitored on the basis of outbreaks	Enhance predictive monitoring of at-risk areas using historical rabies outbreak data, animal bite reports, dog population density, and cross-sectoral inputs (e.g., veterinary and public health data)

Table 2: Summary of Interview Findings

3.3 Sectoral and Multisectoral groups exercise

At the beginning of the session, participants were divided by sector to discuss and fill in a table aimed at reporting the current status of surveillance activities for RVF/V and Rabies.

Table 3 presents the key information shared during the sectoral group discussions. These findings consolidate the outcomes of the interviews. For more details, please refer to the sector-specific tables in Annexes IV, V, and VI.

Disease	Current Status
Environment	
Rabies	Intersectoral communication is limited and occur only during outbreaks; Community-level awareness campaigns are conducted only in response to outbreaks;

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	<p>A SOP for Rabies control is not available;</p> <p>No structured training on rabies control is currently available;</p> <p>Waste management practices are lacking.</p>
RVF/V	The only present activity is awareness creation in case of outbreaks
Human	
Rabies	<p>Intersectoral communication is activated <i>only during outbreaks</i>;</p> <p>Awareness creation at community level only during outbreaks;</p> <p>SOP for Rabies control not available;</p> <p>Training opportunities for human health personnel are not available;</p> <p>Surveillance is uni-sectoral, although rabies is included in the national notifiable disease list with a 24-hour immediate notification requirement;</p> <p>Post-exposure prophylaxis (PEP) is available;</p> <p>Laboratory diagnostic capacity is currently absent.</p>
RVF/V	<p>The only present activity is awareness creation in case of outbreaks;</p> <p>The availability of diagnostic capacity has been reported.</p>
Animal	
Rabies	Intersectoral Communication is activated <i>only during outbreaks</i> ;

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	<p>Community-level awareness activities are conducted only in response to outbreaks;</p> <p>No SOP for Rabies control is available;</p> <p>Training for veterinarians available during outbreaks;</p> <p>Vaccination of domestic animal is currently in place.</p>
RVF/V	<p>The only present activity is awareness creation in case of outbreaks;</p> <p>The availability of diagnostic capacity has been reported.</p>

Table 3: Overview of Sectoral Inputs on Rabies and RVF/V Surveillance

In the second part of the session the participants were divided in two multisectoral groups based on the two targeted pathogens. Each group was tasked with identifying priority activities to strengthen surveillance for RVF/V and Rabies, while also assessing the feasibility of implementing these activities.

The group working on RVF/V identified the following priorities:

- ✓ Joint SOPs for RVF/V control
- ✓ Joint Training of workforce about surveillance and diagnosis
- ✓ Joint OH Rapid Response Teams

The group working on Rabies identified as priorities the majority of the reported activities, but deemed particularly relevant

- ✓ Joint SOPs for Rabies control
- ✓ Building national laboratory capacities

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- ✓ Reinforcement of vaccination capacity through the establishment of vaccination teams
- ✓ Training of workforce

For further details on the group discussion outcomes, please refer to Annex VII and VIII.

4. Conclusions

The information collected through interviews and both sectoral and multi-sectoral group discussions provides a coherent overview of the current status of One Health (OH) operationalization and surveillance activities in Libya for the two pathogens under study.

Several steps have been done recently towards OH operationalization with the signature of the National OH Memorandum of Understanding and the establishment of the OH Task Force.

It appears that the majority of the multisectoral activities are activated in case of outbreaks. Therefore, there is a need to leverage on the mechanisms and procedures already in place to strengthen and institutionalize the OH system.

As highlighted during the NBW exercise, most of the identified gaps are systemic rather than disease-specific. This process enabled participants to visualize critical gaps across essential capacities and to clearly differentiate between systemic issues and disease-specific.

The establishment and the implementation of the OH activities considered joint priorities by the participants (Annex VII and VIII) can facilitate the strengthening of the Integrated Disease Surveillance and Response (IDSR) strategy in Libya and the integration of OH in the implementation of the strategy. The IDSR in Libya should therefore consider the challenges

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pointed out by the participants of this study and contribute to their overcome to allow a full development of the OH system in Libya.

5. Annexes

Annex I – List of involved participants

Annex II - check-list to explore the existing surveillance system for RVF/V and Rabies

Annex III - Human seroprevalence study in 2009

Annex IV -V-VI – Sector-specific tables on the current status of surveillance activities for RVF/V and Rabies

Annex VII-VIII – Tables on priority activities to enhance the surveillance activities for RVF/V and Rabies

Annex I

number		Gender	Discipline	Agency	Level	Location	البريد الإلكتروني
4	Ahmed Miloud Alarbi	M	workforce FETP	NCDC	Central	Tripoli	a.alarbi@ncdc.gov.ly
5	Adem Salem Jomah eljerbi	M	Laboratory	NCDC	Central	Tripoli	a_elierbi@yahoo.com
6	Ahmed Saleh Al-Qarari	M	Zoonotic disease	NCDC	Central	Tripoli	aelgrari78@gmail.com
7	Walid Khalifa Saadawi	M	vector Borne	NCDC	Central	Tripoli	walid_ecology@yahoo.com
10	Rawad sadik Hussain	M	IHR	NCDC	Central	Tripoli	rawad20212021@gmail.com
16	Mohamed Mostafa Hosni	M	Zoonotic disease	Faculty of veterinary medicine	Academia	Tripoli	Hosni0760@gmail.com
19	Abdulaziz Zorgani	M	AMR	Faculty of medicine	Academia	Tripoli	zorgania@yahoo.com
27	Ashraf Mosbah Aldali	M	Air Pollution	MOE	Central	Tripoli	ashrafaldali174@gmail.com
28	Iman Mohamed Ben Hamza	F	Environment Health	MOE	Central	Tripoli	Imanhmz@gmail.com
29	Sumia Mohamed Elarghubi	F	Climate change	MOE	Central	Tripoli	somiamohmed274@gmail.com
31	Naimah Meelad Inqeeqah	M	Laboratory	MOE	Central	Tripoli	naimamila956@yahoo.com
35	ahlam alazhar ahmad shueayb	F	Climate change	MOE	Central	Tripoli	ahlamshaap@gmail.com
38	Amina Elhadi Alost	F	Laboratory	FDCC	Central	Tripoli	aminaelhadialosta@gmail.com
37	Aml Fathi Lawila	F	AMR	FDCC	Central	Tripoli	amelfathi2014@gmail.com
40	Salem Alhadi Abudher	M	Food Safety	FDCC	Central	Tripoli	s.abudher2001@gmail.com
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53	OSAMA NAGI ELWAER	M	Laboratory	NCAH	decentralized	Tripoli	a.ossamavet@gmail.com
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Annex II

“Arboviral and zoonotic diseases in Libya: A joint WHO-ISS intervention to mitigate threats using the One Health approach”

The One Health Situation analysis (OHS Study)

Check List for the interviews at site visit

- i. Filled in during the meeting with: _____
- ii. Sector: _____
- iii. Institution:

- iv. City: _____

1. Level of integration: Policy and Institutional

Have you started any activity related to the *Integrated Disease Surveillance and Response (IDSR) strategy*?

YES NO

If yes, what you have done/are doing?

Is an **Integrated (OH) National steering committee** in place? YES NO

If YES

- i. Role: _____
- ii. Members: _____
- iii. frequency of ordinary meetings: _____
- iv. reasons for extraordinary meetings: _____
- v. ways of communication between members: _____

Is there a *coordinated plan for distribution of human and financial resources* dedicated to surveillance among the different sectors?

YES NO

- **USE of data for PUBLIC HEALTH ACTIONS**

Is a national database available for surveillance data? YES NO

If YES, is this database including all the surveillance data (animal, entomological, human, environment, etc.)
YES NO

If NO, which kind of database are available?

Are they accessible to other sectors involved in the surveillance? YES NO

If YES,

- specify the sector/s: _____
- type of access: consultation data management

2. Level of integration: Dissemination

Is a communication dept. /officer available? YES NO

If YES, is this connected/coordinated with the other relevant sectors? YES NO

Is a National bulletin/newsletter jointly prepared by all the relevant sectors available?

YES NO

If YES:

Frequency: _____

Target/s: _____

Is a dedicated website jointly managed by all the relevant sectors available? YES NO

Is the Evaluation of the surveillance plans performed? YES NO

If YES, is this available? YES NO

3. Focus: RVF

(as per interviewed sector, i.e. human, animal, entomology, environment, etc.)

Starting of the RVF surveillance in the Country?

YES NO

If YES when: _____

Is a **plan** for **RVF** Integrated surveillance available? YES NO

If YES, is it prepared on annual basis? YES NO

If YES, is the 2025 plan available? (to be provided if available) YES NO

Are **types and targets** of surveillance identified in the plan? YES NO

Are Endemic and not-endemic areas identified ? YES NO

Level of integration: Data collection and analysis

Who is in charge for the surveillance (institution, Dept. etc): _____

who does the analysis (institution, Dept. etc): _____

to whom the confirmed cases are reported (institution/s, Dept/s. etc) : _____

timing : _____

way/s: _____

- **Early Warning – Risk Assessment-Response-Communication**

Is there any early warning system, which activates human health measures based on animal and /or entomological surveillance? YES NO

If YES, can you describe your role (organizer, participant, etc.) in the process as per the table below? Is the procedure formally developed and available? YES NO

Steps of the Process	EW	Risk assessment	Response/Public Health Actions	Risk Communication
How does the process start? or What event triggers the process to start?				
You provide info to (Institution/s; Dept/s)				
Type of info				
how soon/periodicity				
Info are provided to you by (Institution/s; Dept/s)				
Type of info				
how soon/periodicity				
Multisectorial meetings (periodicity)				
report exchange (periodicity)				

- Please describe the most recent early warning case and provide available documents

If NO which enabling factors could support awareness initiatives?

What factors could hamper them?

Are there **mechanism supporting the strict collaboration** of human, animal and environmental health and medical entomology for RVF prevention and preparedness? YES NO

If YES which ones?

Which enabling factors supported these mechanisms?

If NO which enabling factors could support collaboration mechanisms?

What factors could hamper them?

Are there **trainings about OH prevention and preparedness to RVF?** YES NO

If YES which ones?

Which enabling factors supported these trainings?

If NO which enabling factors could support the development of these trainings?

What factors could hamper them?

Are there **integrated research studies** targeting prevention and preparedness to RVF?

YES NO

If YES which ones?

Which enabling factors supported these studies?

If NO which enabling factors could support the development of these studies?

What factors could hamper them?

Are there **projects/programs/networks** targeting RVF in your country with a OH approach that could enhance the harmonization of prevention and preparedness among countries?

YES NO

If YES which ones?

Which enabling factors supported these projects/programs/networks?

If NO which enabling factors could support the development of these projects/programs/networks?

What factors could hamper them?

4. Focus: Rabies

(as per interviewed sector, i.e. human, animal, entomology, environment, etc.)

Starting of the Rabies surveillance in the Country?

YES NO

If YES when: _____

Is a **plan** for **Rabies** Integrated (OH) surveillance available? YES NO

If YES, is it prepared on annual basis? YES NO

If YES, is the 2025 plan available? (to be provided if available) YES NO

Are **types and targets** of surveillance identified in the plan? YES NO

Are Endemic and not-endemic areas identified ? YES NO

Level of integration: Data collection and analysis

Who is in charge for the surveillance (institution, Dept. etc): _____

who does the analysis (institution, Dept. etc): _____

to whom the confirmed cases are reported (institution/s, Dept/s. etc) : _____

timing : _____

way/s: _____

- **Early Warning – Risk Assessment-Response-Communication**

Is there any early warning system, which activates human health measures based on animal and /or entomological surveillance? YES NO

If YES, can you describe your role (organizer, participant, etc.) in the process as per the table below? Is the procedure formally developed and available? YES NO

Steps of the Process	EW	Risk assessment	Response/Public Health Actions	Risk Communication
How does the process start? or What event triggers the process to start?				
You provide info to (Institution/s; Dept/s)				
Type of info				
how soon/periodicity				
Info are provided to you by (Institution/s; Dept/s)				
Type of info				
how soon/periodicity				
Multisectorial meetings (periodicity)				
report exchange (periodicity)				

- Please describe the most recent early warning case and provide available documents

If **NO** which enabling factors could support awareness initiatives?

What factors could hamper them?

Are there **mechanism supporting the strict collaboration** of human, animal and environmental health and medical entomology for Rabies prevention and preparedness? YES NO

If **YES** which ones?

Which enabling factors supported these mechanisms?

If **NO** which enabling factors could support collaboration mechanisms?

What factors could hamper them?

Are there **trainings about OH prevention and preparedness to Rabies**? YES NO

If **YES** which ones?

Which enabling factors supported these trainings?

If **NO** which enabling factors could support the development of these trainings?

What factors could hamper them?

Are there **integrated research studies** targeting prevention and preparedness to Rabies?

YES NO

If YES which ones?

Which enabling factors supported these studies?

If NO which enabling factors could support the development of these studies?

What factors could hamper them?

Are there **projects/programs/networks** targeting Rabies in your country with a OH approach that could enhance the harmonization of prevention and preparedness among countries?

YES NO

If YES which ones?

Which enabling factors supported these projects/programs/networks?

If NO which enabling factors could support the development of these projects/programs/networks?

What factors could hamper them?

Annex III

Sero-survey for selected infectious disease agents causing acute febrile illness (AFI) and acute infectious neurological disease (AIND), Libya, 2007.

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Abstract

Background: The etiology and epidemiology of acute febrile illness (AFI) and acute infectious neurological disease (AIND) in Libya has not been fully studied. Viral, rickettsial, and bacterial agents causing AFI and AIND are known to occur in countries bordering Libya including Egypt, Sudan, Chad and Niger. This is the first study to describe the viral, bacterial and rickettsial causes of AFI and AIND in Libya.

Methods: Out of 65,710 serum samples collected in 2004 for the national HBV and HCV survey, a random of 986 samples were tested by ELISA to determine the sero-prevalence of the main viruses and zoonotic bacteria that are known to cause AFI and AIND in Libya. Demographic characteristics of the subjects provided the samples were extracted from the national survey database to describe the epidemiology of the diseases.

Results: Antibodies against at least one pathogen were detected in 51% of the tested samples including 36% against bacterial zoonotic pathogen and 8% against one or more arbovirus and/or encephalitis. Mixed antibodies against bacterial and viral pathogens were also detected in 7% of the samples Antibodies against *C. burnetti* were detected in 24.4% of subjects, 18.1% for *R. conorii*, 13.1% West Nile virus (WNV) and 6.5% for tick-borne encephalitis (TBE). The highest prevalence of all identified pathogens was found in the West region and in age group 15-44 years.

Q fever, *R. typhi*, WNV, Rift valley fever (RVF) and Sand Fly N (SFN) antibodies were more in males, while *Leptospira* and Sindbis virus (SIN) were found more in females than males.

Conclusion: tick-borne pathogens and Arboviruses are among potential causes for AFI and AIND in Libya. Prospective hospital-based surveillance studies are required to better describe the epidemiology and possible etiologies of AFI and AIND and causes of morbidity and mortality in Libya population.

Key words: acute febrile illness, acute infectious neurological diseases, tick-borne diseases, arboviruses, zoonotic diseases, survey, Libya

1. Introduction:

Libya has a total population of 5.7 million. More than two thirds of the population is concentrated in the northern part of the country, towards Tripoli and Benghazi. Libya is bordered by countries known to be endemic for a variety of arboviral and zoonotic diseases including West Nile virus (WNV) and Sindbis in Egypt and Rift Valley fever virus (RVF) in Chad [1,2].

The incidence of arboviral infections in Libya is not well characterized. The presence of several types of mosquitoes-anopheles, *Culex*, and *Aedes* sandflies, suggests the presence of arboviral activity in the country. An earlier study testing sera from individuals living in the Sebha province (southern Libya) using hemagglutination inhibition assay (HI) indicated high levels of antibodies to Sindbis and WNV with prevalence rates of 41% and 74%, respectively [3]. In a more recent study in north-eastern Libya, it was shown that the highest incidence of acute febrile cases is due to aseptic unidentified etiologies [4] and active surveillance has reported more than 30 cases of aseptic meningitis in 2003 from different regions in Libya [5].

Since Libya is highly dependent on importing livestock from neighboring countries, it is conceivable that tick-borne diseases such as Rickettsiosis and Q-fever as well as other zoonotic diseases such as brucellosis may be circulating in the country. Little is known about Rickettsiosis in Libya. In 2003 about 260 cases of Mediterranean type rickettsia were reported in Libya, mainly from the central areas as Musrata and Al Markab [5]. The extent of the disease could be underestimated especially that neighboring countries like Chad have documented cases of spotted fever [8]. *Brucella* antibodies have been found in sera of camels and cows from Libya with a prevalence rate of 4.1% to 0.3% respectively, isolates were identified and typed as *B. melitensis* biovar 1 [9].

In Libya, diagnosis of most tick-borne and zoonotic diseases discussed above is currently dependent on the clinical presentation of the patient rather than proper laboratory investigations. Laboratory confirmation remains inadequate due to lack of specific reagents. To date, a limited number of studies concerning transmission of agents causing acute febrile illness (AFI) and acute infectious neurological disease (AIND) have been conducted in North Africa, and more specifically in Libya. In this study, we have used a randomly selected sample from a 2004 national cohort to

determine the sero-prevalence of 12 viral and bacterial etiologies that can cause AFI and central nervous system disease [6].

2. Materials and Methods:

2.1 Study population: Between April and August, 2004 a total of 65,710 serum samples were randomly collected from the population of the 32 provinces and the five regions of Libya to determine the prevalence of hepatitis B and C virus infections and their related risk factors [6].

Sample size calculation: In this study, a sub sample of 986 sera were randomly selected from the total archived samples collected for the national HBV/HCV survey. Demographic data of the subjects that provided the selected serum samples were extracted from the main HBV/HCV national survey database to describe the epidemiology of the main causes of AFI and AIND in Libya.

2.2 ELISA Assays: Twelve AFI and AIND etiologies were assayed in this study. The testing panel was divided into three groups:

1. Arboviruses and encephalitis: including Tick-Borne encephalitis (TBE), West Nile (WNV), Sandfly Sicilian (SFS), Sandfly Naples (SFN) and Sindbis (SIN).
2. Hemorrhagic fever viruses including Rift Valley Fever (RVF) and Hanta virus (HNT)
3. Zoonotic bacteria group: including *Brucella* (*Bruc.*), Q-fever (*C. Burnetti*), *Leptospira* (*lep*), *Rickettsia typhi* (*R. typhi*) and *Rickettsia conorii* (*R. conorii*).

All the laboratory assays used were standardized at the US Naval Medical Research Unit #3 (NAMRU-3) at that time. The serum samples were initially screened for the antibodies by ELISA. An in-house ELISA assays were used to screen for the antibodies against *Brucella* [10], *R. conorii* and *R. typhi* [11] and SF, SFN, SIN, RVF [12] pathogens. Commercial ELISA kits were used to test for the antibodies against *C. Burnetti* and *Leptospira* (Panbio, Australia), WNV (Focus Diagnostics, US), TBE (IBL, Germany), HTN (Progen (Germany) pathogens. For SF, SFN, SIN, RVF, *R. conorii* and *R. typhi* testing all samples were screened at a dilution 1:100 and reactive samples in the initial screening were confirmed using serial dilutions. For *Brucella* total antibody, a sample is considered reactive if it has antibody titer of $\geq 1:160$. Confirmation for reactive samples by commercial ELISAs was done by duplicate testing using the same assay in another run, following the manufacturers' instructions. No other confirmation or more identification of cross-reacting pathogens were done at that time.

3. Results:

A total of 986 serum samples were collected from 986 subjects representing the five geographical regions throughout Libya. The mean age was 25.7 ± 16 years, ranged from <1 to 99 years, 61.6% of the population were between 15-44 years age group. Male to female ratio was 1,

no significant difference between the age groups in five geographical areas of the country was found ($p=0.3$) (Figure 1). Almost half (49%) of the studied population was from the western parts of Libya, 22% were from the east and south east, 16% from Tripoli (middle) and 13% from the south (Figure 2).

Among the 986 serum samples, 503 (51.0%) were positive for one or more pathogens including 355 (36.0%) against one or more bacterial zoonotic pathogens and 76 (7.7%) against one or more arbovirus and/or encephalitis. Mixed antibodies against bacterial and viral pathogens were also detected in 72 (7.3%) of the samples (Figure 3). The antibodies against *C. Burnettii*, *R. conorii*, *Brucella*, *Leptospira* and *R. typhi* infections were found in 241(24.4%), 178(18.1%), 55(5.6%), 32(3.2%) and 23(2.3%) subjects respectively. No antibodies were detected against Hantavirus in the tested samples. (Figure 4)

Among bacterial causes of AFI and AIND; Q fever had the highest prevalence (24.4%), followed by TBE (18.1%). Q fever was found in all regions, while TBE has higher rates in the middle and South east regions (Table 1). Among viral caused WNV has the highest prevalence (13.1%) followed by TBE (6.5%) with higher rates found in residents of the south and south east (Table 2). The highest prevalence of all identified pathogens were in the middle age (15-44 years), , *R. typhi*, WNV, RVF and SFN antibodies were more prevalent in males than females, while *Leptospira* and SIN were found more in females. (Table 3)

4. Discussion

Data related to the incidence and prevalence rates of infectious diseases in Libya is rare due to the limited number of epidemiological studies performed in the country. A recent outbreak of unidentified VHFs was reported in June/July 2014 among twenty three African patients from immigrants encamps in North West of Libya, twelve of them reported dead. This highlights the evolving risk from spreading such diseases -if occurred- to the European countries and thus worldwide [13].

Our study is the first national comprehensive serological analysis for a number of etiologies causing AFI and AIND representing the population in terms of geography, age and gender distribution.

Except for Hanta virus, serological evidence proved previous exposure to all studied AFI and AIND etiologies at the different provinces of Libya. On several occasions, there was evidence of exposure to more than one agent for the same individual which could indicate higher rates of exposure to different pathogens among population.

Antibodies against tick-born rickettsial diseases were found among the study populations in different parts of the country, while brucellosis was mostly found in the Northern regions, and arboviral infections were identified more in the South. This can be explained by the presence of

grazing in the North with higher possibility for animal exposure, while the vectors for arboviruses may be found in the south from the neighboring countries.

This study is the first confirmation of Q-fever infection in Libyan's indigenous population, while, neighboring countries such as Chad is known to have Q-fever infections. A possible reason for the widespread of Q-fever antibodies in Libya could be due to the increase in imported and domestic animal breeding throughout the country and lack of screening program that might leads to increased risk of transmissions.

In recent decades outbreaks of WNV disease have been recorded in Northern Africa [14]. Early studies have shown that the presence of migratory birds' settlements and the existence of local bird populations support sustainable transmission to humans [15]. Warmer air temperatures influence vector competence, by accelerating the virus replication within mosquito vectors and prolonging their breeding season [16]. Drought may facilitate a closer contact between birds and vector mosquitoes around the remaining water sources, thus facilitating the transmission of the virus [17]. Recently, Conte et al. conducted spatio-temporal approach identifying suitable habitats for WNV disease in the Mediterranean basin (Tunis, Libya, Egypt, Morocco, Greece and Israel) and central Europe [18]. The model also identified suitable areas in Libya that have never reported the disease and therefore deserve a deeper analysis [18]. The presence of anti-WNV IgG antibodies (87%) in certain provinces across the south west part of the country coincides with the flyway of migratory birds, warmer temperature, mosquitoes, oases and drought climate. These risk factors might demonstrate that people living in these areas are at greater risk of WNV infection than in other places of Libya.

Sero-epidemiological studies revealed that murine typhus probably exists in other Mediterranean countries. In the last 15 years African tick bite fever caused by *R. africae* has been described as the most frequent rickettsioses acquired by travelers in sub-Saharan Africa. Other SFG rickettsioses such as Mediterranean spotted fever due to *R. conorii* have been reported as well as the flea-borne murine typhus caused by *R. typhi*. Recently, epidemiological aspects of rickettsial diseases were analyzed in 280 international travelers reported to the Geo Sentinel site from June 1996 through December 2008 [19]. The majority of these cases (82.5%) were tick-borne rickettsioses, 5.7% were cases of scrub typhus, and 2.5% were cases of typhus group rickettsioses [18]. Most cases were associated with travel to sub-Saharan Africa (75.1%). Omezzine-Letaief and colleagues tested 500 sera from blood donors in Tunisia and identified that 3.6% had antibodies to *R. typhi* [20]. Earlier evidence has suggested the presence of SIN virus and *R. typhi* in Libya [8]. Recently, a patient from Switzerland with confirmed Israeli spotted fever was suspected to be infected in Libya [21]. In this study we demonstrated higher level of anti-*R. conorii* (18%) than the seroprevalence of *R. conorii* among healthy population in most of the other countries (ranging from 5% to 8%) [20]. Similar to our finding (2%), the seroprevalence of anti-*R. typhi* among blood donors was from 0.5% to 4% in Algeria [22].

Other etiologies such as TBE, *Leptospira*, Sandfly fever and RVF are usually clinically categorized as suspected infections and diagnosed without laboratory confirmation. This study confirms the presence of antibodies against such pathogens in different parts of Libya and indicates a need for efficient laboratory diagnosis of suspected cases. Similar results have been reported from other countries of the Mediterranean Basin. Infection rates of sandflies have been reported from Italy, Algeria and Tunisia (0.22%, 0.4%, 0.53%, respectively) [23-25]. In Egypt, the prevalence of arboviral, rickettsial, and Hantaan-like viral antibody among schoolchildren in the Nile river delta indicated that the prevalence of antibody was 9% for Sicilian sandfly fever, 4% for RVF, 3% for WNV, 9% for Hantaan virus, 53% against *R. typhi*, and 37% against *R. conorii* [26].

Although in our study only 4 subjects found to have antibodies to RVF, yet there are assumptions from a recent appraisal of North Africa for relative risk of harboring circulating RVF virus [27]. Other neighboring countries such as Algeria and Tunisia are perceived as being at high risk of RVF virus outbreaks [27]. Libya is notable for its close proximity to European Mediterranean countries and the migratory patterns of birds through the country leading northwards into Europe; there is also evidence of RVF virus exposure in bird populations [28]. Further investigations in patients with active AFI are necessary to determine the public health impact of these agents in Libya. The presence of anti-RVF IgG in the south west part may be due to heavy traffic of camels from the south west borders of the country.

Although little information is available; previously reported human brucellosis in Libya is limited to a few cases [29]. Libya is considered to be endemic for brucellosis [9,30] According to a 2006 study, among livestock, 31% of goats and 42% of cattle were seropositive, human samples showed a high seropositivity of 40%, with 95 (43%) of the 221 positive samples positive for IgM, indicating active or recent infection, highlighting brucellosis as an important zoonotic disease in Libya [31]. Findings of our study indicate the presence of antibodies to *Brucella* infections almost exclusively in the west part of the country. In general, the dense population of goats in the west part of Libya as compared to the east could explain the high sero-prevalence of Q-fever, *Leptospira*, TBE and *Brucella* in this region. Preventive measures require surveillance, animal control, and increased use of the brucellosis vaccine for animals at risk.

One of the important findings of our study is the presence of mixed infections (viral, tick-borne and/or bacterial) among our study population. In addition, most of cases were found among the older age groups and in different parts of the country. This can be explained as due to long exposure to more than one pathogen and the presence of old versus recent infections among the study population. One more possible explanation for these findings could be due to serological cross-reactivity between the assays and the specificity of ELISA methods used in this study, the explanation that requires more investigations.

4.1 Study limitations

In-house ELISA kits prepared at NAMRU-3 laboratories after standardization were used to screen for *R. conorii* and *R. typhi* and SF, SFN, SIN, RVF due to unavailability of commercial kits for testing these pathogens when the study was conducted. . Confirmatory tests at NAMRU-3 could not be performed for logistical and political reasons. Cross reactivity between WNV and TBEV could not be addressed for the same reasons. IgG for all pathogens were tested except for Brucella (total antibodies) and leptospira (IgM) according to availability of the kits. In a previous work done in Libya (Fadeel et al, 2006), it was found that IgG and IgM antibody classes were detectable in more than 90% of samples tested in the same time for Brucella antibodies. In spite of the study limitations, yet determining the frequency and characteristics of patients with positive anti-bodies describes who and where infected persons were identified. This information can help in developing minimum estimates of infection burden to direct and evaluate prevention activities.

5. Conclusion

This study has demonstrated that exposure to tick-borne etiologies, particularly Q-fever, *R. conorii*- and Tick-borne encephalitis may be a major cause for AFI in different parts of Libya. Active surveillance for Q-fever and WNV in particular is warranted in this part of the world to assess the risk and/or define the pathogenesis due to these pathogens. Moreover, prospective hospital-based surveillance studies are required also to assess the morbidity and mortality of these etiologies in the population. Active collaboration between public health and animal health institutions of Libya is critical, as is increasing cohesive planning with the institutes of neighboring countries. Though our study is limited, we hope that it provides a foundation for further surveillance and investigation in Libya.

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Disclaimers:

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Figure 1. Distribution of the surveyed population by age group, Libya sero-survey, 2007.

Figure 2. Geographic distribution of the surveyed population by region, Libya sero-survey, 2007.

Figure 3: Proportion of groups of pathogens causing acute febrile illness (AFI) and acute infectious neurological disease (AIND) among studied population, Libya sero-survey, 2007.

Laboratory testing results	No. of subjects	% of subjects
Negative	483	49.0%
Zoonotic bacterial	289	29.3%
> one bacterial infection	66	6.7%
Arbovirus & encephalitis	45	4.6%
> one viral infection	30	3.0%
Mixed infection	72	7.3%
Hemorrhagic Viral	1	0.1%
Total	503	51%

Figure 4. Prevalence of antibodies for selected pathogens causing acute febrile illness (AFI) and acute infectious neurological disease (AIND), Libya sero-survey, 2007.

Table 1 Prevalence of antibodies against bacterial pathogens causing AFI among the tested population according to their geographical region, Libya sero-survey, 2007.

Region	Q fever		R. conorii		R. typhi		Brucella		Leptospira		Total
	No. of subjects with antibodies	Prevalence	No. of subjects with antibodies	Prevalence	No. of subjects with antibodies	Prevalence	No. of subjects with antibodies	Prevalence	No. of subjects with antibodies	Prevalence	
West	116	23.9%	77	15.9%	12	2.5%	18	3.7%	16	3.3%	485
East	49	26.3%	25	13.4%	3	1.6%	10	5.4%	5	2.7%	186
Middle	36	23.1%	52	33.3%	4	2.6%	27	17.3%	3	1.9%	156
South	33	26.0%	16	12.6%	2	1.6%	0	0.0%	6	4.7%	127
South east	7	21.9%	8	25.0%	2	6.3%	0	0.0%	2	6.3%	32
Grand Total	241	24.4%	178	18.1%	23	2.3%	55	5.6%	32	3.2%	986

Table 2 Prevalence of antibodies against viral pathogens causing AFI/AIND among the tested population according to their geographical region, Libya sero-survey, 2007.

Region	WNV		TBE		RVF		HTN		SIN		SFS		SFN		Total
	No. of subjects with antibodies	Prevalence	No. of subjects with antibodies	Prevalence	No. of subjects with antibodies	Prevalence	No. of subjects with antibodies	Prevalence	No. of subjects with antibodies	Prevalence	No. of subjects with antibodies	Prevalence	No. of subjects with antibodies	Prevalence	
West	57	11.8%	28	5.8%	2	0.4%	0	0.0%	2	0.4%	2	0.4%	1	0.2%	485
East	0	0.0%	0	0.0%	0	0.0%	0	0.0%	0	0.0%	1	0.5%	2	1.1%	186
Middle	10	6.4%	3	1.9%	0	0.0%	0	0.0%	0	0.0%	1	0.6%	2	1.3%	156
South	56	44.1%	30	23.6%	2	1.6%	0	0.0%	9	7.1%	2	1.6%	0	0.0%	127
South east	6	18.8%	3	9.4%	0	0.0%	0	0.0%	0	0.0%	1	3.1%	0	0.0%	32
Grand Total	129	13.1%	64	6.5%	4	0.4%	0	0.0%	11	1.1%	7	0.7%	5	0.5%	986

Table 3. Demographic characteristics of subjects with antibodies against selected bacterial and viral pathogens, Libya sero-survey, 2007.

Causative agent	≤15 years old		Total ≤15 years	% of row	15-44 years old		Total 15- 44 years	% of row	≥45 years old		Total ≥45 years	% of row	Total females	Total males	M/F ratio	Grand Total
	Female	Male			Female	Male			Female	Male						
Bacterial pathogens																
Q Fever	28	36	64	26.6	68	76	144	59.8	15	18	33	13.7	111	130	1.2	241
R. Conorii	12	16	28	15.7	52	51	103	57.9	24	23	47	26.4	88	90	1.0	178
R. Typhi	2	1	3	13.0	6	9	15	65.2	2	3	5	21.7	10	13	1.3	23
Brucella	1	4	5	9.1	22	18	40	72.7	4	6	10	18.2	27	28	1.0	55
Leptospira	3	0	3	9.4	20	5	25	78.1	0	4	4	12.5	23	9	0.4	32
Viral pathogens																
WNV	10	19	29	22.5	40	41	81	62.8	8	11	19	14.7	58	71	1.2	129
TBE	5	10	15	23.4	15	22	37	57.8	6	6	12	18.8	26	38	1.5	64
RV	0	0	0	0.0	1	1	2	50.0	0	2	2	50.0	1	3	3.0	4
HTN	0	0	0	0.0	0	0	0	0.0	0	0	0	0.0	0	0	NA	0
SN	2	0	2	18.2	4	3	7	63.6	0	2	2	18.2	6	5	0.8	11
SFS	1	0	1	14.3	6	0	6	85.7	0	0	0	0.0	7	0	0.0	7
SFN	0	1	1	20.0	1	2	3	60.0	0	1	1	20.0	1	4	4.0	5

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Annex IV

Arboviral and zoonotic diseases in Libya: A joint WHO-ISS intervention to mitigate threats using the One Health approach

Environment

Rabies (Please write in English)

Table 1

Rabies control activities currently implemented in Libya								
Activity	Presently implemented/a available	IF YES				IF NOT WHY?		
		Information	Other relevant information about the activity	Institution in charge for the activity	Collaborating institutions	Considered not relevant because....	Lack of these resources	Other
Communication channels/Information exchange	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Routine <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Only after a case/outbreak ----- <input type="checkbox"/> Unisectoral <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Multisectoral ----- <input type="checkbox"/> Local level <input type="checkbox"/> District level <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> National level	FOCAL POINT	NATIONAL LEVEL	YES(NCDC, ES ,NCAH)			
SOPs for Rabies control	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Unisectoral <input type="checkbox"/> Multisectoral ----- <input type="checkbox"/> Local level <input type="checkbox"/> District level <input type="checkbox"/> National level				NO NATIONAL PLANE		

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Rabies control activities currently implemented in Libya								
Activity	Presently implemented/a available	IF YES				IF NOT WHY?		
		Information	Other relevant information about the activity	Institution in charge for the activity	Collaborating institutions	Considered not relevant because....	Lack of these resources	Other
Training	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Routine <input type="checkbox"/> Only after a case/outbreak ----- <input type="checkbox"/> Unisectoral <input type="checkbox"/> Multisectoral ----- <input type="checkbox"/> Local level <input type="checkbox"/> District level <input type="checkbox"/> National level	Topic			(نقص التمويل)		
Identification of at-risk areas	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Local level <input type="checkbox"/> District level <input type="checkbox"/> National level						NO (CABICITY BULDING) نقص الموارد المالية والفنية (
Awareness creation at community level	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Routine <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Only after a case/outbreak ----- <input type="checkbox"/> Unisectoral <input type="checkbox"/> Multisectoral ----- <input type="checkbox"/> Local level <input type="checkbox"/> District level						

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Rabies control activities currently implemented in Libya								
Activity	Presently implemented/a available	IF YES				IF NOT WHY?		
		Information	Other relevant information about the activity	Institution in charge for the activity	Collaborating institutions	Considered not relevant because....	Lack of these resources	Other
		<input type="checkbox"/> National level						
Stray dogs/cats vaccination	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Routine <input type="checkbox"/> Only after a case/outbreak ----- <input type="checkbox"/> Local level <input type="checkbox"/> District level <input type="checkbox"/> National level						
Stray dogs/cats neutering/spaying	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Routine <input type="checkbox"/> Only after a case/outbreak ----- <input type="checkbox"/> Local level <input type="checkbox"/> District level <input type="checkbox"/> National level						
Waste management	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Routine <input type="checkbox"/> Only after a case/outbreak ----- <input type="checkbox"/> Local level <input type="checkbox"/> District level <input type="checkbox"/> National level						ضعف البنية التحتية

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Rabies control activities currently implemented in Libya								
Activity	Presently implemented/a available	IF YES				IF NOT WHY?		
		Information	Other relevant information about the activity	Institution in charge for the activity	Collaborating institutions	Considered not relevant because....	Lack of these resources	Other
Other activities implemented related to Rabies control								التنسيق وتعزيز التعاون بين الجهات ذات العلاقة

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Rift Valley Fever/Virus (Please write in English)

Table 2

RVF/V control activities currently implemented in Libya								
Activity	Presently implemented/available	IF YES				IF NOT WHY?		
		Information	Other relevant information about the activity	Institution in charge for the activity	Collaborating institutions	Considered not relevant because....	Lack of these resources:	Other:
Communication channels/Information exchange	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Routine <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Only after a case/outbreak ----- <input type="checkbox"/> Unisectoral <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Multisectoral ----- <input type="checkbox"/> Local level <input type="checkbox"/> District level <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> National level	عدم التنسيق بين الجهات المعنية					
Risk assessment	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Routine <input type="checkbox"/> Only after a case/outbreak ----- <input type="checkbox"/> Unisectoral <input type="checkbox"/> Multisectoral ----- <input type="checkbox"/> Local level					نقص في الموارد المالية والفنية	

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RVF/V control activities currently implemented in Libya								
Activity	Presently implemented/available	IF YES				IF NOT WHY?		
		Information	Other relevant information about the activity	Institution in charge for the activity	Collaborating institutions	Considered not relevant because....	Lack of these resources:	Other:
		<input type="checkbox"/> District level <input type="checkbox"/> National level						
Environmental monitoring	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No							ضعف التواصل بين القطاعات المعنية
Vector mapping	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No							لا يوجد خطة وطنية وضعف التنسيق بين الجهات ذات العلاقة
Vector control	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No							نقص في الموارد المالية
Training	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Routine <input type="checkbox"/> Only after a case/outbreak ----- <input type="checkbox"/> Unisectoral <input type="checkbox"/> Multisectoral ----- <input type="checkbox"/> Local level <input type="checkbox"/> District level <input type="checkbox"/> National level						نقص في التمويل

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RVF/V control activities currently implemented in Libya								
Activity	Presently implemented/available	IF YES				IF NOT WHY?		
		Information	Other relevant information about the activity	Institution in charge for the activity	Collaborating institutions	Considered not relevant because....	Lack of these resources:	Other:
Awareness creation at community level	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Routine <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Only after a case/outbreak ----- <input type="checkbox"/> Unisectoral <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Multisectoral ----- <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Local level <input type="checkbox"/> District level <input type="checkbox"/> National level			وزارة البيئة والصحة الحيوانية والاصحاح البيئي			
Training of community members for participatory surveillance	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Routine <input type="checkbox"/> Only after a case/outbreak ----- <input type="checkbox"/> Unisectoral <input type="checkbox"/> Multisectoral ----- <input type="checkbox"/> Local level <input type="checkbox"/> District level <input type="checkbox"/> National level						عدم توفير الامكانيات

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RVF/V control activities currently implemented in Libya								
Activity	Presently implemented/available	IF YES				IF NOT WHY?		
		Information	Other relevant information about the activity	Institution in charge for the activity	Collaborating institutions	Considered not relevant because....	Lack of these resources:	Other:
Laboratory diagnosis (entomology)	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No							
SOPs for RVF/V control	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No							
Other activities implemented for RVF/V control	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No							

Annex V

Arboviral and zoonotic diseases in Libya: A joint WHO-ISS intervention to mitigate threats using the One Health approach

Human health sector

Rabies (Please write in English)

Table 1

Rabies control activities currently implemented in Libya								
Activity	Presently implemented/available	IF YES				IF NOT WHY?		
		Information	Other relevant information about the activity	Institution in charge for the activity	Collaborating institutions	Considered not relevant because....	Lack of these resources	Other
Communication channels/information exchange	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Routine <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Only after a case/outbreak ----- <input type="checkbox"/> Unisectoral <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Multisectoral ----- <input type="checkbox"/> Local level <input type="checkbox"/> District level <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> National level	Not endemic in Ly Communication is multisectoral only in suspected cases in Libya.	Depending on the cases If an animal suspects case NCAH in charge. Human awareness or human suspect case NCDC	NCDC NCAH ES FDA MOE			
SOPs for Rabies control	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Unisectoral <input type="checkbox"/> Multisectoral ----- <input type="checkbox"/> Local level <input type="checkbox"/> District level <input type="checkbox"/> National level				The National Rabies Control Program has been suspended since 2011.		

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Rabies control activities currently implemented in Libya								
Activity	Presently implemented/available	IF YES				IF NOT WHY?		
		Information	Other relevant information about the activity	Institution in charge for the activity	Collaborating institutions	Considered not relevant because....	Lack of these resources	Other
Surveillance activities	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Unisectoral <input type="checkbox"/> Multisectoral ----- <input type="checkbox"/> Local level <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> District level <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> National level	Part of notifiable disease list as immediate notification 24h	ncdc	/			
Enforcement of mandatory notification of cases	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Unisectoral <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Multisectoral ----- <input type="checkbox"/> Local level <input type="checkbox"/> District level <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> National level	Part of Notifiable disease list as immediate notification 24h. law 106					
Post-exposure prophylaxis	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> At risk areas <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> National level	Not endemic in Ly. Any animal bite takes the anti-rabies vaccines - A circular issued by the National Center for Hospitals states that any case of infertility must receive the rabies vaccination.	NCDC				

Arboviral and zoonotic diseases in Libya: A joint WHO-ISS intervention to mitigate threats using the One Health approach

Rabies control activities currently implemented in Libya								
Activity	Presently implemented/available	IF YES				IF NOT WHY?		
		Information	Other relevant information about the activity	Institution in charge for the activity	Collaborating institutions	Considered not relevant because....	Lack of these resources	Other
Laboratory Diagnostic capacity	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Local level <input type="checkbox"/> District level <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> National level						Need building capacity
Training of health care workers	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Routine <input type="checkbox"/> Only after a case/outbreak ----- <input type="checkbox"/> Unisectoral <input type="checkbox"/> Multisectoral ----- <input type="checkbox"/> Local level <input type="checkbox"/> District level <input type="checkbox"/> National level					Have a proposal for training, but there is no budget.	
Identification of at-risk areas	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Local level <input type="checkbox"/> District level <input type="checkbox"/> National level	Risk of the introduction area					
Zero reporting of cases to international organizations	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No							
Awareness creation at community level	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Routine <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Only after a case/outbreak -----	Local level after suspect cases in animal	NCDC NCAH ES FDA				

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Rabies control activities currently implemented in Libya								
Activity	Presently implemented/available	IF YES				IF NOT WHY?		
		Information	Other relevant information about the activity	Institution in charge for the activity	Collaborating institutions	Considered not relevant because....	Lack of these resources	Other
		<input type="checkbox"/> Unisectoral <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Multisectoral ----- <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Local level <input type="checkbox"/> District level <input type="checkbox"/> National level		MOE				
Other activities related to Rabies control			Rabies control program committee to revive under the One Health Approach					

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Rift Valley Fever/Virus (Please write in English)

Table 2

RVF/V control activities currently implemented in Libya								
Activity	Presently implemented/available	IF YES				IF NOT WHY?		
		Information	Other relevant information about the activity	Institution in charge for the activity	Collaborating institutions	Considered not relevant because....	Lack of these resources:	Other
Communication channels/information exchange	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Routine <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Only after a case/outbreak ----- <input type="checkbox"/> Unisectoral <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Multisectoral ----- <input type="checkbox"/> Local level <input type="checkbox"/> District level <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> National level	Not endemic in Ly Communication is multisectoral only in the event.	Depend on the event NCDC NCAH ES FDA MOE				
Risk assessment	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Routine <input type="checkbox"/> Only after a case/outbreak ----- <input type="checkbox"/> Unisectoral					No budget	Not endemic in Ly

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RVF/V control activities currently implemented in Libya								
Activity	Presently implemented/available	IF YES				IF NOT WHY?		
		Information	Other relevant information about the activity	Institution in charge for the activity	Collaborating institutions	Considered not relevant because....	Lack of these resources:	Other
		<input type="checkbox"/> Multisectoral ----- <input type="checkbox"/> Local level <input type="checkbox"/> District level <input type="checkbox"/> National level						
Surveillance activities	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Unisectoral <input type="checkbox"/> Multisectoral ----- <input type="checkbox"/> Local level <input type="checkbox"/> District level <input type="checkbox"/> National level						
SOPs for RVF/V control	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Unisectoral <input type="checkbox"/> Multisectoral ----- <input type="checkbox"/> Local level <input type="checkbox"/> District level <input type="checkbox"/> National level						

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RVF/V control activities currently implemented in Libya								
Activity	Presently implemented/available	IF YES				IF NOT WHY?		
		Information	Other relevant information about the activity	Institution in charge for the activity	Collaborating institutions	Considered not relevant because....	Lack of these resources:	Other
Training of health care workers	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Routine <input type="checkbox"/> Only after a case/outbreak ----- <input type="checkbox"/> Unisectoral <input type="checkbox"/> Multisectoral ----- <input type="checkbox"/> Local level <input type="checkbox"/> District level <input type="checkbox"/> National level						
Awareness creation at community level	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Routine <input type="checkbox"/> Only after a case/outbreak ----- <input type="checkbox"/> Unisectoral <input type="checkbox"/> Multisectoral ----- <input type="checkbox"/> Local level						

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RVF/V control activities currently implemented in Libya								
Activity	Presently implemented/available	IF YES				IF NOT WHY?		
		Information	Other relevant information about the activity	Institution in charge for the activity	Collaborating institutions	Considered not relevant because....	Lack of these resources:	Other
		<input type="checkbox"/> District level <input type="checkbox"/> National level						
Laboratory diagnosis capacity	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Local level <input type="checkbox"/> District level <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> National level	Serology – PCR – Mosquitoes identification	NCDC				
Zero reporting human cases to international organizations	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No							
Enforcement of mandatory notification of human cases	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No							
Rapid response teams established	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No							
Other activities implemented/available for RVF/V control								

Annex VI

Arboviral and zoonotic diseases in Libya: A joint WHO-ISS intervention to mitigate threats using the One Health approach

Animal Health sector

Rabies

Table 1

Rabies control activities currently implemented in Libya								
Activity	Presently implemented/available	IF YES				IF NOT WHY?		
		Information	Other relevant information about the activity	Institution in charge for the activity	Collaborating institutions	Considered not relevant because....	Lack of these resources	Other
Communication channels/Information exchange	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Routine <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Only after a case/outbreak ----- <input type="checkbox"/> Unisectoral <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Multisectoral ----- <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Local level <input type="checkbox"/> District level <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> National level	بطء و تأخير في تبادل المعلومات	NCAH CDC	الإصحاح البيئي شرطة زراعية البيئية			
SOPs for Rabies control	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Unisectoral <input type="checkbox"/> Multisectoral ----- <input type="checkbox"/> Local level <input type="checkbox"/> District level <input type="checkbox"/> National level				يوجد مسودة غير معتمدة	تحديث وتطوير المسودة اعتمادها و العمل بها	

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Rabies control activities currently implemented in Libya								
Activity	Presently implemented/available	IF YES			IF NOT WHY?			
		Information	Other relevant information about the activity	Institution in charge for the activity	Collaborating institutions	Considered not relevant because....	Lack of these resources	Other
Surveillance of domestic animals cases	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Routine <input type="checkbox"/> Only after a case/outbreak ----- <input type="checkbox"/> Unisectoral <input type="checkbox"/> Multisectoral ----- <input type="checkbox"/> Local level <input type="checkbox"/> District level <input type="checkbox"/> National level				لا يوجد خطة وطنية لرصد ومكافحة المرض		
Surveillance of stray dogs/cats cases	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Routine <input type="checkbox"/> Only after a case/outbreak ----- <input type="checkbox"/> Unisectoral <input type="checkbox"/> Multisectoral ----- <input type="checkbox"/> Local level <input type="checkbox"/> District level <input type="checkbox"/> National level						
Laboratory Diagnostic capacity	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Local level <input type="checkbox"/> District level <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> National level	نحتاج الى تدريب و تاهيل الكوادر البشرية	NCAH	NCDC UNIVERSITIES Research centers			

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Rabies control activities currently implemented in Libya								
Activity	Presently implemented/available	IF YES				IF NOT WHY?		
		Information	Other relevant information about the activity	Institution in charge for the activity	Collaborating institutions	Considered not relevant because....	Lack of these resources	Other
Identification of at-risk areas	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Local level <input type="checkbox"/> District level <input type="checkbox"/> National level				لا يوجد دراسات		نعتد على تاريخ ظهور الحالات في المناطق
Enforcement of mandatory notification of animal cases	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> At risk areas <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> National level <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Domestic <input type="checkbox"/> Stray <input type="checkbox"/> Wildlife		NCAH LOCAL ANIMAL HEALTH	NCDC ES			
Training vets (public and private)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Routine <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Only after a case/outbreak ----- <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Unisectoral <input type="checkbox"/> Multisectoral ----- <input type="checkbox"/> Local level <input type="checkbox"/> District level <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> National level	التدريب من مدة طويلة و لعدد محدود	NCAH				
Zero reporting animal cases to international organizations	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Domestic <input type="checkbox"/> Stray <input type="checkbox"/> Wildlife		NCAH				
Awareness creation at community level	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Routine <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Only after a case/outbreak	التوعية ضعيفة	NCAH	NCDC ES			

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Rabies control activities currently implemented in Libya								
Activity	Presently implemented/available	IF YES				IF NOT WHY?		
		Information	Other relevant information about the activity	Institution in charge for the activity	Collaborating institutions	Considered not relevant because....	Lack of these resources	Other
		----- <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Unisectoral <input type="checkbox"/> Multisectoral ----- <input type="checkbox"/> Local level <input type="checkbox"/> District level <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> National level						
Domestic animals vaccination	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Routine <input type="checkbox"/> Only after a case/outbreak ----- <input type="checkbox"/> Local level <input type="checkbox"/> District level <input type="checkbox"/> National level	عدم توفر التطعيمات بشكل دوري	NCAH	ES			
Stray animals vaccination	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Routine <input type="checkbox"/> Only after a case/outbreak <input type="checkbox"/> Local level <input type="checkbox"/> District level <input type="checkbox"/> National level				لا يوجد برنامج للسيطرة على الكلاب السائبة	عدم توفر الموارد	
Stray dogs/cats neutering/spaying	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Routine <input type="checkbox"/> Only after a case/outbreak ----- <input type="checkbox"/> Local level						

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Rabies control activities currently implemented in Libya								
Activity	Presently implemented/available	IF YES				IF NOT WHY?		
		Information	Other relevant information about the activity	Institution in charge for the activity	Collaborating institutions	Considered not relevant because....	Lack of these resources	Other
		<input type="checkbox"/> District level <input type="checkbox"/> National level						
Waste management	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Routine <input type="checkbox"/> Only after a case/outbreak ----- <input type="checkbox"/> Local level <input type="checkbox"/> District level <input type="checkbox"/> National level						
Other activities implemented for Rabies control								

Arboviral and zoonotic diseases in Libya: A joint WHO-ISS intervention to mitigate threats using the One Health approach

Rift Valley Fever/Virus (Please write in English)

Table 2

RVF/V control activities currently implemented in Libya								
Activity	Presently implemented/available	IF YES				IF NOT WHY?		
		Information	Other relevant information about the activity	Institution in charge for the activity	Collaborating institutions	Considered not relevant because....	Lack of these resources:	Other:
Communication channels/information exchange	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Routine <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Only after a case/outbreak ----- <input type="checkbox"/> Unisectoral <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Multisectoral ----- <input type="checkbox"/> Local level <input type="checkbox"/> District level <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> National level	بطء وتأخير في تبادل المعلومات	NCAH CDC	الإصحاح البيئي البيئية شرطة الزراعة			
Risk assessment	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Unisectoral <input type="checkbox"/> Multisectoral				NO OFFICIAL SOP	نقص الموارد	يوجد مسودة
Syndromic surveillance in animals based on case definition	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No					نقص الموارد اللوجستية و المعملية	تمويل مسح شامل و دوري	

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RVF/V control activities currently implemented in Libya								
Activity	Presently implemented/available	IF YES				IF NOT WHY?		
		Information	Other relevant information about the activity	Institution in charge for the activity	Collaborating institutions	Considered not relevant because....	Lack of these resources:	Other:
Participatory surveillance system (community) in animals using syndromic case definition	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No					لا يوجد خطة وطنية معتمدة		
Sentinel herd system based on risk assessment and map	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No					لا يوجد خطة وطنية معتمدة		
Environmental monitoring (i.e. weather)	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No					لا يوجد خطة وطنية معتمدة		
Vector mapping	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No					لا يوجد خطة وطنية معتمدة	لا يوجد مراقبة حشرية	
Vector control	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No					لا يوجد خطة وطنية معتمدة		
Training of animal health workers (public and private)	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Routine <input type="checkbox"/> Only after a case/outbreak ----- <input type="checkbox"/> Unisectoral				لا يوجد خطة وطنية معتمدة		

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RVF/V control activities currently implemented in Libya								
Activity	Presently implemented/available	IF YES				IF NOT WHY?		
		Information	Other relevant information about the activity	Institution in charge for the activity	Collaborating institutions	Considered not relevant because....	Lack of these resources:	Other:
		<input type="checkbox"/> Multisectoral ----- <input type="checkbox"/> Local level <input type="checkbox"/> District level <input type="checkbox"/> National level						
Awareness creation at community level	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Routine <input type="checkbox"/> Only after a case/outbreak ----- <input type="checkbox"/> Unisectoral <input type="checkbox"/> Multisectoral ----- <input type="checkbox"/> Local level <input type="checkbox"/> District level <input type="checkbox"/> National level				لا يوجد خطة وطنية معتمدة		
Training of community members for participatory surveillance	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Routine <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Only after a case/outbreak ----- <input type="checkbox"/> Unisectoral <input type="checkbox"/> Multisectoral ----- <input type="checkbox"/> Local level <input type="checkbox"/> District level						

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RVF/V control activities currently implemented in Libya								
Activity	Presently implemented/available	IF YES			IF NOT WHY?			
		Information	Other relevant information about the activity	Institution in charge for the activity	Collaborating institutions	Considered not relevant because....	Lack of these resources:	Other:
		لا يوجد خطة وطنية معتمدة <input type="checkbox"/> National level						
Laboratory diagnosis capacity (animal virology)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No			NACH	NCDC			
Laboratory diagnosis (entomology)	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No					لا يوجد خطة وطنية معتمدة		
Zero reporting animal cases to international organizations	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No							
Enforcement of mandatory notification of animal cases	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> At risk areas <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> National level						
Rapid response teams established	Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No							الاستجابة عند الحدث
SOPs for RVF/v control	Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No					لا يوجد خطة وطنية معتمدة		يوجد مسودة
Other activities implemented								

Annex VII

Arboviral and zoonotic diseases in Libya: A joint WHO-ISS intervention to mitigate threats using the One Health approach

MULTISECTORAL

TABLE 3

RABIES

Rabies opportunities to enhance One Health prevention and control								
Activity	Priorty (1>5, high to low)	Feasibility (1>5) Entire country or at-risk area	Challenges	Institution in charge for coordinating the activity and main role/activities	Collaborating institutions and main role/activities	Implementation steps	Needed resources	Suggestions and opportunities
Communication channels	1	1	Communication are present between sectors but not with a formalised way and not with a unified means including all the involved institutions	A multisectorial committee should be set and a coordinating institution should be identified in accordance with the institutions' mandates	All the institutions with a role in the control of Rabies should be involved with a precise mandate	1.To start an institutional process to establish a multisectoral committee for the control of Rabies 2. to give official mandate to the Committee to developed a Plan for prevention and control of Rabies	The resources needed to implement the Plan for Rabies should be available and secured on constant basis and not only intermittently	

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Rabies opportunities to enhance One Health prevention and control								
Activity	Priority (1>5, high to low)	Feasibility (1>5) Entire country or at-risk area	Challenges	Institution in charge for coordinating the activity and main role/activities	Collaborating institutions and main role/activities	Implementation steps	Needed resources	Suggestions and opportunities
SOPs for Rabies control	1	It may be a long process but it is feasible and should be done		The Committee		The SOP should be a mandate of the multisectoral Committee	As above	
Surveillance activities	1	It is feasible to reinforce the surveillance capacity of each sector both in terms of training of workforce and consolidation of data electronic system	Presently only NCDC started to developed and electronic system including also Rabies.			1 To promote weekly/monthly reports to be shared between sectors 2 to plan electronic system development also for the other Institutions involved in surveillance of Rabies		

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Rabies opportunities to enhance One Health prevention and control								
Activity	Priority (1>5, high to low)	Feasibility (1>5) Entire country or at-risk area	Challenges	Institution in charge for coordinating the activity and main role/activities	Collaborating institutions and main role/activities	Implementation steps	Needed resources	Suggestions and opportunities
Enforcement of mandatory notification of cases	1	To be verified if the present law is including mandates for all the institutions involved in the control of Rabies						
Post-exposure prophylaxis	1	Since the last 3 months Post-exposure prophylaxis is available in Libya and NCDC sent notification with instructions of its use	The Post-exposure prophylaxis availability should be constant					

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Rabies opportunities to enhance One Health prevention and control								
Activity	Priority (1>5, high to low)	Feasibility (1>5) Entire country or at-risk area	Challenges	Institution in charge for coordinating the activity and main role/activities	Collaborating institutions and main role/activities	Implementation steps	Needed resources	Suggestions and opportunities
		after an animal bite						
Diagnostic capacity	1	Not available at human and animal level. It should be built at national level	At animal lab it was available until 2009, after it was not more implemented.					
Training of work force	1	It is sustainable because there is not an high staff turnover and there is staff availability to be trained	Training should be considered both for surveillance and staff and selection criteria should be considered to ensure sustainability					

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Rabies opportunities to enhance One Health prevention and control								
Activity	Priority (1>5, high to low)	Feasibility (1>5) Entire country or at-risk area	Challenges	Institution in charge for coordinating the activity and main role/activities	Collaborating institutions and main role/activities	Implementation steps	Needed resources	Suggestions and opportunities
			and consolidation overtime					
Identification of at-risk areas	1	To be consolidated						
Vaccination domestic animals	1	Presently vaccination campaign for dogs and cats Feasibility for establishing a vaccination team		NCDC		1 to establish a vaccination team to elaborate Control plan including vaccination but also other control methods		

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Rabies opportunities to enhance One Health prevention and control								
Activity	Priority (1>5, high to low)	Feasibility (1>5) Entire country or at-risk area	Challenges	Institution in charge for coordinating the activity and main role/activities	Collaborating institutions and main role/activities	Implementation steps	Needed resources	Suggestions and opportunities
Vaccination stray animals	1 Plan not available							
Vaccination wildlife	1 Plan not available							
Zero reporting of cases to international organizations	1	Feasible with workforce training						

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Rabies opportunities to enhance One Health prevention and control								
Activity	Priority (1>5, high to low)	Feasibility (1>5) Entire country or at-risk area	Challenges	Institution in charge for coordinating the activity and main role/activities	Collaborating institutions and main role/activities	Implementation steps	Needed resources	Suggestions and opportunities
Awareness creation at community level	1	Feasible with the institution of a unite committee and with the elaboration of a control plan						
Other activities related to Rabies control								

Annex VIII

Arboviral and zoonotic diseases in Libya: A joint WHO-ISS intervention to mitigate threats using the One Health approach

MULTISECTORAL

Rift Valley Fever/Virus (Please write in English)

Table 4

RVF/V opportunities to enhance One Health prevention and control								
Activity	Priority (1>5, low to high)	Feasibility (1>5) Entire country or at-risk area	Challenges	Institution in charge for coordinating the activity and main role/activities	Collaborating institutions and main role/activities	Implementation steps	Needed resources	Suggestions and opportunities
Communication channels	High priority 4		Need to formalize internally the roles and responsibilities	Each sector internally	NCAH NCDC ESA	formalize internally the roles and responsibilities in each sector and then share the contact focal point with other partners	no	Yes, an activity to be considered for integrated surveillance
Risk assessment	Not a priority for human health (even sectoral RA). For animal health priority (even sectoral) For animal health 4?	At-risk areas feasible for animal health	Refugees, Animal movements, Funds, Sample collection equipment	NCDC				Not suggested as a priority to be considered in the integrated surveillance of RVF to conduct a Joint risk

Commentato [AS1]: In this group we felt more comfortable to say high priority is high number
So the 4 is like the 2 in the others scale

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RVF/V opportunities to enhance One Health prevention and control								
Activity	Priority (1>5, low to high)	Feasibility (1>5) Entire country or at-risk area	Challenges	Institution in charge for coordinating the activity and main role/activities	Collaborating institutions and main role/activities	Implementation steps	Needed resources	Suggestions and opportunities
								assessment for RVF
Surveillance activities	Very important (4) for animal health, not important for humans (2)	At risk	New disease, No equipment for active surveillance, Passive surveillance no trained officers, no awareness of communities, resistance in communities to notify cases	NCAH	Share info with MoH and ESA for vector control		Yes	strengthen NCAH capacity for routine surveillance
SOPs for RVF/V control	High priority 5 for both	1 can be applied whole					Yes, for the a final meeting for validation of the SOPs alongside with the joint	

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RVF/V opportunities to enhance One Health prevention and control								
Activity	Priority (1>5, low to high)	Feasibility (1>5) Entire country or at-risk area	Challenges	Institution in charge for coordinating the activity and main role/activities	Collaborating institutions and main role/activities	Implementation steps	Needed resources	Suggestions and opportunities
							protocol of surveillance	
Training of workforce	5 for both	4 at risk	funds	NCDC/NCAH	ESA/MOE		YES	Joint trainings ToT national level (if possible train also field staff) on surveillance and diagnostics
Awareness creation at community level	4	At risk	funds	NCAH	NCDC/ESA/MOE/MEDIA Possibility of collaboration with famous/influencers as this practice has been used for vaccination campaign		Yes – limited need	Influencers from the community for human vaccination were used

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RVF/V opportunities to enhance One Health prevention and control								
Activity	Priority (1>5, low to high)	Feasibility (1>5) Entire country or at-risk area	Challenges	Institution in charge for coordinating the activity and main role/activities	Collaborating institutions and main role/activities	Implementation steps	Needed resources	Suggestions and opportunities
Laboratory diagnosis	5	At risk	Funds (animal capacity for testing, no tests) NCDC needs training	NCAH	NCDC/ESA/MOE		Yes, important need	Need laboratory equipment and testing kits
Zero reporting to international organizations	No (the person working with reporting wasn't there to provide information on the Libya practice in notification to WAHIS)							
Enforcement of mandatory notification of cases	No for both							
Rapid response teams established	5 high	5	funds	NCDC NCAH	ESA			

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RVF/V opportunities to enhance One Health prevention and control								
Activity	Priority (1>5, low to high)	Feasibility (1>5) Entire country or at-risk area	Challenges	Institution in charge for coordinating the activity and main role/activities	Collaborating institutions and main role/activities	Implementation steps	Needed resources	Suggestions and opportunities
Other activities implemented for RVF/V control								

First 3 priorities agreed:

Joint SOPs for RVF/V control

Joint Training of workforce about surveillance and diagnosis

Joint One Health RRTs

Annex 2: List of participants

Rabies working group

Name	Discipline	Agency
Mohamed Assedig Elalem	Zoonotic Disease	NCDC
Waleed salah eddin zurgani	Zoonotic Disease	ESA
Omar Ramadan Elahmer	IHR NFP	NCDC
Elsdiegali Elsyeeh	ICO	MoH
Allaaeddin Ali Shor El Salabi	Quality Directorate	MoH
Mohammed Abdulla Alhabroush	Zoonotic Disease	NCAH
Sana Mohammed Ali	Vector borne	NCAH

Brucellosis working group

Name	Discipline	Agency
Salem Alhadi Abudher	Food Safety	FDCC
Adem Salem Jomah Eljerbi	Laboratory	NCDC
Osama Nagi Elwaer	Laboratory	NCAH
Fatima Khalifa Millod	Laboratory	MoH
Abdulaziz Zorgani	Academia	Faculty of Medicine
Amina Elhadi Alostha	Laboratory	FDCC
Osama salem abograin	Quality Directorate	MoH
Rawad Sadik Hussain	RRT Surveillance	NCDC

VBDs working group

Name	Discipline	Agency
Hatem Yiuniis Almeslati	Zoonotic Diseases	NCAH
Mohamed Mostafa Hosni	Academia	Faculty of Veterinary Medicine
Hayfa Ibrahim ALKoURBU	Vector Borne	ESA
Munay Ali Algamoudi	Vector Borne	NCAH
Iman Mohamed Ben Hamza	Environmental Health	MoE
Sumia Mohamed Elarghubi	Climate Change	MoE
Yusef Ali Zwaik	Quality Directorate	MoH
Ahmed Saleh Al-Garari	Zoonotic Disease	NCDC

Facilitators

Name	Area of work	Institution
Claudia Robbiati	Public Health and epidemiology/Global Health	Istituto Superiore di Sanità
Maham Habib	Public Health and epidemiology/Global Health	Istituto Superiore di Sanità
Asma Saidouni	Veterinary Epidemiologist – Technical officer- One Health	World Health organization
Rmadhan Mohamed Osman	Technical officer – Surveillance	World Health organization

Annex 3: Agenda

Annex 3: Agenda

DAY 1 (07/07/2025) <i>The One Health approach to the Prevention, Preparedness and Response to vector-borne and zoonotic diseases in Libya</i>	
08:30 – 09:00	Registration of participants
09:00 – 10:00	<p><u>Opening Ceremony</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • National Center for Disease Control (5') • National Center for Animal Health (5') • Ministry of Environment (5') • Environmental sanitation Affairs (5') • WHO Libya (5') • ISS (5') • Introduction of participants (10') • Group Picture (10')
10:00 – 10:30	Coffee break (30')
10:30 – 12:00	<p><u>Session 1: Workshop Introduction</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • General overview of One health implementation in Libya (WHO) (10') • Introduction to the WHO-ISS project and achieved results (WHO) (10') • One Health e-learning course (10') (ISS) • Situation analysis results (ISS) (10') • Workshop objective, approach and methodology (WHO-ISS) (10') • Q&A (10') • Team building activity (30')
Lunch (12:00-13:00)	
13:00 – 14:50	<p><u>Session 2: The One Health approach for the surveillance of vector-borne and zoonotic diseases</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The OH approach for Rabies surveillance (GARC) (15') • The One Health approach for RVFV surveillance (FAO) (15') • One health surveillance of Dengue in Italy (ISS) (15') • WOAHA activities for VBDs and Zoonoses (WOAHA) (15') • Q&A and discussion (15')
14:50 – 16:30	<p><u>Session 3: Addressing policy gap (WHO)</u></p> <p>Addressing policy gap: addressing Prevention, Preparedness and Response policy change for vector borne and zoonotic disease</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Working groups (70') • Restitution (30')

16:30 – 17:00	<u>Session 4: Closure of the first day</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Introduction and preparation to next days activities (ISS) (30')
17:00 – 17:30	Group leads and moderators only: Briefing Session

DAY 2 – 08/07/2025	
<i>One Health surveillance protocols: system design</i>	
09:00 – 10 :30	<u>Session 5: One Health surveillance pillars (ISS)</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Working groups (60') Restitution (30')
10 :30 – 11 :00	Coffee break
11:00 – 12:30	<u>Session 6: - Reviewing Existing disease control plan, protocols and SoPs</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Working group (60') Restitution (30')
Lunch (12:30-13:30)	
13:30 – 14:30	<u>Session7: One Health surveillance system design: scope and actors</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Working groups (60')
14:30 – 16:00	<u>Session 8: One Health surveillance system design: system flowchart and trigger points</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Working group (60') Restitution (30') including for session 7
16:00 – 17:30	<u>Session 9: One Health surveillance cross-cutting activities</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Working group (60') Restitution (30')
17:30 – 17:40	<u>Session 10: Closure of the second day</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Introduction to day 3 activities (ISS) (10')
17.40 – 18.10	Group leads only: Compilation of results

DAY 3 – 09/07/2025	
<i>OH surveillance protocols: joint activities</i>	
09:00 – 10:30	<u>Session 11: One Health surveillance routine multisectoral data collection and reporting</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Working group (60') Restitution (30')
10:30 – 11 :00	Coffee break

11:00 – 12:30	Session 12: One Health surveillance joint risk assessment and reduction <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Working group (60') Restitution (30')
Lunch (12:30-13:30)	
13:30-15 :00	Session 13: One Health surveillance coordinated early warning and preparedness <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Working group (60') Restitution (30')
15:00–16:30	Session 14: One Health surveillance multisectoral data collection and reporting (epizootic/epidemic period) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Working group (60') Restitution (30')
16:30-16:40	Session 15: Closure of the third day <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Introduction to day 4 activities (ISS) (10')
16.40 – 17.10	Group leads only: Compilation of results

DAY 4 – 10/07/2025	
<i>OH surveillance protocols: review and next steps</i>	
09:00 – 10:30	Session 16: One Health surveillance system assumptions <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Working group (60') Restitution (30')
10:30 – 11 :00	Coffee break
11:00 – 12:30	Session 17: Review session <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Working group (90')
Lunch (12:30-13:30)	
13:30-15 :00	Session 18: Presentation of the results <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Working group (60') Restitution (30')
15:00–16:30	Session 19: OH surveillance next steps <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Working group (60') Restitution (30')
16:30-17:00	Session 20: Closure of the fourth day <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Way forward (Group leads – ISS)
17.00 – 17.30	Group leads only: Compilation of results

DAY 5 – 11/07/2025	
<i>One Health National strategy</i>	

09:00 – 10:30	<p><u>Session 21: Linking the National Bridging Workshop (NBW) outcomes and One Health National Strategy</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Presentation of NBW One Health Road map (15') • Working group (Identify the One Health Strategy pillars/strategic objectives) (30') • Restitutions, discussion & consensus (45')
10:30 – 10:45	Coffee break
10:45 – 11:30	<p><u>Session 22: Development of the strategic objectives</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Working group (60') • Restitution (15')
11:30-12:00	<p><u>Session 23: Closure of the workshop</u></p> <p>Way forward and closing remarks</p>

Annex 4: Template

Annex 4: Template

Developing Joint protocols for One health surveillance for priority zoonotic diseases in Libya

Disease name: _____

This template will guide your group to develop the foundations for a One Health surveillance protocol for the selected disease, considering the joint actions that should be performed according to multisectoral surveillance pillars (multisectoral data collection and reporting during the interepizootic/interepidemic period, joint risk assessment and reduction, coordinated early warning and preparedness, multisectoral data collection and reporting during the epizootic/epidemic period, cross-cutting activities).

Please write in English.

Each section will be followed by a restitution to the other working groups.

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Section 0. Sectoral surveillance

Day 1. Sectoral working groups.

Fill in the following tables by describing currently implemented activities for the surveillance of the selected disease in Libya according to each sector.

1. Sectoral surveillance	
1.1. Current surveillance activities (type and timeframe) for the selected disease in Libya according to the different sectors	Human health:
	Animal health:
	Environmental health:
	Other sectors:
1.2. Stakeholders involved in current surveillance activities for the selected disease in Libya according to the different sectors	Human health:
	Animal health:
	Environmental health:
	Other sectors:

1.3. How are data shared between local/district/national level for the selected disease?	Human health:
	Animal health:
	Environmental health:
	Other sectors:
1.4. Reference documents (plans, procedures etc.) for the selected disease in Libya	Human health:
	Animal health:
	Environmental health:
	Other sectors:
1.5. Other relevant information	

Section 1a. One Health surveillance system design: scope and actors

Day 2. Work in multisectoral groups.

Fill in the following table by describing practical and feasible activities to design One Health surveillance for the selected diseases in Libya.

1. One Health surveillance system design	
Components (for the selected disease)	Description

1.1. Selected disease epidemiological situation in Libya	
1.2. Scope of <u>One Health</u> surveillance for the selected disease (Link the scope of OH surveillance to the epidemiological situation)	
1.3. Actors of <u>One Health</u> surveillance for the selected disease	Human health:
	Animal health:
	Environmental health:
	Other sectors:
1.4. Type and timing/seasonality of <u>One Health</u> surveillance for the selected disease according to the scope of OH surveillance	Human health:
	Animal health:
	Environmental health:
	Other sectors:
1.5. Geographical areas (at-risk areas/entire country) of <u>One Health</u> surveillance for the selected disease	Human health:
	Animal health:
	Environmental health:
	Other sectors:

1.6. Other information relevant for the design of the OH surveillance system for the selected disease	Human health:
	Animal health:
	Environmental health:
	Other sectors:

Section 1b. One Health surveillance system design: system flowchart and trigger points

Day 2. Work in multisectoral groups.

Draw (on the flipchart) the flow of information for the One Health surveillance system of the specific disease and identify trigger points that elicit joint actions.

Section 2. One Health surveillance cross-cutting activities

Day 2. Work in multisectoral groups.

Fill in the following table by describing practical and feasible cross-cutting activities to all the pillars to implement One Health surveillance for the selected disease in Libya.

Glossary

Description: Describe the actions that the activity should cover

Responsible: Identify the responsible for the action

When: Timing of the action (every month, during a specific period etc.)

Means: Practical means that support the joint activity (excel file, meetings, shared human resources etc.)

Assumptions: Assumptions are the necessary conditions to implement the specific activity (legal framework, resources, equipment, tools, etc.)

2. One Health surveillance: cross-cutting activities	
Activity (for the selected disease)	Information
2.1. Joint governance mechanism meetings (new or existing mechanism, with the mandate to coordinate OH surveillance activities)	Description:
	Responsible:
	When:
	Means:
	Assumptions (Legal framework, resources, equipment, tools, etc.)
2.2. Definition, agreement and update of joint indicators to perform OH surveillance activities (set of minimum	Description:
	Responsible:
	When:
	Means:

<p>indicators based on trigger points to be collected to perform OH surveillance activities according to each disease e.g. weather forecasts, presence of the pathogen in vectors, temporal and spatial distribution of cases in animals etc.)</p>	<p>Assumptions (Legal framework, resources, equipment, tools, etc.)</p>
<p>2.3. Joint OH surveillance activities monitoring and evaluation (e.g. Joint surveillance Protocol SimEx)</p>	<p>Description:</p> <hr/> <p>Responsible:</p> <hr/> <p>When:</p> <hr/> <p>Means:</p> <hr/> <p>Assumptions (Legal framework, resources, equipment, tools, etc.)</p>
<p>2.4. Joint training about OH surveillance activities (e.g. training about protocols)</p>	<p>Description:</p> <hr/> <p>Responsible:</p> <hr/> <p>When:</p> <hr/> <p>Means:</p>

		Assumptions (Legal framework, resources, equipment, tools, etc.)
2.5. Joint agreements with private sector, organizations, universities and research institutes to provide essential services (e.g. data collection)	Description:	
	Responsible:	
	When:	
	Means:	
	Assumptions (Legal framework, resources, equipment, tools, etc.)	
2.6. Sharing diagnostic capacity e.g. sharing of diagnostic reagents and of expertise between veterinary and medical laboratories	Description:	
	Responsible:	
	When:	
	Means:	
	Assumptions (Legal framework, resources, equipment, tools, etc.)	
2.7. Other relevant activities	Description:	
	Responsible:	

	When:
	Means:
	Assumptions (Legal framework, resources, equipment, tools, etc.)

Section 3. One Health surveillance multisectoral routine data collection and reporting

Day 3. Work in multisectoral groups.

Fill in the following table by describing practical and feasible multisectoral routine data collection and reporting activities during the interepidemic/interepizootic period to implement One Health surveillance for the selected disease.

3. One Health surveillance: routine data collection and reporting	
Activity (for the selected disease)	Description
3.1. Exchange of epidemiological information between sectors at local/governorate level	Description:
	Responsible:
	When:
	Means:
	Assumptions (Legal framework, resources, equipment, tools, etc.)

3.2. Exchange of epidemiological information between sectors at national level	Description:
	Responsible:
	When:
	Means:
	Assumptions (Legal framework, resources, equipment, tools, etc.)
3.3. Exchange of joint epidemiological information between local/governorate and national level	Description:
	Responsible:
	When:
	Means:
	Assumptions (Legal framework, resources, equipment, tools, etc.)
3.4. Joint field data collection	Description:
	Responsible:
	When:
	Means:
	Assumptions (Legal framework, resources, equipment, tools, etc.)

3.5. Joint data analysis and interpretation	Description:
	Responsible:
	When:
	Means:
	Assumptions (Legal framework, resources, equipment, tools, etc.)
3.6. Joint reporting to local/governorate authorities	Description:
	Responsible:
	When:
	Means:
	Assumptions (Legal framework, resources, equipment, tools, etc.)
3.7. Joint reporting to national authorities	Description:
	Responsible:
	When:
	Means:
	Assumptions (Legal framework, resources, equipment, tools, etc.)
	Description:

3.8. Joint dissemination of information	Responsible:
	When:
	Means:
	Assumptions (Legal framework, resources, equipment, tools, etc.)
3.9. Joint public/community awareness	Description:
	Responsible:
	When:
	Means:
	Assumptions (Legal framework, resources, equipment, tools, etc.)
3.10. Other relevant activities	Description:
	Responsible:
	When:
	Means:
	Assumptions (Legal framework, resources, equipment, tools, etc.)

Section 4. One Health surveillance joint risk assessment and reduction

Day 3. Work in multisectoral groups.

Fill in the following table by describing practical and feasible joint risk assessment and reduction activities to implement One Health surveillance for the selected disease in Libya.

4. One Health surveillance joint risk assessment and reduction	
Activity (for the selected disease)	Information
4.1. Identification of areas at risk	Description:
	Responsible:
	When:
	Means:
	Assumptions (Legal framework, equipment, tools, etc.)
4.2. Joint risk assessment implementation	Description:
	Responsible:

	When:
	Means:
	Assumptions (Legal framework, equipment, tools, etc.)
4.3. Joint field investigation (data collection)	Description:
	Responsible:
	When:
	Means:
	Assumptions (Legal framework, resources, equipment, tools, etc.)
4.4. Joint data analysis and interpretation of risks	Description:
	Responsible:
	When:
	Means:
	Assumptions (Legal framework, resources, equipment, tools, etc.)
4.5. Joint reporting to authorities	Description:
	Responsible:
	When:

	Means:
	Assumptions (Legal framework, resources, equipment, tools, etc.)
4.6. Joint decision-making about risk reduction measures	Description:
	Responsible:
	When:
	Means:
	Assumptions (Legal framework, resources, equipment, tools, etc.)
4.7. Joint dissemination of information	Description:
	Responsible:
	When:
	Means:
	Assumptions (Legal framework, resources, equipment, tools, etc.)
4.8. Joint public/community awareness	Description:
	Responsible:
	When:
	Means:

	Assumptions (Legal framework, resources, equipment, tools, etc.)
4.9. Other relevant activities	Description:
	Responsible:
	When:
	Means:
	Assumptions (Legal framework, resources, equipment, tools, etc.)

Section 5. One Health surveillance coordinated early warning and preparedness

Day 3. Work in multisectoral groups.

Fill in the following table by describing practical and feasible coordinated early warning and preparedness activities to implement One Health surveillance for the selected disease in Libya.

5. One Health surveillance coordinated early warning and preparedness	
Activity (for the selected disease)	Information
5.1. Sharing data/information	Description:

<p>about events consistent with an outbreak (humans/animals) of the selected diseases (e.g. onset of heavy, prolonged rains, onset of increased mosquito populations, confirmation of animal case, confirmation of a human case etc.)</p>	Responsible:
	When:
	Means:
	Assumptions (Legal framework, resources, equipment, tools, etc.)
<p>5.2. Activation of joint alert mechanisms</p>	Description:
	Responsible:
	When:
	Means:
	Assumptions (Legal framework, resources, equipment, tools, etc.)
<p>5.3. Coordinate joint preparedness and response to outbreaks</p>	Description:
	Responsible:
	When:

	Means:
	Assumptions (Legal framework, resources, equipment, tools, etc.)
5.4. Other relevant activities	Description:
	Responsible:
	When:
	Means:
	Assumptions (Legal framework, resources, equipment, tools, etc.)

Section 6. One Health surveillance multisectoral data collection and reporting (epizootic/epidemic period)

Day 3. Work in multisectoral groups.

Fill in the following table by describing practical and feasible multisectoral data collection and reporting activities during the epizootic/epidemic period to implement One Health surveillance for the selected disease in Libya.

6. One Health surveillance multisectoral data collection and reporting (epizootic/epidemic period)	
Activity	Information
6.1. Mechanism to coordinate action during epizootic/epidemic period	Description:
	Responsible:
	When:
	Means:
	Assumptions (Legal framework, resources, equipment, tools, etc.)
6.2. Exchange of epidemiological information between sectors at local/governorate level	Description:
	Responsible:
	When:
	Means:
	Assumptions (Legal framework, resources, equipment, tools, etc.)
6.3. Exchange of epidemiological information between sectors at national level	Description:
	Responsible:
	When:
	Means:

		Assumptions (Legal framework, resources, equipment, tools, etc.)
6.4. Exchange of joint epidemiological information between local/governorate and national level	Description:	
	Responsible:	
	When:	
	Means:	
	Assumptions (Legal framework, resources, equipment, tools, etc.)	
6.5. Joint field data collection	Description:	
	Responsible:	
	When:	
	Means:	
	Assumptions (Legal framework, resources, equipment, tools, etc.)	
6.6. Joint data analysis and interpretation	Description:	
	Responsible:	
	When:	

	Means:
	Assumptions (Legal framework, resources, equipment, tools, etc.)
6.7. Joint reporting to local/governorate authorities	Description:
	Responsible:
	When:
	Means:
	Assumptions (Legal framework, resources, equipment, tools, etc.)
6.8. Joint reporting to national authorities	Description:
	Responsible:
	When:
	Means:
	Assumptions (Legal framework, resources, equipment, tools, etc.)
6.9. Joint dissemination of information	Description:
	Responsible:
	When:
	Means:

	Assumptions (Legal framework, resources, equipment, tools, etc.)
6.10. Joint public/community awareness	Description:
	Responsible:
	When:
	Means:
	Assumptions (Legal framework, resources, equipment, tools, etc.)
6.11. Other relevant activities:	Description:
	Responsible:
	When:
	Means:
	Assumptions (Legal framework, resources, equipment, tools, etc.)

Section 7. One Health system surveillance assumptions

Day 4. Work in multisectoral groups.

Fill in the following table by describing practical and feasible multisectoral actions to address the assumptions identified so far to implement One Health surveillance system for the selected disease in Libya.

Add as many rows as needed.

7. One Health surveillance system assumptions management	
Assumptions	Information
7.1. Assumption name:	Actions to manage the assumption:
	Responsible:
	Means:
7.2. Assumption name:	Actions to manage the assumption:
	Responsible:
	Means:
7.3. Assumption name:	Actions to manage the assumption:
	Responsible:
	Means:

Section 8. OH surveillance next steps

Day 4. Work in multisectoral groups.

Fill in the following table by describing the next steps to implement One Health surveillance for the selected disease in Libya.

Consider steps linked to the finalization of the protocol, endorsement at national level, gaps and needs to meet the requirements for the implementation of the OH surveillance activities.

Add as many rows as needed.

Step	Responsible	Timeline

Annex 5: Rabies template filled by the participants

Developing Joint protocols for One health surveillance for priority zoonotic diseases in Libya

Disease name: Rabies

This template will guide your group to develop the foundations for a One Health surveillance protocol for the selected disease, considering the joint actions that should be performed according to multisectoral surveillance pillars (multisectoral data collection and reporting during the interepizootic/interepidemic period, joint risk assessment and reduction, coordinated early warning and preparedness, multisectoral data collection and reporting during the epizootic/epidemic period, cross-cutting activities).

Please write in English.

Each section will be followed by a restitution to the other working groups.

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Section 0. Sectoral surveillance

Day 1. Sectoral working groups.

Fill in the following tables by describing currently implemented activities for the surveillance of the selected disease in Libya according to each sector.

1. Sectoral surveillance	
1.1. Current surveillance activities (type and timeframe) for the selected disease in Libya according to the different sectors	Human health:
	Animal health:
	Environmental health:
	Other sectors:
1.2. Stakeholders involved in current surveillance activities for the selected disease in Libya according to the different sectors	Human health:
	Animal health:
	Environmental health:
	Other sectors:
1.3. How are data shared between local/district/national level for the selected disease?	Human health:
	Animal health:
	Environmental health:

	Other sectors:
1.4. Reference documents (plans, procedures etc.) for the selected disease in Libya	Human health:
	Animal health:
	Environmental health:
	Other sectors:
1.5. Other relevant information	

Section 1a. One Health surveillance system design: scope and actors

Day 2. Work in multisectoral groups.

Fill in the following table by describing practical and feasible activities to design One Health surveillance for the selected diseases in Libya.

1. One Health surveillance system design	
Components (for the selected disease)	Description
1.1. Selected disease epidemiological situation in Libya	Not endemic (sporadic cases), for human and animal health.
1.2. Scope of <u>One Health</u> surveillance for the selected disease (Link the scope of	Surveillance of rabies exists in animal and human health, despite lack of sop's or guide lines in the animal health.

OH surveillance to the epidemiological situation)	
1.3. Actors of <u>One Health</u> surveillance for the selected disease	Human health: RRTs
	Animal health: Passive surveillance from private vets and animal health offices in the municipalities
	Environmental health: no surveillance but the control through environmental offices in the municipalities
	Other sectors: ESA: no surveillance but there is control procedures
1.4. Type and timing/seasonality of <u>One Health</u> surveillance for the selected disease according to the scope of OH surveillance	Human health: N/A
	Animal health: N/A
	Environmental health: N/A
	Other sectors:
1.5. Geographical areas (at-risk areas/entire country) of <u>One Health</u> surveillance for the selected disease	Human health: The areas at risk (western mountain region , and the cities near the western border of Libya with Tunisia). Surveillance activities should be performed.
	Animal health: The areas at risk (western mountain region , and the cities near the western border of Libya with Tunisia). Surveillance activities should be performed.
	Environmental health: The areas at risk (western mountain region , and the cities near the western border of Libya with Tunisia). Surveillance activities should be performed.

	Other sectors:
1.6. Other information relevant for the design of the OH surveillance system for the selected disease	Human health: building integrated surveillance and data sharing systems in Rabies.
	Animal health: building integrated surveillance and data sharing systems in Rabies
	Environmental health: building integrated surveillance and data sharing systems in Rabies
	Other sectors:

Section 1b. One Health surveillance system design: system flowchart and trigger points

Day 2. Work in multisectoral groups.

Draw (on the flipchart) the flow of information for the One Health surveillance system of the specific disease and identify trigger points that elicit joint actions.

Section 2. One Health surveillance cross-cutting activities

Day 2. Work in multisectoral groups.

Fill in the following table by describing practical and feasible cross-cutting activities to all the pillars to implement One Health surveillance for the selected disease in Libya.

Glossary

Description: Describe the actions that the activity should cover

Responsible: Identify the responsible for the action

When: Timing of the action (every month, during a specific period etc.)

Means: Practical means that support the joint activity (excel file, meetings, shared human resources etc.)

Assumptions: Assumptions are the necessary conditions to implement the specific activity (legal framework, resources, equipment, tools, etc.)

2. One Health surveillance: cross-cutting activities	
Activity (for the selected disease)	Information
2.1. Joint governance mechanism meetings (new or existing mechanism, with the mandate to coordinate OH surveillance activities)	Description: OH high committee.
	Responsible: OH HIGH COMITTE+ OH ADISORY COMMITTEE.
	When: ROUTINE "QUARTERLY".
	Means: PHYSICAL MEETINGS.
	Assumptions (Legal framework, resources, equipment, tools, etc.) DECREE.
	Description:

2.2. Definition, agreement and update of joint indicators to perform OH surveillance activities (set of minimum indicators based on trigger points to be collected to perform OH surveillance activities according to each disease e.g. weather forecasts, presence of the pathogen in vectors, temporal and spatial distribution of cases in animals etc.)	OH SURVILLANCE JOINT INDICATORS.
	Responsible: ADVISORY COMMITTEE, NATIONAL TECHNICAL TEAMS.
	When: In the preparatory stage, and updated regularly.
	Means: Regular meetings. Consultation, technical support from international organizations.
	Assumptions (Legal framework, resources, equipment, tools, etc.) IT tools, IT experts, international organizations resources.
2.3. Joint OH surveillance activities monitoring and evaluation (e.g. Joint surveillance Protocol SimEx)	Description: Development of joint monitoring and evaluation program.
	Responsible: OH advisory committee.
	When: During OH joint surveillance System building.
	Means: OH, joint indicators and monitoring evaluation tool.
	Assumptions (Legal framework, resources, equipment, tools, etc.)

	Guide lines, external assistance, fund.
2.4. Joint training about OH surveillance activities (e.g. training about protocols)	Description: OH surveillance training package
	Responsible: OH advisory committee and Expertise in each sectors
	When: Upon finalizing OH surveillance protocol based on OH training plan.
	Means: TOT's and training workshops.
	Assumptions (Legal framework, resources, equipment, tools, etc.) Training package, surveillance protocol, SEMex.
2.5. Joint agreements with private sector, organizations, universities and research institutes to provide essential services (e.g. data collection)	Description: Mutual cooperation.
	Responsible: Technical cooperation offices at OH sectors.
	When: When needed.
	Means: Agreements, MOU's, joint protocols.
	Assumptions (Legal framework, resources, equipment, tools, etc.) To benefit from their expertise, use of their facility for trainings and research purposes.
2.6. Sharing diagnostic capacity e.g. sharing of diagnostic reagents and of expertise	Description: Sharing diagnostic capacity.
	Responsible: Reference laboratory at OH sectors.
	When:

between veterinary and medical laboratories	Exchange resources when needed.
	Means: Through communications between heads of reference laboratories.
	Assumptions (Legal framework, resources, equipment, tools, etc.) Transfer of technology, retesting.
2.7. Other relevant activities (establish quality management system)	Description: Establish quality management system.
	Responsible: International organizations.
	When: According on planning.
	Means: Training evaluation, assistance, documentation, safety, human resources.
	Assumptions (Legal framework, resources, equipment, tools, etc.) Full package of quality management system.

Section 3. One Health surveillance multisectoral routine data collection and reporting

Day 3. Work in multisectoral groups.

Fill in the following table by describing practical and feasible multisectoral routine data collection and reporting activities during the interepidemic/interepizootic period to implement One Health surveillance for the selected disease.

3. One Health surveillance: routine data collection and reporting
--

Activity (for the selected disease)	Description
3.1. Exchange of epidemiological information between sectors at local/governorate level	Description: Exchange epi-info between focal points at local authorities throw mobile phone and official letter.
	Responsible: primary health care \ vet clinic\ environment monitoring office \ESA office.
	When: Immediately, regular info sharing "weekly, monthly"
	Means: Phone calls followed by official letter.
	Assumptions (Legal framework, resources, equipment, tools, etc.) Appointment of "focal points" at local level, standardized reporting forms, improve data sharing infrastructure.
3.2. Exchange of epidemiological information between sectors at national level	Description: Exchange epi-info at national level, throw mobile phone and official letter.
	Responsible: NCDC, NCAH ,ESA, ENVIROMENT
	When: Immediately, regular info: weekly\monthly, regular meetings
	Means: Phone calls followed by official letter.
	Assumptions (Legal framework, resources, equipment, tools, etc.) Monthly Multisectoral committee meetings for info sharing.
3.3. Exchange of joint epidemiological information between	Description: Vertical communication between local authorities and central levels for each sector
	Responsible: Central level of each sector is responsible to maintain the communication channels.

local/governorate and national level	When: Immediately, regular info: weekly\monthly, regular meetings
	Means: IT tools
	Assumptions (Legal framework, resources, equipment, tools, etc.) Trained human resources
3.4. Joint field data collection	Description: DATA collection related to any event reported from related or relevant sector
	Responsible: OH RRT
	When: Based on reporting as soon as possible.
	Means: Specimen collection kits , investigation forms, transportations, logistics.
	Assumptions (Legal framework, resources, equipment, tools, etc.) Human resources capacity building, electronic tools, investigation kits.
3.5. Joint data analysis and interpretation	Description: Joint analysis and interpretation of field data
	Responsible: Technical expertise in relevant sectors.
	When: When the field data is available.
	Means: Electronic data analysis tools, and/or manually by epidemiologists.
	Assumptions (Legal framework, resources, equipment, tools, etc.) Fund, trained personal in data analysis, and software.
3.6. Joint reporting to local/governorate authorities	Description: Joint final reports.
	Responsible: OH field task force team

	When: After finalizing field data report.
	Means: Dissemination of the final report to governorate authorities.
	Assumptions (Legal framework, resources, equipment, tools, etc.) Cover letter.
3.7. Joint reporting to national authorities	Description: Joint final reports.
	Responsible: Local/governorate authorities
	When: After receiving the final report from the local authorities.
	Means: Official letter and OH official meetings.
	Assumptions (Legal framework, resources, equipment, tools, etc.) Cover letter.
3.8. Joint dissemination of information	Description:
	Responsible: OH authorities.
	When: After getting official clearance.
	Means: Pollutant, media , emails, medical journals, one health conference.
	Assumptions (Legal framework, resources, equipment, tools, etc.) Fund, approval from concerned authorities.
	Description: Joint awareness campaigns

3.9. Joint public/community awareness	Responsible: OH media departments at sectors.
	When: Regular campaigns.
	Means: Media, world rabies day, posters. Fliers.
	Assumptions (Legal framework, resources, equipment, tools, etc.) Funds, resources

Section 4. One Health surveillance joint risk assessment and reduction

Day 3. Work in multisectoral groups.

Fill in the following table by describing practical and feasible joint risk assessment and reduction activities to implement One Health surveillance for the selected disease in Libya.

4. One Health surveillance joint risk assessment and reduction	
Activity (for the selected disease)	Information
4.1. Identification of areas at risk	Description: Joint risk assessment planning.

	Responsible: NCDC, NCAH, ESA, ENVIROMENT.
	When: Annually risk assessment of the areas at risk.
	Means: joint checklist. <i>according to mapping of dog population, number of cases of dog bites.</i>
	Assumptions (Legal framework, equipment, tools, etc.) Fund, transportation, logistics, ICT.
4.2. Joint risk assessment implementation	Description: Conducted through field joint risk assessment.
	Responsible: Quadripartite OH Risk assessment team.
	When: Annually.
	Means: Through field visits , interviews with locals.
	Assumptions (Legal framework, equipment, tools, etc.) Electronic checklist, GIS.
4.3. Joint field investigation (data collection)	Description: Joint field data collection.
	Responsible: Quadripartite OH Risk assessment team.
	When: Annually after implementation of joint risk assessment.
	Means: Data collection tool.
	Assumptions (Legal framework, resources, equipment, tools, etc.)

	Logistics. Official communication.
4.4. Joint data analysis and interpretation of risks	Description: Joint data analysis between sectors.
	Responsible: Joint OH epidemiologists.
	When: After implantation of joint data collection.
	Means: statistical and epi-analysis.
	Assumptions (Legal framework, resources, equipment, tools, etc.) Funds, Data analysis programs, data analysis expertise.
4.5. Joint reporting to authorities	Description: Joint risk assessment final reports.
	Responsible: OH risk assesment team.
	When: After finalizing risk assessment report.
	Means: Dissemination of the final report to authorities.
	Assumptions (Legal framework, resources, equipment, tools, etc.) Cover letter.
4.6. Joint decision-making about risk reduction measures	Description: Action taking by decision makers
	Responsible: OH Authorities.
	When: Upon receiving final risk assessment report.
	Means: Joint meetings of the OH authorities.

	Assumptions (Legal framework, resources, equipment, tools, etc.)
4.7. Joint dissemination of information	Description: Risk assessment dissemination.
	Responsible: OH authorities.
	When: After getting official clearance.
	Means: Pollutant, media , emails, medical journals, one health conference.
	Assumptions (Legal framework, resources, equipment, tools, etc.) Fund, approval from concerned authorities.
4.8. Joint public/community awareness	Description: Joint awareness campaigns
	Responsible: OH media departments at sectors.
	When: Regular campaigns.
	Means: Media, world rabies day, posters. Fliers.
	Assumptions (Legal framework, resources, equipment, tools, etc.) Funds, resources.
4.9. Other relevant activities	Description: Risk Mitigation Measures
	Responsible: NCAH
	When: Annually.
	Means:
	Assumptions (Legal framework, resources, equipment, tools, etc.)

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Section 5. One Health surveillance coordinated early warning and preparedness

Day 3. Work in multisectoral groups.

Fill in the following table by describing practical and feasible coordinated early warning and preparedness activities to implement One Health surveillance for the selected disease in Libya.

5. One Health surveillance coordinated early warning and preparedness	
Activity (for the selected disease)	Information
5.1. Sharing data/information about events consistent with an outbreak (humans/animals) of the selected diseases (e.g. onset of heavy, prolonged rains, onset of increased mosquito populations, confirmation of animal case,	Description: Signal Reports from Relevant Sectors
	Responsible: NCDC, ESA, NCDC, and Environment
	When: Upon Receiving Signal Notification
	Means: Notification from Surveillance Officer
	Assumptions (Legal framework, resources, equipment, tools, etc.): Joint-IT tools, Qualified Human Resources to conduct verification processes.

confirmation of a human case etc.)	
5.2. Activation of joint alert mechanisms	<p>Description: Activation of Early Warning System</p> <p>Responsible: Early warning staff at NCDC, NCAH, ESA, and Environment</p> <p>When: Upon Receiving Signal</p> <p>Means: Joint-SOPs and Communication channels,</p> <p>Assumptions (Legal framework, resources, equipment, tools, etc.): Electronic tools, Capacity building, and Detection capacity</p>
5.3. Coordinate joint preparedness and response to outbreaks	<p>Description: Joint Preparedness to Outbreaks</p> <p>Responsible: Joint-OH Sectors</p> <p>When: After finalizing risk assessment</p> <p>Means: Joint preparedness and response plan</p> <p>Assumptions (Legal framework, resources, equipment, tools, etc.): Funding to develop preparedness response plan, and Expert Support and Finding of risk assessment</p>
5.4. Other relevant activities (Simulation exercise After Action Review)	<p>Description: Outbreak lessons learned.</p> <p>Responsible: Technical expertise in relevant sectors.</p> <p>When: End of an outbreak</p> <p>Means: Round table discussions, evaluation, challenges, effectiveness of preparedness and response.</p> <p>Assumptions (Legal framework, resources, equipment, tools, etc.): Expertise, conduct SIMex and after-action review.</p>

Section 6. One Health surveillance multisectoral data collection and reporting (epizootic/epidemic period)

Day 3. Work in multisectoral groups.

Fill in the following table by describing practical and feasible multisectoral data collection and reporting activities during the epizootic/epidemic period to implement One Health surveillance for the selected disease in Libya.

6. One Health surveillance multisectoral data collection and reporting (epizootic/epidemic period)	
Activity	Information
6.1. Mechanism to coordinate action during epizootic/epidemic period	Description:
	Responsible:
	When:
	Means:
	Assumptions (Legal framework, resources, equipment, tools, etc.)
6.2. Exchange of epidemiological information between	Description:
	Responsible:

sectors at local/governorate level	
	When:
	Means:
	Assumptions (Legal framework, resources, equipment, tools, etc.)
6.3. Exchange of epidemiological information between sectors at national level	Description:
	Responsible:
	When:
	Means:
	Assumptions (Legal framework, resources, equipment, tools, etc.)
6.4. Exchange of joint epidemiological information between local/governorate and national level	Description:
	Responsible:
	When:
	Means:
	Assumptions (Legal framework, resources, equipment, tools, etc.)
6.5. Joint field data collection	Description:
	Responsible:

		When:
		Means:
		Assumptions (Legal framework, resources, equipment, tools, etc.)
6.6. Joint data analysis and interpretation		Description:
		Responsible:
		When:
		Means:
		Assumptions (Legal framework, resources, equipment, tools, etc.)
6.7. Joint reporting to local/governorate authorities		Description:
		Responsible:
		When:
		Means:
		Assumptions (Legal framework, resources, equipment, tools, etc.)
6.8. Joint reporting to national authorities		Description:
		Responsible:
		When:

	Means:
	Assumptions (Legal framework, resources, equipment, tools, etc.)
6.9. Joint dissemination of information	Description:
	Responsible:
	When:
	Means:
	Assumptions (Legal framework, resources, equipment, tools, etc.)
6.10. Joint public/community awareness	Description:
	Responsible:
	When:
	Means:
	Assumptions (Legal framework, resources, equipment, tools, etc.)
6.11. Other relevant activities:	Description:
	Responsible:
	When:

	Means:
	Assumptions (Legal framework, resources, equipment, tools, etc.)

Section 7. One Health system surveillance assumptions

Day 4. Work in multisectoral groups.

Fill in the following table by describing practical and feasible multisectoral actions to address the assumptions identified so far to implement One Health surveillance system for the selected disease in Libya.

Add as many rows as needed.

7. One Health surveillance system assumptions management	
Assumptions	Information
7.1. Assumption name:	Actions to manage the assumption:
	Responsible:

	Means:
7.2. Assumption name:	Actions to manage the assumption:
	Responsible:
	Means:
7.3. Assumption name:	Actions to manage the assumption:
	Responsible:
	Means:

Section 8. OH surveillance next steps

Day 4. Work in multisectoral groups.

Fill in the following table by describing the next steps to implement One Health surveillance for the selected disease in Libya.

Consider steps linked to the finalization of the protocol, endorsement at national level, gaps and needs to meet the requirements for the implementation of the OH surveillance activities.

Add as many rows as needed.

Priority joint action(feasible)	Description	Step	Responsible	Timeline	Needed resources(assumptions)
Integrated Bite Case Management (IBCM) Enhancement	Coordinated investigation and management of all animal bite cases, linking human and animal health data.	Standardize reporting forms; train human/animal health workers on joint protocols; establish rapid communication channels; ensure timely PEP access and animal observation/testing.	NCDC, NCAH), ESA, ENVIROMENT.	6 months	Joint training materials, communication platforms (e.g., shared online database), diagnostic kits, PEP supplies, transportation for field investigations.
Risk communication and Community Engagement.	Educate communities on rabies risks, prevention, and the importance of reporting suspicious animal behavior and bite incidents to relevant authorities.	conduct community workshops/campaigns. Develop communication materials	NCDC, NCAH), ESA, ENVIROMENT.	Short-term (3-6 months	Information education materials (posters, brochures), community health workers, public awareness campaign budget, dedicated reporting infrastructure
Develop Rabies SOP's on: 1-Rabies data sharing and analysis 2- Rabies Laboratory diagnostics	Develop SOP's	Collection of information, technical meeting,	NCDC, NCAH), ESA, ENVIROMENT	12 MONTHS	Trained staff,

Annex 6: Brucellosis template filled by the participants

Developing Joint protocols for One health surveillance for priority zoonotic diseases in Libya

Disease name: Brucellosis

This template will guide your group to develop the foundations for a One Health surveillance protocol for the selected disease, considering the joint actions that should be performed according to multisectoral surveillance pillars (multisectoral data collection and reporting during the interepizootic/interepidemic period, joint risk assessment and reduction, coordinated early warning and preparedness, multisectoral data collection and reporting during the epizootic/epidemic period, cross-cutting activities).

Please write in English.

Each section will be followed by a restitution to the other working groups.

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Section 0. Sectoral surveillance

Day 1. Sectoral working groups.

Fill in the following tables by describing currently implemented activities for the surveillance of the selected disease in Libya according to each sector.

1. Sectoral surveillance	
1.1. Current surveillance activities (type and timeframe) for the selected disease in Libya according to the different sectors	Human health: Passive
	Animal health: Active
	Environmental health: No
	Other sectors: No
1.2. Stakeholders involved in current surveillance activities for the selected disease in Libya according to the different sectors	Human health: MOH, NCDC, FDCC, ESA,
	Animal health: MOA, ESA, WOAHO
	Environmental health: ESA
	Other sectors: FAO, WHO, Syndicate, NSMC
1.3. How are data shared between local/district/national level for the selected disease?	Human health: No
	Animal health: Incidence Report (NCDC WOAHO)
	Environmental health: No

	Other sectors:	No
1.4. Reference documents (plans, procedures etc.) for the selected disease in Libya	Human health:	Yes (Guideline, plan, Protocol)
	Animal health:	No
	Environmental health:	No
	Other sectors:	No
1.5. Other relevant information		

Section 1a. One Health surveillance system design: scope and actors

Day 2. Work in multisectoral groups.

Fill in the following table by describing practical and feasible activities to design One Health surveillance for the selected diseases in Libya.

1. One Health surveillance system design	
Components (for the selected disease)	Description
1.1. Selected disease epidemiological situation in Libya	Sporadic cases (The whole country) Males
1.2. Scope of <u>One Health</u> surveillance for the selected disease (Link the scope of	Index case or suspected are detection by diagnostic technique and confirmed to establish a channel of communicate with NACH HQ then communicate with NCDC, followed by the NCDC will share the data with MOH, WHO and WOH

OH surveillance to the epidemiological situation)	
1.3. Actors of <u>One Health</u> surveillance for the selected disease	Human health: MOH, NCDC, FDCC, ESA,
	Animal health: MOA, ESA, WOA
	Environmental health: ESA
	Other sectors: FAO, WHO, WOA, Syndicate, NSMC
1.4. Type and timing/seasonality of <u>One Health</u> surveillance for the selected disease according to the scope of OH surveillance	Human health: No Season
	Animal health: No Season
	Environmental health:
	Other sectors:
1.5. Geographical areas (at-risk areas/entire country) of <u>One Health</u> surveillance for the selected disease	Human health: ALL
	Animal health: ALL
	Environmental health:
	Other sectors:
1.6. Other information relevant for the design of the OH surveillance system for the selected disease	Human health: Share the data with all relevant sectors
	Animal health: Share the data with all relevant sectors
	Environmental health: Share the data with all relevant sectors

	Other sectors:
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Section 1b. One Health surveillance system design: system flowchart and trigger points

Day 2. Work in multisectoral groups.

Draw (on the flipchart) the flow of information for the One Health surveillance system of the specific disease and identify trigger points that elicit joint actions.

Section 2. One Health surveillance cross-cutting activities

Day 2. Work in multisectoral groups.

Fill in the following table by describing practical and feasible cross-cutting activities to all the pillars to implement One Health surveillance for the selected disease in Libya.

Glossary

Description: Describe the actions that the activity should cover

Responsible: Identify the responsible for the action

When: Timing of the action (every month, during a specific period etc.)

Means: Practical means that support the joint activity (excel file, meetings, shared human resources etc.)

Assumptions: Assumptions are the necessary conditions to implement the specific activity (legal framework, resources, equipment, tools, etc.)

2. One Health surveillance: cross-cutting activities	
Activity (for the selected disease)	Information
2.1. Joint governance mechanism meetings (new or existing mechanism, with the mandate to coordinate OH surveillance activities)	Description: Establish focal points in all geographical areas to communicate to surveillance governance in both human and animal
	Responsible: Task force Zoonotic disease (NACH, MOA, MOH, NCDC)
	When: meeting quarterly
	Means: To review trends, reports, data analysis, bulletins
	Assumptions (Legal framework, resources, equipment, tools, etc.) To develop strategy, review challenges, identify gaps, provide budget
2.2. Definition, agreement and update of joint indicators to perform OH surveillance activities (set of minimum indicators based on trigger points to be collected to perform OH surveillance)	Description: Establish focal points in all geographical areas to communicate to surveillance governance in both human and animal sectors, define indicators, action plan with time to develop strategy
	Responsible: Task force Zoonotic disease (NACH, MOA, MOH, NCDC, MoLA)
	When: Quarterly
	Means: To analyze key performance indicators identify the risks associated with transmission of disease to humans Clear mandates and inter-ministerial agreements for data sharing and collaboration between sectors
	Assumptions (Legal framework, resources, equipment, tools, etc.)

<p>activities according to each disease e.g. weather forecasts, presence of the pathogen in vectors, temporal and spatial distribution of cases in animals etc.)</p>	<p>review challenges, identify gaps, provide budget, advanced data international tools</p>
<p>2.3. Joint OH surveillance activities monitoring and evaluation (e.g. Joint surveillance Protocol SimEx)</p>	<p>Description: To determine specific processes and scope of monitoring and evaluation for One Health surveillance activities. Conduct simulations or exercises might be part of the evaluation process to test protocols. The generated data should be quality, timeliness, collaboration effectiveness) and perform regular reviews, specific assessments, simulation exercises results</p> <p>Responsible: This identify the individual, team, or entity accountable for overseeing and conducting the monitoring and evaluation activities and feedback to Task force Zoonotic disease (NACH, MOA, MOH, NCDC)</p> <p>When: "quarterly reviews," "annual reports," "after each major surveillance campaign," or "before new protocols are implemented.</p> <p>Means: This details the methods, tools, and resources used for monitoring and evaluation. This could include data analysis software, dashboards, review meetings, questionnaires, simulation exercise tools, or specific indicators for evaluation.</p> <p>Assumptions (Legal framework, resources, equipment, tools, etc.)</p>
<p>2.4. Joint training about OH surveillance activities (e.g.</p>	<p>Description: To determine the content and scope of the joint training to cover specific modules, learning objectives, target audience (e.g., veterinarians, public health officers, lab technicians), and the focus areas. The example "training about SOPs" indicates a focus on standardized procedures.</p>

training about protocols)	Responsible: All sectors involved in data sharing
	When: "biannually," "as part of onboarding for new staff," or "prior to the start of disease seasons or support from international organization
	Means: Workshop formats, online learning platforms, field exercises, training materials, facilitators, and training venues.
	Assumptions (Legal framework, resources, equipment, tools, etc.)
2.5. Joint agreements with private sector, organizations, universities and research institutes to provide essential services (e.g. data collection)	Description: Establish a collaborations with external entities to identify data collection mechanisms from all partners that include laboratory analysis, specialized research, technical assistance, or sharing of expertise/resources.
	Responsible: All stakeholders or entity responsible for initiating, negotiating, formalizing, and managing these joint agreements.
	When: Prior to project commencement, on an ongoing basis as needs arise and potentially their duration.
	Means: To describes mechanisms through which these agreements will be established and operationalized. This might involve Memoranda of Understanding (MOUs), contracts, partnership frameworks, specific terms of reference, and defined communication channels.
	Assumptions (Legal framework, resources, equipment, tools, etc.)
	Description:

<p>2.6. Sharing diagnostic capacity e.g. sharing of diagnostic reagents and of expertise between veterinary and medical laboratories</p>	<p>Establish and strengthen a formal and organized mechanism for sharing diagnostic capacities related to Brucellosis between public health (human) and veterinary laboratories in Libya. This includes the exchange of diagnostic reagents, standards, testing protocols, and advanced diagnostic techniques (e.g., PCR, genetic sequencing).</p> <p>The goal is to standardize diagnostic methods, improve the accuracy (specificity and sensitivity) and speed of results, and maximize the utilization of available resources for Brucellosis diagnosis in both humans and animals. It also encompasses the exchange of expertise and technical knowledge among laboratory personnel.</p>
	<p>Responsible: Local entities, private sectors and International organization</p>
	<p>When:</p> <p>Phase 1 (Assessment & Planning): 3-6 months (e.g., Q3 2025 - Q4 2025) - Assess current laboratory capacities, identify needs, and develop joint cooperation protocols.</p> <p>Phase 2 (Implementation & Training): 6-12 months (e.g., Q1 2026 - Q4 2026) - Initiate sharing, organize joint training workshops, and standardize procedures.</p> <p>Phase 3 (Scale-up & Continuous Monitoring): Ongoing after initial success - Expand collaboration to include other sub-laboratories and ensure sustainability of exchange and development.</p>
	<p>Means:</p> <p>Assumptions (Legal framework, resources, equipment, tools, etc.):</p> <p>Legal Framework: Establishment of a Memorandum of Understanding (MOU) or formal agreement between the Ministry of Health and the Ministry of Agriculture, Livestock and Marine Resources for diagnostic capacity sharing. Development of standardized protocols for sample collection, transportation, testing, and result sharing. Legal framework to facilitate the import and distribution of reagents and equipment.</p> <p>Resources: Human Resources: Qualified laboratory technicians, infectious disease specialists, laboratory quality experts from both sectors. Financial Resources: Dedicated budget allocation for reagent procurement, equipment maintenance, staff training, and transportation costs.</p>

	<p>Infrastructure: Adequate laboratory space, appropriate storage systems for reagents (e.g., refrigerators, freezers).</p> <p>Equipment & Tools: Availability of basic (e.g., Rose Bengal, Tube Agglutination Test, ELISA reagents) and specific (e.g., PCR reagents) diagnostic reagents for Brucellosis. Necessary laboratory equipment (centrifuges, incubators, PCR machines, ELISA readers, microscopes). Laboratory Information Management Systems (LIMS) to ensure data accuracy and sample traceability. Sample transport equipment with cold chain maintenance. Availability of specialized technical expertise in Brucellosis diagnosis and confirmation.</p> <p>Assumptions (Legal framework, resources, equipment, tools, etc.)</p>
<p>2.7. Other relevant activities</p>	<p>Description: To develop policies, guidelines, research data, SOPs, bi-annually bulletin</p> <p>Suggested Examples:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> * Organization of joint health and veterinary awareness campaigns: Targeting livestock breeders, animal product vendors, and the general public on Brucellosis risks, transmission routes, and the importance of prevention (e.g., boiling milk, safe animal handling, vaccination). * Development and implementation of regular livestock vaccination programs against Brucellosis: In collaboration between veterinary authorities and breeders, focusing on high-risk areas. * Enhancement of periodic epidemiological surveillance programs: In livestock herds and at-risk human populations to determine disease prevalence and assess the effectiveness of control programs. * Conducting joint applied research: On Brucellosis transmission dynamics in the Libyan context, identification of circulating strains, and assessment of risk factors. * Preparation and implementation of a rapid joint outbreak response plan: Defining roles, responsibilities, and necessary actions upon detection of a Brucellosis outbreak in either sector. <p>Responsible: * Primary Entities:</p>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> * Ministry of Health (Health Promotion Department, NCDC). * Ministry of Agriculture, Livestock and Marine Resources (Veterinary Services Department, NCAH). * Collaborating Agencies: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> * Academic and research institutions. * Non-governmental organizations working in health and rural development. * Professional syndicates (doctors, veterinarians). * Media outlets.
	<p>When:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> * Awareness Campaigns: Regular and ongoing, intensified as needed or during specific seasons. * Vaccination and Survey Programs: Annually or semi-annually, according to national plans. * Research: Continuous, based on identified research priorities. * Response Plans: Should be developed within a short timeframe (e.g., 6-9 months) and updated regularly.
	<p>Means: AS above</p>
	<p>Assumptions (Legal framework, resources, equipment, tools, etc.)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> * Legal Framework: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> * Existence of national policies supporting joint awareness, vaccination, and research programs. * Clear delineation of authorities for relevant bodies to implement these activities. * Resources: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> * Human Resources: Health education specialists, field veterinarians, researchers. * Financial Resources: Dedicated funding for campaigns, vaccine procurement, survey implementation, and research. * Infrastructure: Veterinary and human health centers, farms, laboratories. * Equipment & Tools: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> * Educational materials (posters, brochures, videos). * Brucellosis vaccines for livestock. * Field sample collection equipment.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> * Statistical software for epidemiological data analysis. * Transportation for field teams. * Platforms for joint communication and coordination
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Section 3. One Health surveillance multisectoral routine data collection and reporting

Day 3. Work in multisectoral groups.

Fill in the following table by describing practical and feasible multisectoral routine data collection and reporting activities during the interepidemic/interepizootic period to implement One Health surveillance for the selected disease.

3. One Health surveillance: routine data collection and reporting	
Activity (for the selected disease)	Description
3.1. Exchange of epidemiological information between sectors at local/governorate level	<p>Description: from NCAH. In case of positive case, share information with NCDC (zoonotic disease department). The issue is currently, the NCAH Field officer have to inform the NCAH central level and who will inform the NCDC central level then will inform the NCDC decentralized office of the same location initially detected the case.</p> <p>We suggest that local NCAH, informs the local NCDC focal point at field level at the same time the information is shared with the national level + ESA field level</p>
	<p>Responsible: NCAH Focal point to notify NCDC focal point at the field level as well as national level of NCDC</p>

	<p>When: Detection of positive case of Brucellosis</p> <p>Means: WhatsApp and call (for the speed to take action in the meantime to receive the official communication from the central) List of variables to be agreed on</p> <p>Assumptions (Legal framework, resources, equipment, tools, etc.) To include animal and human</p>
3.2. Exchange of epidemiological information between sectors at national level	<p>Description: We suggest a Monthly sharing of compiled data on confirmed cases of Brucellosis</p> <p>Responsible: NCDC/NCAH Focal point to the NCDC/NCAH focal point and FDCC central level MoH to share monthly results if detected from the Hospitals to the NCDC</p> <p>When: Monthly</p> <p>Means: Excel (List of variables to be confirmed and agreed on)</p> <p>Assumptions (Legal framework, resources, equipment, tools, etc.): laptop needed</p>
3.3. Exchange of joint epidemiological information between local/governorate and national level	<p>Description: from NCAH field level, information is shared in case of positive case with NCDC (zoonotic disease department) at central level. The issue is currently, the NCAH Field officer have to inform the NCAH central level and who will inform the NCDC central level then will inform the NCDC decentralized office of the same location initially detected the case. NCAH Field → NCAH Central → NCDC central + FDCC+ ESA</p> <p>Responsible: same like before</p> <p>When: confirmed cases</p> <p>Means: whatsapp</p>

	Assumptions (Legal framework, resources, equipment, tools, etc.)
3.4. Joint field data collection	Description: no need for a joint field data collection. We suggest that each sector collects its own data and share the needed data with other sectors. We suggest to agree on a joint set of data to be collected.
	Responsible: Emergency response teams at municipal level, coordinated with national authorities.
	When: During outbreak alerts, suspected cases, or seasonal surveillance campaigns.
	Means: Pre-agreed joint field plans, shared data collection tools, and logistical support
	Assumptions (Legal framework, resources, equipment, tools, etc.)
3.5. Joint data analysis and interpretation	Description: We suggest to agree on a joint set of data and indicators to be analysed.
	Responsible: Central level of each sector
	When:
	Means:
	Assumptions (Legal framework, resources, equipment, tools, etc.)
3.6. Joint reporting to local/governorate authorities	Description: We suggest to develop a joint report of the surveillance (epidemiological situation) with key action conducted
	Responsible: NCDC/NCAH/ESA focal points at field
	When: Every three months.
	Means:

	Word report
	Assumptions (Legal framework, resources, equipment, tools, etc.)
3.7. Joint reporting to national authorities	Description: As previous
	Responsible: Local health offices, NCAH branches, and local environment offices; submitted to Ministry of Health, NCAH central office, and Environmental General Authority.
	When: Every three months
	Means: Email reports, hard copies, or use of digital platforms (where available).
	Assumptions (Legal framework, resources, equipment, tools, etc.)
3.8. Joint dissemination of information	Description: As previous
	Responsible: Communication units within MoH , NCAH, and the Environmental Authority.
	When: After significant surveillance updates or on a bi-monthly basis.
	Means: Newsletters, official statements, printed bulletins, and online dissemination.
	Assumptions (Legal framework, resources, equipment, tools, etc.)
3.9. Joint public/community awareness	Description: Develop joint communication and awareness material and organize joint awareness campaign in high risk areas
	Responsible: NCDC, NCAH, ESA

	When: Absolutely after each human case Periodically for example around EID
	Means: All media
	Assumptions (Legal framework, resources, equipment, tools, etc.)
3.10. Other relevant activities	Description: Develop a National strategy for eradication of Brucellosis
	Responsible: One Health national coordination committee, in collaboration with WHO, FAO, and OIE/WOAH partners
	When: Quarterly, or immediately in the case of outbreaks or alerts.
	Means: Email reports, hard copies, or use of digital platforms (where available).
	Assumptions (Legal framework, resources, equipment, tools, etc.)

Section 4. One Health surveillance joint risk assessment and reduction

Day 3. Work in multisectoral groups.

Fill in the following table by describing practical and feasible joint risk assessment and reduction activities to implement One Health surveillance for the selected disease in Libya.

4. One Health surveillance joint risk assessment and reduction	
Activity (for the selected disease)	Information
4.1. Identification of areas at risk	<p>Description:</p> <p>Form task force to coordinate between sectors</p> <p>1- Identify the hazards by identify geographical areas within Libya known to have a high prevalence or high risk of Brucellosis transmission. This includes areas with high densities of susceptible livestock (sheep, goats, cattle, camels), regions with traditional animal husbandry practices, areas lacking effective animal vaccination programs, and areas with previously reported human or animal cases. Border regions may also be high-risk due to animal movement.</p> <p>2- Develop checklist and incidence forms</p> <p>3- Develop risk assessment matrix to identify the likelihood and consequences to evaluate the risks and find control measures</p> <p>3- Categorize the risks to determine the situation</p> <p>4- Update and review periodically</p>
	<p>Responsible:</p> <p>Ministry of Agriculture and Livestock, NACH National Centre for Disease Control (Zoonotic Diseases Department). Ministry of Health (Epidemiology and Primary Healthcare Departments). ESA, FDCC Veterinary quarantine stations and border checkpoints (POE).</p>
	<p>When:</p> <p>Annual assessment based on surveillance data. Continuous update upon reports of new incidence, outbreaks in previously unknown areas. Following periodic sero-epidemiological surveys for Brucellosis in livestock.</p>
	<p>Means:</p>

	<p>Surveillance data of human and animal Brucellosis cases and share the data. Maps showing livestock distribution and density. Information on pastoralist and animal movement patterns. Serological epidemiological survey data from animals. Reports from veterinary and public health laboratories. Geographic Information Systems (GIS) for mapping risk areas.</p> <p>Assumptions (Legal framework, equipment, tools, etc.) Existence of laws and regulations supporting zoonotic disease surveillance programs. Availability of software for data analysis and hot-spot identification. Capacity to conduct field surveys for data collection. Effective coordination for data sharing between sectors (Bulletins). Bio-RAM software</p>
4.2. Joint risk assessment implementation	<p>Description: Outline the process for conducting a joint risk assessment involving public health, animal health, and environmental sectors. This includes analyzing disease prevalence in animals and humans, identifying key transmission routes (e.g., unpasteurized milk, direct contact with infected animals, unsafe slaughtering practices), and evaluating the impact of local practices (consumption, animal rearing). The aim is to identify gaps and vulnerabilities in the prevention and response chain. Educate foreign labor and concentration centers</p> <p>Responsible: National Joint One Health Committee (if established). Joint task force Experts from relevant universities and research centers.</p> <p>When: Periodic assessment (e.g., bi-annually or when epidemiological changes occur). Rapid assessment in case of large or unexpected outbreaks.</p> <p>Means: Joint workshops for information exchange and analysis. Use of internationally recognized risk assessment tools (e.g., those from WHO or WOA). Collection and analysis of epidemiological and bacteriological laboratory data from both sectors.</p>

	Rapid surveys to assess practices and behaviors in at-risk communities.
	<p>Assumptions (Legal framework, equipment, tools, etc.)</p> <p>Clear protocols for sharing sensitive information between ministries.</p> <p>Training of personnel on risk assessment methodologies.</p> <p>Provision of necessary funding for joint meetings and workshops.</p> <p>Support from senior leadership for the One Health process.</p>
4.3. Joint field investigation (data collection)	<p>Description:</p> <p>Design and implement protocols for joint field investigations of suspected Brucellosis cases (human or animal). <u>This includes:</u></p> <p>For human cases: Collecting epidemiological information, exposure history (occupational, consumption of animal products), and blood samples for diagnosis.</p> <p>For animal cases: Identifying source animals, collecting samples (serum, milk, tissues), assessing rearing and grazing practices, and evaluating biosecurity conditions.</p> <p>Establishing the link between human and animal cases.</p> <p>Develop infographic matrix</p> <hr/> <p>Responsible:</p> <p>Joint rapid response teams (comprising human medical doctors, veterinarians, laboratory technicians).</p> <p>Local veterinary health departments and public health departments.</p> <p>Logistical support from local authorities.</p> <p>National Institution and International organization</p> <hr/> <p>When:</p> <p>Immediately upon notification of a confirmed or suspected human or animal case.</p> <p>When an unexplained increase in cases is registered in a specific area.</p> <hr/> <p>Means:</p> <p>Sterile sample collection kits for humans and animals</p> <p>Appropriate Personal Protective Equipment (PPE) for field workers.</p> <p>Standardized forms for epidemiological data collection in the field.</p> <p>Safe transport for samples to laboratories.</p> <p>GPS devices for mapping locations.</p>

	<p>Mobile data collection applications for rapid reporting.</p> <p>Assumptions (Legal framework, resources, equipment, tools, etc.):</p> <p>Legal authorization for field teams to access farms and households.</p> <p>Availability of trained and equipped field teams.</p> <p>Existence of reference laboratories capable of accurate and rapid Brucellosis diagnosis.</p> <p>Logistical support (vehicles, fuel, accommodation for teams).</p>
	<p>Assumptions (Legal framework, resources, equipment, tools, etc.)</p> <p>As above</p>
<p>4.4. Joint data analysis and interpretation of risks</p>	<p>Description:</p> <p>Analyze data collected from surveillance, field investigations, and laboratory results in an integrated manner to provide a comprehensive understanding of the Brucellosis risk. This includes:</p> <p>Analyzing the epidemiological link between human and animal cases.</p> <p>Identifying factors influencing disease spread (agricultural practices, animal movement, food consumption).</p> <p>Evaluating the effectiveness of current control and prevention measures.</p> <p>Providing evidence-based recommendations to decision-makers.</p> <hr/> <p>Responsible: Epidemiologists from the National Centre for Disease Control and the Animal Health Department.</p> <p>Biostatisticians.</p> <p>Laboratory scientists.</p> <p>A joint expert committee for interpretation and recommendations.</p> <hr/> <p>When:</p> <p>Continuously as new data become available.</p> <p>After each field investigation.</p> <p>During periodic risk assessment meetings.</p> <hr/> <p>Means:</p> <p>Statistical and epidemiological analysis software (e.g., Epi Info, R, Stata).</p> <p>Joint information systems to integrate human and animal health data.</p> <p>Regular meetings to discuss findings and interpretations.</p> <p>Dissemination of reports and analyses to relevant stakeholders.</p> <p>Assumptions (Legal framework, resources, equipment, tools, etc.):</p>

	<p>Clear policies for data sharing while maintaining privacy. Availability of qualified human resources in data analysis. Access to advanced analysis software and training. IT infrastructure to support data integration and sharing. To make this form more accurate and specific for Libya, you would need to provide concrete information such as: Exact names of specific governmental bodies and departments responsible for human and animal health in Libya. Existence of any current national strategies for Brucellosis control or zoonotic disease management. Available laboratory capacities (locations, types of Brucellosis tests offered). Identification of major geographical areas already affected by Brucellosis or with significant livestock populations. Details on any animal vaccination programs against Brucellosis in Libya, if they exist. Specific challenges facing inter-sectoral collaboration in Libya (e.g., resource shortages, security issues, weak infrastructure). I hope this framework serves as a useful starting point for you to complete the form thoroughly and accurately</p> <p>Assumptions (Legal framework, resources, equipment, tools, etc.)</p>
<p>4.5. Joint reporting to authorities</p>	<p>Description: Define unified and regular mechanisms for reporting Brucellosis cases (human and animal) and risk assessment results to higher authorities and relevant stakeholders at local and national levels. This should include reporting outbreaks, high-risk areas, and proposed recommendations.</p> <p>Responsible: National Centre for Disease Control (for human health data). Animal Health Department, Ministry of Agriculture and Livestock (for animal health data). National One Health Committee or Joint Team (for compiling reports). Security agencies and local authorities when enforcement measures are required.</p> <p>When: Immediately for emergency cases or outbreaks.</p>

	<p>Periodically (weekly/monthly) for routine reports. After each risk assessment or major field investigation.</p> <p>Means: Standardized and inter-sectoral reporting forms. Integrated information systems for electronic reporting. Regular coordination meetings with authorities. Secure and reliable communication channels (e.g., hotlines, official email).</p> <p>Assumptions (Legal framework, resources, equipment, tools, etc.)</p>
4.6. Joint decision-making about risk reduction measures	<p>Description Describe the process of joint decision-making among various sectors (Health, Agriculture, Environment, Trade) to develop and implement effective Brucellosis risk reduction measures. This includes developing response plans, identifying required resources, and allocating roles and responsibilities. Decisions should be based on joint risk assessment and available data.</p> <p>Responsible: High-level National One Health Committee (if established and active). Undersecretaries of relevant ministries or directors of key departments. Local leaders in affected areas.</p> <p>When: Immediately upon identification of a significant risk or outbreak. Periodically to review and update national control strategies. After each risk assessment to determine new preventive measures.</p> <p>Means: Decision-maker level meetings with participation from all sectors. National policies and strategies documents for Brucellosis control. Dedicated budgets for zoonotic disease control programs. Monitoring and evaluation systems for measure implementation.</p> <p>Assumptions (Legal framework, resources, equipment, tools, etc.)</p>
4.7. Joint dissemination of information	<p>Description:</p>

	<p>Define how crucial and updated information on Brucellosis (epidemiological situation, prevention tips, research developments) is disseminated to the public, relevant communities (farmers, butchers), healthcare and veterinary professionals, and international bodies. The goal is to ensure transparency and raise awareness.</p> <p>Responsible: Official spokespersons for the Ministries of Health and Agriculture. Awareness and Media departments in relevant agencies. National Centre for Disease Control. Partner civil society organizations.</p> <p>When: Regularly (e.g., monthly or quarterly reports). During outbreaks or significant changes in the epidemiological situation. During awareness campaigns.</p> <p>Means: Regularly (e.g., monthly or quarterly reports). During outbreaks or significant changes in the epidemiological situation. During awareness campaigns.</p> <p>Assumptions (Legal framework, resources, equipment, tools, etc.)</p>
<p>4.8. Joint public/community awareness</p>	<p>Description: Design and implement joint and targeted awareness campaigns for the public and at-risk communities (e.g., animal breeders, slaughterhouse workers, consumers) on Brucellosis risks, transmission routes, and the importance of preventive practices (e.g., boiling milk, safe animal handling, vaccination). Campaigns should be in simple, understandable language and consider the local cultural context.</p> <p>Responsible: Health Awareness departments at the Ministry of Health. Agricultural Extension departments at the Ministry of Agriculture. Civil society organizations, livestock breeder associations. Religious leaders and tribal elders to facilitate community access.</p> <p>Consider:</p> <p>When:</p>

	<p>Assumptions (Legal framework, resources, equipment, tools, etc.): Once you provide this information, I can help you structure it and suggest how it fits into the form.</p>
	<p>Means: Press conferences, press releases. Official websites and social media platforms. Publications, brochures, awareness posters. Training and awareness workshops for target groups. Collaboration with local and national media outlets.</p>
	<p>Assumptions (Legal framework, resources, equipment, tools, etc.)</p>
<p>4.9. Other relevant activities</p>	<p>Description: Any additional activities deemed necessary to enhance Brucellosis control within a One Health framework in Libya, not covered in previous sections. This could include: Developing joint research programs for a better understanding of local Brucellosis epidemiology. Strengthening laboratory capacities (human and veterinary) for advanced diagnostics. Capacity building and training of human resources on One Health concepts and Brucellosis control. Developing rapid epidemiological emergency response plans. Regional and international cooperation with neighboring countries or international organizations.</p>
	<p>Responsible: (Will depend on the specific activity)</p>
	<p>When: Continuously as part of strategic planning. Upon identification of capacity gaps or new needs. (Will depend on the specific activity)</p>
	<p>Means: (Will depend on the specific activity)</p>
	<p>Assumptions (Legal framework, resources, equipment, tools, etc.)</p>

Section 5. One Health surveillance coordinated early warning and preparedness

Day 3. Work in multisectoral groups.

Fill in the following table by describing practical and feasible coordinated early warning and preparedness activities to implement One Health surveillance for the selected disease in Libya.

5. One Health surveillance coordinated early warning and preparedness	
Activity (for the selected disease)	Information
5.1. Sharing data/information about events consistent with an outbreak (humans/animals) of the selected diseases (e.g. onset of heavy, prolonged rains, onset of increased mosquito populations, confirmation of animal case,	Description: Sharing data/information about events consistent with an outbreak (onset of heavy, prolonged rains; onset of widespread flooding, onset of increased mosquito populations, livestock disease consistent with the RVF case definition, cases of human febrile illness, confirmation of a human case etc.)
	Responsible: Ministry of Health (MoH) - Veterinary Services (Ministry of Agriculture and Livestock) - Environmental Protection Agency - National Center for Disease Control (NCDC) - Local health authorities and veterinary offices - Research institutions and universities
	When: Immediately upon detection of any suspicious event or case (human or animal). - Daily/weekly during high-risk periods (e.g., rainy season, periods of high mosquito activity). - Regularly scheduled meetings or communication channels for inter-sectoral sharing (e.g., monthly, quarterly). - After specific triggers (e.g., unusual rainfall patterns, reports of unexplained animal deaths, clusters of human febrile illness).

confirmation of a human case etc.)	<p>Means: Established reporting channels: Formal reporting lines from local to central levels within MoH and Veterinary Services. - Joint One Health platforms: Regular inter-sectoral meetings (physical or virtual) involving human health, animal health, and environmental sectors. - Digital communication: Secure email, dedicated communication platforms (e.g., WhatsApp groups for rapid alerts, if formally adopted and secure), online dashboards for data sharing (if available). - Public health alerts: Issuing official alerts or bulletins to relevant stakeholders. - Shared databases/information systems: Developing or utilizing integrated surveillance systems that allow for cross-sectoral data entry and access. - Training and awareness campaigns: Ensuring all relevant personnel are aware of reporting requirements and the importance of timely data sharing.</p>
	Assumptions (Legal framework, resources, equipment, tools, etc.)
5.2. Activation of joint alert mechanisms	<p>Description:</p> <hr/> <p>Responsible:</p> <hr/> <p>When:</p> <hr/> <p>Means:</p> <hr/> <p>Assumptions (Legal framework, resources, equipment, tools, etc.)</p>
5.3. Coordinate joint preparedness and response to outbreaks	<p>Description:</p> <hr/> <p>Responsible:</p> <hr/> <p>When:</p> <hr/> <p>Means:</p> <hr/> <p>Assumptions (Legal framework, resources, equipment, tools, etc.)</p>

5.4. Other relevant activities	Description:
	Responsible:
	When:
	Means:
	Assumptions (Legal framework, resources, equipment, tools, etc.)

Section 6. One Health surveillance multisectoral data collection and reporting (epizootic/epidemic period)

Day 3. Work in multisectoral groups.

Fill in the following table by describing practical and feasible multisectoral data collection and reporting activities during the epizootic/epidemic period to implement One Health surveillance for the selected disease in Libya.

<h3>6. One Health surveillance multisectoral data collection and reporting (epizootic/epidemic period)</h3>

Activity	Information
6.1. Mechanism to coordinate action during epizootic/epidemic period	Description:
	Responsible:
	When:
	Means:
	Assumptions (Legal framework, resources, equipment, tools, etc.)
6.2. Exchange of epidemiological information between sectors at local/governorate level	Description:
	Responsible:
	When:
	Means:
	Assumptions (Legal framework, resources, equipment, tools, etc.)
6.3. Exchange of epidemiological information between sectors at national level	Description:
	Responsible:
	When:
	Means:

	Assumptions (Legal framework, resources, equipment, tools, etc.)
6.4. Exchange of joint epidemiological information between local/governorate and national level	Description:
	Responsible:
	When:
	Means:
	Assumptions (Legal framework, resources, equipment, tools, etc.)
6.5. Joint field data collection	Description:
	Responsible:
	When:
	Means:
	Assumptions (Legal framework, resources, equipment, tools, etc.)
6.6. Joint data analysis and interpretation	Description:
	Responsible:
	When:
	Means:

	Assumptions (Legal framework, resources, equipment, tools, etc.)
6.7. Joint reporting to local/governorate authorities	Description:
	Responsible:
	When:
	Means:
	Assumptions (Legal framework, resources, equipment, tools, etc.)
6.8. Joint reporting to national authorities	Description:
	Responsible:
	When:
	Means:
	Assumptions (Legal framework, resources, equipment, tools, etc.)
6.9. Joint dissemination of information	Description:
	Responsible:
	When:
	Means:
	Assumptions (Legal framework, resources, equipment, tools, etc.)

6.10. Joint public/community awareness	Description:
	Responsible:
	When:
	Means:
	Assumptions (Legal framework, resources, equipment, tools, etc.)
6.11. Other relevant activities:	Description:
	Responsible:
	When:
	Means:
	Assumptions (Legal framework, resources, equipment, tools, etc.)

Section 7. One Health system surveillance assumptions

Day 4. Work in multisectoral groups.

Fill in the following table by describing practical and feasible multisectoral actions to address the assumptions identified so far to implement One Health surveillance system for the selected disease in Libya.

Add as many rows as needed.

7. One Health surveillance system assumptions management	
Assumptions	Information
7.1. Assumption name:	Actions to manage the assumption:
	Responsible:
	Means:
7.2. Assumption name:	Actions to manage the assumption:
	Responsible:
	Means:
7.3. Assumption name:	Actions to manage the assumption:
	Responsible:
	Means:

Section 8. OH surveillance next steps

Day 4. Work in multisectoral groups.

Fill in the following table by describing the next steps to implement One Health surveillance for the selected disease in Libya.

Consider steps linked to the finalization of the protocol, endorsement at national level, gaps and needs to meet the requirements for the implementation of the OH surveillance activities.

Add as many rows as needed.

Step	Responsible	Timeline

ACTION PLAN

Priority joint action	Description	Steps	Response	Timeline	Needed resources
Develop Advanced Data Network For all Sectors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The tool is used in understanding current situation, challenges, making sound decisions, and improving outcomes - Determine the needs assessment to 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1- Establish task force with clear objectives to ensure alignment with all sectors, foster data integration 2- identify the roles each sector in achieving the network objective of all institutions involved in uploading the data 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Develop effective communication channels using online platforms - Build trust through transparency, reliability of data - Monitor progress and evaluate impact 	3-6 months	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Purchase tap for data collection and server connected - Training for focal points on how to use the network

	<p>enhance OH capabilities</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Establish long term commitment and significant investment 	<p>3- data analysis and focused sound discussions</p> <p>4- determine security levels of sharing data (develop data exchange mechanism)</p> <p>5- Map existing system and data flows between involved partners</p> <p>6- develop the system that can interoperability to allow exchange data seamlessly and ensure reliable data exchange</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Identify the gaps and how to improve sharing of the data and perform impact assessments - Conduct maintenance and continuous improvement phases 		
Enhance laboratory diagnostic capacity					
	<p>1 Advanced Technology and Infrastructure</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Identify Needs and Gaps -technology Roadmap - human Resource Development Plan 			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Operating Budget - Maintenance and Repair - Scientists/Microbiologists/Pathologists - Medical Technologists/Laboratory Technicians - Adequate Laboratory Facilities

	<p>2- Skilled and Specialized Workforce</p> <p>3- Robust Quality Management Systems</p> <p>4- Integrated Data Management and Information Systems</p> <p>5- Efficient Supply Chains</p> <p>6- Networking and Collaboration</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Quality Management Plan - Data Integration Plan - Cross-Sectoral Training - Develop Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs) - Internal Quality Control - External Quality Assessment (EQA) - Accreditation Pursuit - Implement Laboratory Information Management System (LIMS) - Data Analysis and Utilization 			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Biosafety and Biosecurity Infrastructure - Diagnostic Reagents and Consumables
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Annex 7: VBDs template filled by the participants

Section 1a. One Health surveillance system design: scope and actors

Day 2. Work in multisectoral groups.

Fill in the following table by describing practical and feasible activities to design One Health surveillance for the selected diseases in Libya.

1. One Health surveillance system design	
Components (for the selected disease)	Description
1.1. Selected disease epidemiological situation in Libya	<p>RVF is a zoonotic viral disease transmitted primarily by mosquitoes.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Outbreaks have occurred sporadically in North Africa and the Sahel region. - Risk increases during periods of heavy rainfall and livestock movement. - Libya is vulnerable due to its livestock trade, seasonal vector activity, and climate variability.
1.2. Scope of <u>One Health</u> surveillance for the selected disease (Link the scope of OH surveillance to the epidemiological situation)	<p><i>Build and improve the capacity control of vector born diseases</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Develop early warning systems linking meteorological data, vector density, and livestock health/human health. - Monitor animal abortions, fever in herds, and wildlife mortality as trigger points. - Incorporate entomological and virological data for forecasting - Integrate data from veterinary labs, environmental sensors, and human clinics. - Link outbreak alerts to rapid joint interventions in high-risk zones.
1.3. Actors of <u>One Health</u> surveillance for the selected disease	<p>Human health– Passive cases detection at all PHCs and hospitals; active case finding through mobile clinics</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Weekly electronic reporting of suspect RVF (febrile hemorrhagic) and CL (skin ulcer) cases – Laboratory network linking regional labs to NCDC for IgM ELISA/PCR confirmation – Integration of human case alerts into national One Health dashboard

	<p>Animal health: – regularly syndromic monitoring of sentinel livestock (sheep, goats, camels) for abortions and fever</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Serosurveys (ELISA) in high-risk areas – control planning in outbreak zones (when human or animal cases detected) -Vector survey NCAH/NCDC <p>Environmental health: Training capacity for entomological surveys using ovitraps and CDC light traps for Aedes, Culex and Phlebotomus</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – training capacity for GIS-based risk mapping combining larval indices <p>METROLOGICAL DATA</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Rapid response spraying of larval habitats upon threshold exceedance – Coordination with MoA for integrated vector and reservoir control <p>Quarterly One Health Task Force meetings (MoH/MoA/ESA/FDA) to review integrated data</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -awareness campaigns in schools, markets and livestock fairs
<p>1.4. Type and timing/seasonality of <u>One Health</u> surveillance for the selected disease according to the scope of OH surveillance</p>	<p>Human health:</p> <p>Passive / active case detection</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Year-round with weekly reporting <p>Animal health:</p> <p>Passive surveillance around year</p> <p>Active surveillance – seasonally</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Syndromic herd monitoring & serosurveys – Monthly checks year-round – Extra field visits following heavy rain events or transhumance (July–Sept) <p>Environmental health:</p> <p>Entomological larval surveys & GIS risk mapping – Bi-weekly April–Nov</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Monthly Dec–March (dry season spot checks)

	<p>Other sectors: Community event-based reporting (abortion & bite alerts) </p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Continuous with district-level “trigger” thresholds – Quarterly inter-sectoral data reviews
<p>1.5. Geographical areas (at-risk areas/entire country) of <u>One Health</u> surveillance for the selected disease</p>	<p>Human health: Southern area and Western livestock markets</p>
	<p>Animal health: Southern area and Western livestock markets</p>
	<p>Environmental health: – Municipal waste sites and irrigation networks – Rodent burrow clusters in peri-urban areas</p>
	<p>Other sectors: Community hotspots identified via past outbreaks</p>
<p>1.6. Other information relevant for the design of the OH surveillance system for the selected disease</p>	<p>Human health: Ensure stockpiles of RVF POC tests and CL smear kits at district labs; – Incorporate clinical mentorship via tele-MD to support remote PHCs.</p>
	<p>Animal health: – Build in rapid diagnostic kits for RVF Ag detection at slaughterhouses; – Plan for ring-vaccination logistics (cold chain, personnel) in MoA contingency plans.</p>
	<p>Environmental health: – Link real-time weather data feeds (rainfall, NDVI) to larval survey triggers; – Standardise entomology SOPs across municipalities.</p>
	<p>Other sectors: – Develop community-facing dashboard with SMS alerts; – Seek sustainable funding via public–private partnerships and FAO/WHO grants; – Plan for after-action reviews following every outbreak to iterate surveillance design.</p>

Section 2. One Health surveillance cross-cutting activities

Fill in the following table by describing practical and feasible cross-cutting activities to all the pillars to implement One Health surveillance for the selected disease in Libya.

Glossary

Description: Describe the actions that the activity should cover

Responsible: Identify the responsible for the action

When: Timing of the action (every month, during a specific period etc.)

Means: Practical means that support the joint activity (excel file, meetings, shared human resources etc.)

Assumptions: Assumptions are the necessary conditions to implement the specific activity (legal framework, resources, equipment, tools, etc.)

2. One Health Surveillance: Cross-Cutting Activities (Libya – RVF & Leishmaniasis)

Activity	Description	Responsible	When	Means	Assumptions
2.1. Joint Governance Mechanism Meetings	Convene quarterly One Health Task Force meetings to align strategy across health, agriculture, environment, and academia . Review surveillance performance and coordinate interventions.	MoH, MoA, MoLG, MOE, NCDC, NCAH, ESA, FDCC.	Quarterly	Multi-sectoral meetings, shared agenda, coordination team	Legal mandate for governance structure; administrative support; political will Resource mobilization

<p>2.2. Definition & Update of Joint Indicators</p>	<p>Identify and revise joint indicators such as rainfall, vector density, animal abortions, human case spikes, and environmental risk factors.</p>	<p>MoH, MoA, MoLG, MOE, NCDC, NCAH, ESA, FDCC</p> <p>WHO, WOA, UNEP and FAO</p>	<p>Every 6 months</p>	<p>Technical meetings, indicator matrix (shared Excel sheets), epidemiological dashboards</p>	<p>Agreed indicator framework; historical baseline data; institutional collaboration</p> <p>And support from WHO, WOA, UNEP and FAO</p>
<p>2.3. Joint Monitoring & Evaluation (M&E)</p>	<p>Conduct simulation exercises (SimEx), protocol audits, and outcome evaluations to assess system responsiveness and coordination efficacy.</p>	<p>MoH, MoA, MoLG, MOE, NCDC, NCAH, ESA, FDCC</p> <p>WHO, WOA, UNEP and FAO</p>	<p>Annually (SimEx), Semi-annual protocol reviews</p>	<p>Review reports, field assessments, national dashboard, post-SimEx debriefs</p>	<p>Surveillance protocols in place; funding for evaluation activities; intersectoral M&E committee</p>

2.4. Joint Training on OH Surveillance Activities	Deliver co-developed training sessions on surveillance protocols, data collection, lab safety, and outbreak response procedures.	MoH, MoA, MoLG, MOE, NCDC, NCAH, ESA, FDCC WHO, WOA, UNEP and FAO	Every 3–6 months	Training workshops, manuals, simulation kits, joint field mentoring	Budget allocation; available trainers from all sectors; harmonized SOPs Evaluate training needs
2.5. Joint Agreements with External Partners	Formalize agreements with universities, NGOs (all relevant NGOs) , and private sector for surveillance data collection, diagnostic collaboration, and community outreach.	MoH, MoA, MoLG, MOE, NCDC, NCAH, ESA, FDCC WHO, WOA, UNEP and FAO	Annually; reviewed mid-year	OH MOU MOUs, shared reporting templates, technical working groups	Legal framework supporting data sharing; motivated stakeholders; clear terms of reference
2.6. Sharing Diagnostic Capacity	Share reagents, kits, lab expertise, and diagnostic SOPs between human and animal health labs. Enable	National Labs (Human & Veterinary); Regional Lab Network	Monthly coordination; emergency activation	Reagent inventories, logistics protocols, centralized	Policy supporting lab integration; adequate resources and

	dual use of mobile labs and reference facilities.		during outbreaks	coordination system	transport; biosafety norms
2.7. Other Relevant Activities	- Develop a real-time SMS alert system for RVF/leishmaniasis. - Establish a national entomology SOP repository. - Conduct post-outbreak After Action Reviews (AARs).	MoH ICT Unit + NCDC Surveillance Division + MoA Vector Control	SMS alerts: continuous; SOP updates: annual; AAR: post-outbreak	Online platforms, mobile tools, review templates	ICT infrastructure; national SOP endorsement; funding for AAR events

Section 3. One Health surveillance multisectoral routine data collection and reporting

Fill in the following table by describing practical and feasible multisectoral routine data collection and reporting activities during the interepidemic/interepizootic period to implement One Health surveillance for the selected disease.

3. One Health Surveillance: Routine Data Collection & Reporting – Libya (RVF & Leishmaniasis)

Activity	Description	Responsible	When	Means	Assumptions
3.1. Exchange of epidemiological information at	Human, animal, and environmental data shared at district (Local),	Local health offices (PHC and Hospitals), veterinary clinics (governmental and	Weekly, Monthly During epizootics and	Joint regular meetings, electronic (Whatsup excel Sheets)	Legal mandate for data sharing, staff availability,

local/governorate level	municipality and national levels to detect early patterns (e.g. fever cases, animal abortions, vector abundance).	private), municipal environmental teams	epidemics periods == Daily	or shared reporting templates	mobile internet access
3.2. Exchange of epidemiological information at national level	Integration of sectoral reports from sectors to national surveillance databases for trend analysis and dashboard updates.	NCDC, MoH Surveillance Dept, MoA NCAH Veterinary Surveillance Dept, ESA, MoLG, MOE and FDCC	Quarterly + Semi-annually During epizootics and epidemics periods == Daily/weekly	Centralized digital dashboard, email summaries, national coordination calls	Established reporting infrastructure, regular uploads from local level
3.3. Exchange of joint information between local/governorate	Bidirectional data flow enabling feedback, outbreak alerts, and prioritization	NCDC, MoH Surveillance Dept, MoA NCAH Veterinary Surveillance Dept,	Monthly with real-time alerts during risk periods	Data pipeline tools, WhatsApp groups for urgent	Commitment to integrated data systems, mobile communication channels

and national levels	of high-risk zones. Includes lab confirmations, field feedback.	ESA, MoLG, MOE and FDCC	During epizootics and epidemics periods == Daily	alerts, feedback forms	
3.4. Joint field data collection	Cross-sectoral teams collect clinical, entomological, veterinary, and environmental data during routine field visits.	Regional OH task teams (NCDC,NCAH,MOE,ESA) joint teams)	Every 2 months, intensified during rainy season & vector season (during alerts the collection will be at least 2-3 times a month)	Mobile data collection apps, GPS tracking, standardized forms	Transportation availability, joint field protocols (SOPs), fuel and logistics budget
3.5. Joint data analysis and interpretation	Harmonized data analysis by epidemiologists, veterinarians, and entomologists to identify trends and anomalies.	OH Analytical Cell (Surveillance, GIS specialists) from (NCDC,NCAH,MOE,ESA)	Quarterly & post-field missions During epizootics and epidemics	Shared dashboards, for analysis, and visual reports	Trained analysts, compatible data formats, common interpretation criteria

			periods = weekly		
3.6. Joint reporting to local/governorate authorities	Sectoral updates translated into usable decision-making reports for local authorities and health directors.	Surveillance officers (NCDC and NCAH) at governorate level	Monthly & during season transitions During epizootics and epidemics periods == Daily	Policy briefs, summary tables, heat maps	Stakeholder engagement, acceptance of joint recommendations
3.7. Joint reporting to national authorities	Consolidated OH reports prepared for ministries with recommendations for seasonal preparedness and hotspot control measures.	OH taskforce team	Every quarter	National OH briefings, policy memos, electronic bulletins	Political support, inter-ministerial commitment, up-to-date data

3.8. Joint dissemination of information	Sharing data publicly and across sectors: via dashboards, newsletters, SMS alerts, and community boards.	OH taskforce team	Monthly, emergency push alerts	Online platforms, infographics, SMS alerts, localized bulletin boards	Communication tools, translation capacities, communication approval
3.9. Joint public/community awareness	Community engagement on disease prevention, recognizing symptoms, and reporting events like dog bites or sandfly exposure.	OH taskforce team	Bimonthly sessions + during vector seasons	Flyers, TV + Radio broadcasts, school events, social media and farmers associations	Educational materials, community trust, multilingual outreach
3.10. Other relevant activities	- Surveillance drills to test system functionality	One Health Simulation & Field Support Units WHO, WOA, FAO	Semi-annually + Annually	SimEx protocols, mobile surveys, satellite	Funding availability, trained drill facilitators,

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Feedback collection from field teams - Updating GIS maps and entomology databases 	UNEP		mapping tools	working mapping software
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Section 4. One Health surveillance joint risk assessment and reduction

Fill in the following table by describing practical and feasible joint risk assessment and reduction activities to implement One Health surveillance for the selected disease in Libya.

4. One Health Surveillance: Joint Risk Assessment & Reduction (RVF & Leishmaniasis – Libya)

Activity	Description	Responsible	When	Means	Assumptions
4.1. Identification of Areas at Risk	Use GIS mapping of past outbreaks, vector habitats, and high-risk zones based on environmental, livestock trade and movement, and human migration data.	OH taskforce team	Twice yearly + Epizootic / Epidemics periods	GIS software, metrological data, historical case records neighbor country report	Access to mapping tools; intersectoral information sharing agreements; trained GIS analysts

<p>4.2. Joint Risk Assessment Implementation</p>	<p>Conduct coordinated risk assessments in priority districts by collecting vector, animals, and human case data.</p>	<p>OH taskforce team</p>	<p>Every 6 months and after notable environmental alerts and epizootics /Epidemics periods</p>	<p>Risk assessment checklist, simulation models, stakeholder interviews</p>	<p>National One Health risk framework; technical assessment tools; team mobilization capacity Joint training of the staff</p>
<p>4.3. Joint Field Investigation (Data Collection)</p>	<p>Investigate hotspots using joint teams to collect samples, assess vector presence, and record human and animal symptoms.</p>	<p>OH taskforce team</p>	<p>During rainfall peaks, post-alerts, and vector seasons Epizootics /Epidemics periods</p>	<p>SOPs, Field kits, mobile labs, entomological traps, medical equipment, and sample collection tools</p>	<p>Availability of vehicles; access permits; stocked field kits; logistics support Joint capacity building</p>
<p>4.4. Joint Data Analysis & Interpretation of Risks</p>	<p>Merge and analyze data from multiple sectors to determine disease risk levels and geographic spread likelihood.</p>	<p>OH taskforce team</p>	<p>Quarterly and post-investigation</p>	<p>Shared databases, joint review workshops / meetings</p>	<p>Agreed SOPs for analysis; compatible data formats; time-bound workflows Enforcement of Risk assess</p>
<p>4.5. Joint Reporting to Authorities</p>	<p>Consolidate findings into sectoral and national-level risk briefings with recommendations for</p>	<p>OH taskforce team</p>	<p>After each assessment & investigation and</p>	<p>Briefing templates, joint communication tools</p>	<p>Sectoral commitment; reporting protocol; responsive</p>

	making decision for control measures.		epizootics /Epidemics periods		communication channels
4.6. Joint Decision-Making on Risk Reduction Measures	Jointly decide on interventions (controlling animal movement, spraying, vaccination, public alerts, lab strengthening) based on risk levels.	OH taskforce team	Following each reporting cycle	-SOPS (guidance) -Decision recommendations - cross-sector meetings,	- Political stability - resource availability - intersectoral trust
4.7. Joint Dissemination of Information	Sharing data publicly and across sectors: via dashboards, newsletters, SMS alerts, and community boards.	OH taskforce team	Monthly, emergency push alerts	Online platforms, infographics, SMS alerts, localized bulletin boards	Communication tools, translation capacities, communication approval
4.8. Joint Public/Community Awareness	Community engagement on disease prevention, recognizing symptoms, and reporting events like dog bites or sandfly exposure.	OH taskforce team	Bimonthly sessions + during vector seasons	Flyers, TV + Radio broadcasts, school events, social media and farmers associations	Educational materials, community trust, multilingual outreach
4.9. Other Relevant Activities	- Develop shared entomology SOPs - Pilot predictive modeling for outbreak triggers	OH taskforce team	Annually for SOPs and drills; monthly for modeling updates	SOP manuals, modeling software, meeting facilitation tools	Expert availability; cross-sector endorsement; funding support

	- Plan periodic tabletop exercises to test coordination				
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Section 5. One Health surveillance coordinated early warning and preparedness

Fill in the following table by describing practical and feasible coordinated early warning and preparedness activities to implement One Health surveillance for the selected disease in Libya.

5. Coordinated Early Warning & Preparedness – Libya (RVF & Leishmaniasis)

Activity	Description	Responsible	When	Means	Assumptions
5.1. Sharing data/information about potential outbreak events	Collect and exchange meteorological alerts (e.g. heavy rainfall), entomological data (mosquito/sandfly density), and first human or animal case confirmations.	OH taskforce team	- Weekly monitoring - immediate sharing upon detection	Shared data dashboards, email alerts, SMS triggers, joint monitoring protocols WhatsApp groups for urgent alerts, feedback forms	Agreement on sharing thresholds, access to real-time weather and lab data, field information, and secure digital communication
5.2. Activation of joint alert mechanisms	Launch coordinated alerts across sectors when a risk threshold is exceeded (e.g. vector abundance, confirmed	OH taskforce team	Within 24–48 hours of meeting risk trigger	Early Warning System (EWS), email + SMS chains, press	Legal authority for alerts; trusted communication channels; technical

	zoonotic case). Mobilize surveillance and control plans.			briefings, local activation teams	protocols for risk verification
5.3. Coordinate joint preparedness and response to outbreaks	Develop and activate response protocols: vaccination (for RVF), vector control, case investigation, lab mobilization, and community awareness.	OH taskforce team	Trigger-based activation; readiness reviewed monthly	SOPs, logistics plans, cold chain access, stockpiled supplies, community outreach tools	Funding for field response, shared logistics, skilled personnel in remote areas
5.4. Other relevant activities	- Maintain dynamic risk maps - Conduct seasonal readiness reviews - Update mobile app notifications- Practice response protocols via tabletop exercises and drills	OH taskforce team	Risk map: monthly Readiness reviews: quarterly Drills: annually	Simulation EX GIS systems, mobile app platforms, simulation kits, after-action review templates	Functional risk modeling tools, communication infrastructure, endorsement of protocols by all sectors

Section 6. One Health surveillance multisectoral data collection and reporting (epizootic/epidemic period)

Day 3. Work in multisectoral groups.

Fill in the following table by describing practical and feasible multisectoral data collection and reporting activities during the epizootic/epidemic period to implement One Health surveillance for the selected disease in Libya.

6. One Health Surveillance – Multisectoral Data Collection & Reporting (Epidemic Period)

Activity	Description	Responsible	When	Means	Assumptions
6.1. Mechanism to coordinate action	Activate emergency coordination cells	OH Task Force (MoH, MoA, ESA, NCDC) other relevant	Within 24 hours of outbreak confirmation	Crisis coordination meetings rapid response protocols, communication tools.	Legal cover Emergency SOPs; coordination personnel. Hotlines
6.2. Local Exchange of Epidemiological Info	Share real-time outbreak data across all sectors	Local Surveillance Officers OH Task Force (MoH, MoA, ESA, NCDC) other relevant, MoE	Daily during outbreaks	Shared spreadsheets, WhatsApp channels,	Hotline Multilingual tools Trained personals SOPs
6.3. National Exchange of Epidemiological Info	Merge reports from affected local to national authorities to assess national-level situation	OH Task Force (MoH, MoA, ESA, NCDC) other relevant, MoE	Daily/Weekly	Regular reports	Dashboard
6.4. Local–National Joint Info Exchange	Ensure continuous two-way communication	OH Task Force (MoH, MoA, ESA, NCDC) other relevant, MoE	Real-time; Daily/Weekly	email summaries, secure cloud folders	Internet access

				WhatsApp channels,	
6.5. Joint Field Data Collection	Cross-sectoral teams collect clinical, entomological, veterinary, and environmental data during routine field visits.	Mobile Response Teams (MoH/MoA/ESA/MoE)	Daily to weekly depending on outbreak dynamics	Apps, GPS tracking,	Transportation availability, joint field protocols (SOPs) Resource mobilization
6.6. Joint Data Analysis & Risk Interpretation	Conduct coordinated reviews of outbreak data.	Joint Analysis Cells (OH Task Force (MoH, MoA, ESA, NCDC) other relevant, MoE)	Twice weekly	Data integration tools, maps, statistical software	Staff capacity
6.7. Joint Reporting to Local Authorities	Provide summarized outbreak status updates and response options	Surveillance Coordination Officers OH Task Force (MoH, MoA, ESA, NCDC) other relevant, MoE	Twice Weekly	Infographics, summary briefs, interactive dashboards	
6.8. Joint Reporting to National Authorities	Consolidated national-level summary of outbreak developments, gaps, and recommendations	OH Task Force (MoH, MoA, ESA, NCDC) other relevant, MoE	Bi-weekly & post-assessment	Situation reports, strategic bulletins, outbreak heat maps	Political support; national endorsement for OH approach; clear SOPs

6.9. Joint Dissemination of Information	Share verified information with the public, NGOs	Communication Units OH Task Force (MoH, MoA, ESA, NCDC) other relevant, MoE	As outbreak evolves (weekly minimum)	SMS alerts, TV / radio reports, press releases, public dashboard	Approval for messaging; community access to media; translation into local languages
6.10. Joint Public/Community Awareness	Community engagement on disease prevention, recognizing symptoms, and reporting events like dog bites or sandfly exposure	Municipal outreach teams, OH Task Force (MoH, MoA, ESA, NCDC) other relevant, MoE	Ongoing during outbreaks (weekly sessions)	Flyers, school outreach, social media	Willingness to engage; trained educators; materials tailored to cultural context
6.11. Other Relevant Activities	- Outbreak drills to test system response - After Action Reviews (AAR) post-epidemic - Deployment of surge diagnostic kits to outbreak zones	OH Technical Units + Rapid Logistics Teams OH Task Force (MoH, MoA, ESA, NCDC) other relevant, MoE	AAR: post-epidemic Drills: mid-outbreak Diagnostic kits: within 72 hrs of case confirmation	SimEx protocols, feedback templates, emergency procurement workflow	Budget allocation; field team availability; updated supply chain info

Section 7. One Health system surveillance assumptions

Day 4. Work in multisectoral groups.

Fill in the following table by describing practical and feasible multisectoral actions to address the assumptions identified so far to implement One Health surveillance system for the selected disease in Libya.

Add as many rows as needed.

7. One Health Surveillance System Assumptions Management – Libya (RVF & Leishmaniasis)

Assumption Name	Actions to Manage the Assumption	Responsible	Means
7.1. Legal framework for data sharing across sectors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Draft and endorse a national One Health Memorandum of Understanding (MoU) that defines roles, data-sharing protocols, and coordination mechanisms - Advocate for ministerial decrees to formalize intersectoral collaboration. 	OH Task Force teams (MoH, MoA, MoE, ESA, NCDC, NCAH,)	Legal drafting workshops, inter-ministerial meetings, technical support from WHO/FAO
7.2. Availability of trained personnel for joint field activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Develop a national roster of trained field investigators from all sectors - Conduct regular joint training and simulation exercises. 	Public Health Institute, Veterinary Training Centers, ESA	Training curricula, simulation kits, field deployment SOPs
7.3. Access to real-time meteorological and environmental data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Establish a data-sharing agreement with the National Meteorological Authority - Integrate NDVI and rainfall data into the OH surveillance dashboard. 	ESA + NCDC ICT Unit	API integration, GIS platforms, shared data protocols

7.4. Diagnostic capacity and logistics for outbreak response	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Pre-position diagnostic kits and PPE in regional labs - Develop a joint logistics plan for emergency deployment. 	National Labs (MoH & MoA), Logistics Units	Inventory management tools, cold chain logistics, emergency procurement plans
7.5. Community trust and participation in surveillance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Engage local leaders, schools, and NGOs in awareness campaigns - Establish feedback mechanisms (e.g., SMS hotlines, community meetings). 	Municipal Health Offices, NGOs, Community Health Workers	IEC materials, mobile communication tools, participatory workshops
7.6. Interoperability of data systems across sectors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Harmonize data collection tools and formats - Develop a shared digital platform for OH data entry and visualization. 	NCDC Surveillance Division + MoA IT Unit	Shared dashboards, standardized Excel templates, cloud-based systems
7.7. Sustainable funding for OH surveillance activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Develop a multi-year OH investment plan - Engage donors (FAO, WHO, EU) and explore public-private partnerships. 	MoH Planning Dept + OH Secretariat	Donor proposals, budget advocacy briefs, stakeholder roundtables

Section 8. OH surveillance next steps

Day 4. Work in multisectoral groups.

Fill in the following table by describing the next steps to implement One Health surveillance for the selected disease in Libya.

Consider steps linked to the finalization of the protocol, endorsement at national level, gaps and needs to meet the requirements for the implementation of the OH surveillance activities.

Add as many rows as needed.

Next Steps for Implementing One Health Surveillance – Libya (RVF & Leishmaniasis)

Priority	Description	Step	Responsible	Timeline	Needed resources
Establishment of Communication between sectors	Establishment of Communication at local and national levels	Simple / WhatsApp Any other communication available	OH Technical Working Group (MoH, MoA, MoE, NCDC, NCAH, ESA) Academia	Month 1–2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Fund allocation ➤ Training ➤ Equipment
Review / Develop SOPS.	Communication and data sharing standards, to include essential information	Through stakeholder consultation workshops at national and local levels	OH Technical Working Group (MoH, MoA, MoE, NCDC, NCAH, ESA)	Month 2–3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Fund allocation ➤ Expertise
Agreed templates for data sharing	Joint template to be in action	Intersectoral meetings	OH Technical Working Group (MoH, MoA, MoE, NCDC, NCAH, ESA)	Month 3-6	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Fund allocation ➤ Training
Develop / validate case definition	Develop case definition for VBD in NCAH NCDC, review and validation	Per sector meeting	Each sector NCAH NCDC	Month 3–4	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Fund allocation ➤ Expertise ➤ International organization

Joint response / investigation plans / SOPs	Building and strengthening joint investigation and response plans	Intersectoral meetings and workshops	OH Technical Working Group (MoH, MoA, MoE, NCDC, NCAH, ESA)	Month 6-9	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Fund allocation ➤ Expertise ➤ International organization
Metrological and GIS establishment Remote sensing⁰	Train MOE staff on how to use Metrological data	Training Procure and train on GIS	Expertise, governmental and international organization	Month 7–12	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Fund allocation ➤ Expertise ➤ International organization
Mosquito collection and identification	Use of mosquito as trigger for raising alerts	Train the ESA staff to how to collect mosquito data.	NCDC	Month 8–14	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Fund allocation
Dashboard for surveillance	To build a national data center that can be accessed through all sectors	Build the dashboard and train all sectors	ITC in all sectors	1–2 years	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Fund allocation ➤ Expertise ➤ International organization

Annex 8: Rabies digitalized flowchart

Rabies Surveillance and Information Sharing

Red arrows refer to **Notification** Other colored arrows refer to **information sharing between sectors**

Annex 9: Brucellosis digitalized flowchart

- = Headquarters level
- = Field/operational level
- = Ministry level
- = International organizations
- = Direct reporting
- = Coordination
- = Informal communication

Annex 10: VBDs digitalized flowchart

TRIGGER

- Metrological
- Susp. Cases
- Sero-Prevalance
- Vector Ab.

